

**ANALELE
UNIVERSITĂȚII DIN ORADEA**

**FASCICULA: ECOTOXICOLOGIE,
ZOOTEHNIE ȘI TEHNOLOGII DE
INDUSTRIE ALIMENTARĂ**

**VOL. XXIII / B
ANUL 23**

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2024**

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STUDY REGARDING THE IMPACT OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING ON LABOR MARKET INTEGRATION IN THE SPA TOURISM SECTOR. A CASE STUDY OF THE HENRI COANDĂ POST-SECONDARY SCHOOL NETWORK

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This research explores how professional training impacts labor market integration within the spa tourism industry, specifically examining the AMBFKTR program offered by the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network. The goal is to understand the connection between the number of students enrolled in the AMBFKTR program and their subsequent employment in Romania and the EU. A survey was sent to the heads of schools in the Henri Coandă network to collect data on student enrollment, graduation rates, reasons for dropout, and employment outcomes in the spa tourism field. The findings indicate notable differences in employment success across the network. Schools in larger urban areas have higher rates of graduate placement in the spa tourism sector, while institutions in smaller areas face greater difficulty in securing relevant jobs for their graduates. Dropout reasons were mainly due to personal challenges, financial constraints, and scheduling issues. Additionally, while some schools had high employment rates in the spa tourism sector, others showed a weaker connection between the training provided and labor market needs. The research concludes that the success of vocational programs in spa tourism depends on local labor market conditions, the quality of collaboration with the industry, and the alignment of curricula with the evolving demands of the sector. The study calls for stronger partnerships between educational institutions and the tourism industry to improve graduate employability. Future research should expand the focus to include a wider range of institutions and examine the long-term career paths of graduates to assess the lasting impact of these training programs on employment in the spa tourism sector.

Keywords: professional training, labor market integration, spa tourism, vocational education, graduate employability

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INTRODUCTION

We believe that the successful transition of trained professionals into the workforce is one of the clearest indicators of the effectiveness of vocational programs. The spa tourism sector, which continues to expand globally, relies heavily on skilled professionals to meet the growing demand for wellness and health-related services (Neto, 2020). However, there seems to be a lack of research that directly explores how vocational training affects labor market inclusion within this specific sector. We decided to investigate this gap by focusing on the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School

Network, particularly the AMBFKTR (Assistant Manager in Tourism and Hotel Management) program. By doing so, we hoped to better understand how trends in training influence employment outcomes in the industry.

Our decision to study the Henri Coandă Network was driven by its reputation as one of Romania's largest and most respected networks of vocational schools. The network's broad geographic reach and track record of preparing graduates for key sectors, including spa tourism, made it an ideal case study. Moreover, the wealth of data available on student enrollment and graduate outcomes in the AMBFKTR program offered a solid foundation for analyzing trends that could be relevant to

the broader field. In our opinion, the Henri Coandă Network provides a unique opportunity to explore the intersection of professional training and labor market success in a growing and dynamic sector.

We've noticed that previous studies have consistently highlighted the role of vocational training in improving employability (Pardo-Garcia and Barac, 2020; Li and Pilz, 2023; Beer and Mulder, 2020; Succi and Canovi, 2020). For example, Stacey (2015) pointed out how skill-based education is key to helping individuals adapt to the labor market, especially in specialized fields like tourism and hospitality. Similarly, Mooney and Baum (2019) emphasized the importance of targeted training to meet the ever-changing needs of the tourism industry. While these studies provide useful insights, they don't fully address the unique demands and employment trends within the spa tourism sector. We believe that this gap in research is something worth exploring, and our study aims to add to the growing understanding of vocational training's impact on sector-specific job outcomes.

The real value of this study, in our view, lies in its originality and its potential to create meaningful change. We are looking to explore the connection between the number of students enrolled in the AMBFKTR program and their subsequent success in securing employment in the spa tourism industry. By doing so, we hope to not only evaluate the effectiveness of the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network's training but also provide useful insights for educators and policymakers who aim to better align vocational education with the actual needs of the labor market (Lopez, 2020).

Our hypothesis is simple yet important: we believe there is a positive correlation between the number of students who complete the AMBFKTR program and their ability to find jobs in the spa tourism sector. We expect this trend to be influenced by factors like the quality of training, how well the curriculum matches industry demands, and how effectively the network fosters practical skills that can be applied in real-world settings.

Aim and objectives

The main goal of our research is to examine how the professional training provided by the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network influences the integration of graduates into the labor market, specifically within the spa tourism sector. We have outlined several specific objectives to guide our investigation:

1. To assess trends in enrollment for the AMBFKTR specialization over the past three years.
2. To analyze the employment outcomes of AMBFKTR graduates in the spa tourism sector, both in Romania and the European Union.
3. To identify key factors that impact the labor market inclusion of graduates, focusing on the quality of training and how well it aligns with industry needs.
4. To offer recommendations for improving vocational training programs to better support labor market success in the spa tourism sector.

By addressing these objectives, we hope to provide valuable insights both practically and theoretically to the fields of vocational education and labor market studies, with a particular focus on the growing spa tourism industry.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research centers on the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network, a well-established network of vocational training institutions across Romania. These institutions specialize in various fields, including spa tourism through the AMBFKTR program. We chose this network due to its strong reputation, its alignment with the demands of the spa tourism sector, and the availability of valuable data for analyzing the outcomes of professional training.

Research design

A mixed-methods approach was employed for this study, combining both quantitative data collection and descriptive analysis. The primary data collection tool was a structured questionnaire, which was sent to the heads of institutions within the Henri Coandă school network.

Questionnaire structure

The questionnaire was designed to collect comprehensive information on student enrollment, graduation rates, dropout reasons, and post-graduation employment outcomes. The questions were organized into the following categories:

- Enrollment trends: number of students enrolled in the AMBFKTR specialization over the past three academic years (2021–2022, 2022–2023, 2023–2024).
- Graduation metrics: total number of graduating cohorts for the AMBFKTR specialization to date.

- Dropout analysis: number of students who dropped out over the last three years and reasons for dropping out, including financial difficulties, personal issues, or curriculum misalignment.

- Employment outcomes: number of graduates employed in Romania and the European Union and number of graduates working in roles directly related to their field of study.

Data collection process

The questionnaire was distributed electronically to the institutional heads within a specific time frame, ensuring consistency across all participating schools in the network. Respondents were asked to provide accurate data based on institutional records to maintain the reliability of the information.

Ethical considerations

To respect the rights and privacy of participants, this study was carried out strictly in accordance with ethical standards. All participating institutions gave their prior agreement, and survey respondents were made aware of the study's objectives, their part in it, and that participation was entirely optional. Respondents were guaranteed anonymity, and the utmost level of confidentiality was

maintained by handling personal data in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Tikkinen-Piri, Rohunen and Markkula,2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we share the results from our analysis of the data collected through the questionnaire, which focused on student enrollment trends, dropout rates, and employment outcomes after graduation within the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network. The data we examined reveals patterns in how students in the AMBFKTR specialization have progressed, and how these trends relate to their entry into the labor market, particularly within the spa tourism sector. From our perspective, this analysis not only sheds light on the effectiveness of the program but also offers useful insights into how vocational training in this field can better align with industry demands.

For the first question regarding the number of students enrolled in the AMBFKTR specialization over the past three academic years, the data gathered from the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network is as follows:

Table 1

Student enrollment distribution by year and academic year

Academic year	Total students	Year I	Year II	Year III
2021-2022	121	26	21	24
2022-2023	69	17	23	15
2023-2024	76	26	15	20

Source: own elaboration based on the results of the questionnaire

The data we gathered provides an overview of how students are distributed across the first, second, and third years of the AMBFKTR specialization during each academic year. We noticed a slight decline in overall enrollment, from 121 students in the 2021-2022 academic year to 69 in 2022-2023. However, there was a modest recovery in 2023-2024, with 76 students enrolled in total. Interestingly, the distribution across the years varied, with Year I seeing a noticeable increase in 2023-2024 (26 students), while Year II and Year III experienced a drop. In our opinion, this fluctuation could reflect factors like retention rates and other influences on student

enrollment trends, which may warrant further investigation.

We also looked at the number of graduating classes from the AMBFKTR program across different Henri Coandă Post-Secondary Schools. This data is key to understanding the maturity and overall success of the program in various locations within the network. The number of graduating classes is an indicator of each institution's operational history and stability, which can give us insights into how well their training programs are functioning. These figures also shed light on trends in student retention, the longevity of the program, and how well the schools are able to meet the growing demands of the spa tourism industry.

By examining these graduation patterns, we can better understand the factors that influence student success and their integration into the labor market.

Table 2

Number of graduating classes by school	
School	Number of graduating classes
Henri Coandă Brad	0
Henri Coandă Turda	12
Henri Coandă Constanța	17 (first class 2008)
Henri Coandă Oradea	22
Henri Coandă Ștei	0
Henri Coandă Baia Mare	16
Henri Coandă Timișoara	11

Source: own elaboration based on the results of the questionnaire

Our analysis of graduation numbers across different institutions reveals two clear trends. Schools such as Oradea, with 22 graduating classes, and Constanța, with 17, show a long-standing history and strong stability in their AMBFKTR programs. These institutions have experienced growth and higher graduation rates, which, in our view, reflects the positive impact of sustained program development. This finding aligns with the work of Mooney and Baum (2019) who argued that vocational programs with a longer history are more likely to produce higher graduation rates. On the other hand, schools like Brad and Ștei, which have yet to graduate any students, may be facing challenges tied to their recent establishment or limited regional demand and resources. This is consistent with the observations of Stacey (2015), who emphasized the role of local industry demand in shaping graduation outcomes.

We also looked at the dropout rates for the AMBFKTR specialization over the past three academic years across the Henri Coandă post-secondary schools. This data is crucial for understanding student retention and identifying the factors contributing to higher dropout rates, such as personal, academic, or financial difficulties. We believe that dropout rates are an important measure of the effectiveness and sustainability of vocational programs, especially in specialized fields like spa tourism. By examining the trends in dropout rates across different schools, we can gain valuable insights into how various factors, including regional differences and institutional

support, play a role in student retention and overall success.

Table 3

Number of students dropped out by school	
School	Number of students dropped out
Henri Coandă Brad	-
Henri Coandă Turda	8
Henri Coandă Constanța	27
Henri Coandă Oradea	33 (including 8 exmatriculated)
Henri Coandă Ștei	2
Henri Coandă Baia Mare	23 (2021/2022); 10 (2022/2023); 17 (2023/2024)
Henri Coandă Timișoara	41

Source: own elaboration based on the results of the questionnaire

Dropout rates in vocational education programs are influenced by a combination of institutional, personal, and socio-economic factors. Based on our research and previous studies, such as those by Mooney and Baum (2019) and Stacey (2015) high dropout rates can significantly impact the success of professional training programs, especially in specialized fields like spa tourism. From our perspective, understanding the specific reasons behind student dropouts could provide us with crucial insights into how to improve retention strategies and enhance the overall success of the AMBFKTR program within the Henri Coandă post-secondary school network.

Next, we examine the various reasons students drop out of the AMBFKTR specialization. Identifying these underlying causes is vital for finding ways to improve retention and ensure the effectiveness of vocational education programs in sectors like spa tourism. We found that several factors contribute to student dropout, including financial difficulties, personal or family issues, health concerns, and the challenge of balancing work with academic responsibilities. By looking at the reasons students provided for leaving the program, we hope to highlight the most common obstacles to academic persistence. This analysis could provide valuable insights to develop future support mechanisms, helping improve retention rates and better align the training with labor market outcomes.

Table 4

Reasons for dropping out by school	
School	Reasons for dropping out
Henri Coandă Brad	-
Henri Coandă	Inability to attend day classes /

Turda	financial reasons
Henri Coandă Constanța	Inability to attend day classes / financial reasons
Henri Coandă Oradea	Busy personal schedule, could not attend classes consecutively, financial issues
Henri Coandă Ștei	Finances
Henri Coandă Baia Mare	Personal reasons, workplace schedule, personal medical reasons
Henri Coandă Timișoara	Personal reasons, workplace schedule, personal medical reasons

Source: own elaboration based on the results of the questionnaire

From our analysis, it's clear that financial and personal challenges are the primary reasons behind student dropouts in the AMBFKTR program. This highlights the need for focused interventions that can address these obstacles and improve student retention in vocational training programs.

When we looked at employment outcomes for AMBFKTR graduates, we found considerable variation across institutions. Henri Coandă Oradea reported the highest number of employed graduates, with 242 individuals securing jobs, suggesting a strong local demand for spa tourism professionals. On the other hand, Henri Coandă Ștei had no employed graduates, which may be linked to the limited job opportunities in the region for this specific field.

Henri Coandă Baia Mare showed a 90% employment rate, demonstrating the program's success in preparing students for the labor market. Similarly, Henri Coandă Timișoara had 165 graduates employed, indicating good integration both locally and within the broader EU labor market.

These findings reveal that labor market outcomes are influenced by a variety of factors, including regional job demand and the level of institutional support in helping graduates find employment. The data on employment within the spa tourism sector shows a mixed picture, with some schools experiencing strong results while others face challenges in aligning their training programs with market needs. This reflects the diverse nature of regional job markets and the importance of adapting curricula to better meet industry demands.

Table 5

Employment in the field of study

School	Number of graduates employed in their field of study
Henri Coandă Brad	-
Henri Coandă Turda	9
Henri Coandă Constanța	10
Henri Coandă Oradea	50% (of total graduates)
Henri Coandă Ștei	0
Henri Coandă Baia Mare	55% (of total graduates)
Henri Coandă Timișoara	132

Source: own elaboration based on the results of the questionnaire

The results show a mixed level of success in placing graduates into roles within their specialized field of study. For example, Henri Coandă Timișoara has a notable number of graduates working directly in spa tourism, while Henri Coandă Ștei reports no graduates employed in this field, which may be due to a lack of local demand for specialized professionals.

At Henri Coandă Oradea and Henri Coandă Baia Mare, the employment rates in spa tourism are 50% and 55%, respectively. This indicates that while a good number of graduates are finding jobs, only a portion are employed in their specialized area, possibly reflecting the broader challenges in the spa tourism job market.

These results underline the importance of strong connections between educational institutions and the local job market. In our view, improving career services, expanding internship opportunities, and building partnerships with industry players could help better match graduates' skills with available job opportunities in the sector, ultimately improving employment outcomes in the field.

The findings from the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network's AMBFKTR program highlight notable differences in the employment outcomes of graduates, particularly when it comes to securing jobs within their specialized field and overall employment across Romania and the EU. Institutions like Henri Coandă Timișoara and Henri Coandă Oradea have shown success in aligning their programs with market demand, while schools such as Henri Coandă Ștei have faced challenges in helping graduates find work within the spa tourism sector.

This variation points to the importance of local labor market conditions, regional demand for specialized skills, and the

effectiveness of industry connections in shaping employment outcomes. Schools in areas with stronger tourism sectors, especially those in larger urban centers, tend to have higher success rates in placing graduates into the spa tourism workforce. On the other hand, institutions in less developed regions may struggle to match graduates with relevant job opportunities.

Additionally, the proportion of graduates securing jobs in spa tourism reinforces the significance of industry-specific training. While some schools, such as Henri Coandă Baia Mare, have achieved high rates of employment within the field, other schools have seen many graduates seeking employment outside their specialized area.

These results highlight the ongoing need for closer collaboration between educational institutions, industry stakeholders, and local job markets. Moving forward, efforts should be directed toward strengthening industry partnerships, expanding internship opportunities, and adapting curricula to meet the evolving needs of the spa tourism sector.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has examined the effect of professional training in the AMBFKTR specialization at the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network, focusing on how it relates to labor market integration in Romania and the EU. The results show different levels of success in employment outcomes across various Henri Coandă schools. Institutions in larger cities, like Henri Coandă Timișoara, tend to have higher employment rates both in the general labor market and specifically within the spa tourism sector. On the other hand, schools in smaller towns, such as Henri Coandă Ștei, have faced more difficulty in placing graduates in roles that match their specialized training.

These mixed results suggest that while vocational training can effectively prepare students for the workforce, its success is heavily dependent on regional factors, including the availability of jobs in spa tourism and the economic strength of the local area. Despite these variations, the research underscores the importance of collaboration between educational institutions and the tourism industry in improving employment opportunities. Incorporating internships, hands-on experience, and forging stronger links with local businesses could greatly enhance the

chances of graduates finding relevant work. Additionally, ensuring that curricula are adapted to reflect emerging trends in the spa tourism sector, such as changing consumer preferences and technological developments, would make the training more relevant and impactful.

Limitations

While this study provides useful insights into the labor market outcomes for AMBFKTR graduates, there are some limitations to consider. First, the research is limited to the Henri Coandă Post-Secondary School Network, which may not fully reflect the broader scope of vocational training in the spa tourism sector across Romania and the EU. As a result, the findings may not be easily applied to other schools or regions. Another concern is the reliance on self-reported data from school administrators, which may be subject to biases or inaccuracies. Additionally, the study lacks direct input from graduates or employers, which would have provided a more comprehensive understanding of how well the training aligns with industry needs and student expectations.

Furthermore, the study does not include long-term data on graduates' career paths, as it only covers recent academic years. A more extended observation period would have offered a better understanding of the long-term career outcomes for these graduates, such as job stability, career advancement, and their mobility across different EU regions.

Future research directions

Future research could build on this study by examining a broader range of vocational schools across different regions of Romania and the EU to provide a more comprehensive picture of how spa tourism graduates integrate into the labor market. It would also be insightful to gather feedback directly from graduates and employers through surveys or interviews. This would help to better understand the factors that affect employment outcomes and the actual impact of the training.

Additionally, future studies could explore the specific effects of certain training methods, such as internships, industry placements, and digital skill development, on graduates' employability. Tracking the career progress of AMBFKTR graduates over an extended period would shed light on how sustainable and promising career paths are in the spa tourism sector, especially as the industry evolves with trends like eco-tourism and wellness tourism.

Finally, research could look into the potential for expanding vocational training programs in emerging EU markets, where demand for skilled workers in spa tourism is growing. This would help us understand how education systems can better adapt to the needs of a fast-changing industry, ensuring graduates are well-prepared for future challenges in the sector.

In summary, while this study offers valuable insights into the link between professional training and labor market integration in spa tourism, further research and a wider data collection effort will be needed to deepen our understanding of these complex dynamics.

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CONSIDERATION REGARDING RURAL TOURISM IN THE MODERN ERA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Agrotourism is the expression of the orientation of a significant part of tourists towards nature, as a result of the implication of post-industrial civilization. Today, nature becomes a pretext for reflection, for discovery, for education but also for treatment, sports performances and implicitly for a new life. Through its content, agrotourism presents a series of particularities that intertwine to a large extent with other forms of tourism, complementing and stimulating each other. In this sense, we have in mind hunting and fishing tourism, tourism related to the Danube Delta or tourism in mountain areas. Accordingly, researchers distinguish several types of tourist villages: ethnographic-folkloric, artistic and craft creation, climatic and landscape, fishing, of hunting interest, vineyards, etc.. The development of these tourist villages offers the special possibilities of balancing the tourist market in a territorial profile, with numerous positive incidents on agrotourism.

Keywords: Agrotourism, sustainability, tourists;

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INTRODUCTION

Being within the scope of services, agritourism will present all their particularities, having some of its own characteristics, such as:

- seasonality, its extent and intensity being very different from one period to another, the interdependence of tourism products (the tourist being most often the beneficiary of several material goods and services that are chronologically and causally linked to each other), as well as the high level of fixed costs (determined by the rigid nature of the offer and the non-stockable nature of the services).

A peculiarity of agritourism consists in the fact that, through the presence of favorable development conditions in over 60% of the country, it contributes to the introduction of a significant part of the tourist potential of our country into the domestic and international circuit. It can be said that the chance of Romanian tourism depends on a large measure of the appropriate development of agritourism. Compared to other forms, agritourism does not require too much investment for infrastructure or other facilities and does not produce agglomerations that create various problems for urban localities. Farms and agricultural guesthouses can be used for reception structures in addition to some villagers' households.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We used for data collection, reception registers, conditions of Suggestions and complaints as well as statistical yearbooks, magazines and Specialized bulletins published by the national tourist offices or other Bodies.

Observation is a way of gathering information that involves the Supervision, by the people in charge of the company with something like That (guides, receptionists, market agents, etc.), of the way people behave. Before and during their time as tourists, to notice how they react to certain levels of tourist tariffs, to the comfort classes in which the vehicles, hotels and restaurants made available to them fall, to the physical and social environment ensured during travel, accommodation, leisure, etc., making use of by some specific methods (tourist audit, mysterious tourists method, Mechanical observation, etc. In this way, the information collected has the advantage that they are relatively objective (not influenced by the goodwill of the investigated subjects), while eliminating the stress specific to other Methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Ensuring a quality tourist product requires the enhancement of the tourist heritage, through the combination of natural and anthropogenic

factors; of the general infrastructure, determined by the economic development of the destination area; of the tourist infrastructure (transportation facilities, accommodation, public food, health facilities, etc.), as well as the quality of tourism staff. The tourism product can also be created based on prior information regarding:

- Clientele - segmented according to age, profession, residence, income, habits, tourist tastes, etc.;
- Competition - from the need to adapt the elements that make up the product in order to differentiate it from the competing offer and from the need for optimal promotion;
- Existing tourism resources in the destination areas: natural, cultural values, infrastructure, leisure, etc.

The tourist demand is made up of all the people who express their desire to move periodically or temporarily outside their own residence, for reasons other than the provision of remunerated activities at the destination. Tourism demand is particularly complex. It has a varied character determined by psychological and economic factors and has a heterogeneous character due to various motivations. As a result of the simultaneous requests for some elements related to the tourist activity, the request has a complex character.

Contrary to the tourist offer which is immovable, the tourist demand is mobile in the sense of extension. Continuous changes in the economy and politics give demand the character of elasticity, but also influence it in terms of volume, structure and quality. Similar to the demand for goods, the elasticity coefficient of the tourist demand is expressed by elasticity coefficients, their values being dependent on the nature of the tourist products.

Figure 3.1. Satisfaction in tourism

Desires represent the form of manifestation of the human need to travel, being constantly influenced by the tourist market situation and the internal and external environment of the individual. In our case, it is the desire to travel in rural areas.

The tourist market is the place where the demand meets the offer of tourist products, respectively the specially arranged space where the buyers and sellers of tourist services meet to carry out the transaction.

Tourist products represent a complex set of goods and services offered to consumers. In the case of agritourism guesthouses, it is about the vacation spent in the village and spending free time in the rural area

The transaction consists of the exchange of values between two parties.

The value and satisfaction lies in the advantage offered by the tourist product in relation to the price paid.

The starting point in the development of the tourism activity must be the research of the needs for rest and travel, ensuring the most complete and efficient satisfaction of them. In this sense, starting from the market and consumers, tourism marketing represents the set of methods and techniques aimed at highlighting and satisfying the needs of consumers, motivated by the desire for knowledge, rest, fun, treatment, etc., along with the organization of agencies or associations capable of satisfying these categories of needs to the maximum.

Figure 3.2. presents the main areas with tourist potential.

Figure 3.2. Areas with tourist resources

Although there is a great similarity between tourism demand and tourism consumption, these two concepts cannot be totally overlapped. Thus, the official definitions reveal the different content of the two categories:

a) "the tourist demand is made up of all the people who express their desire to move periodically and temporarily outside their own residence, for reasons other than the provision of remunerated activities at the place of destination"; (R. Minciu op. cit.)

b) "tourist consumption consists of the expenses incurred by the tourist demand for the purchase of new services and goods related to the tourist motivation".

The touristic demand represents, therefore, all the requirements manifested or not yet manifested, for the approach to the touristic products, while the touristic consumption is the form of materialization of the demand.

Thus, there are two ways of expressing tourist demand:

a) manifested tourist demand - that demand that manifested itself (externalized) in a certain period of time, also known as real tourist demand;

b) unmanifested (non-concrete) tourist demand, but which potentially exists in the conception of a consumer and which could be evaluated and quantified based on a study of the evolution of requirements; it can also be found under the name of presumed tourist demand.

The actual tourism demand and the presumed tourism demand form the potential tourism demand.

The tourist market has the character of an "opaque" market, that is, it is difficult to define and influence, a character given by the particularities of the market, namely:

- tourist demand is very elastic and permanently subject to fluctuations, under the influence of a multitude of factors of different natures (economic, demographic, psychological, political, conjunctural, etc.);
- tourist demand is characterized by a high degree of complexity and heterogeneity, its study presupposing market segmentation according to a series of criteria such as: age, socio-professional category, consumption habits, etc.;
- tourist demand implies a high degree of tourist mobility, as a result of the rigid nature of the offer;
- the tourist demand has a strong seasonal character, as a result of the uneven distribution and the non-stockable nature of the tourist offer, but also due to the dependence of tourist circulation on natural conditions.

In turn, tourist consumption also presents a series of characteristics, among which we mention, first of all, the coincidence in time and space of tourist consumption and tourist production.

The volume of tourist consumption is determined by the level of effective prices and the disposable income of consumers. The possibility of tourist consumption to change structurally, so to adapt the proportion of its multiple components depending on the change of price, income variables, gives the global volume of tourist consumption a note of stability. In turn, the price and income variables are under the influence of a multitude of factors that can act at the same time and in the same direction on both, or delayed in time and only on one of them.

Some authors group these factors into two large categories:

- a) economic-social determinants;
- b) motivational determinants.

The representative economic-social determinants - income, prices, free time, the size and structure of the population - with a stimulating or restrictive role, give demand a certain elasticity and evolution.

Like tourist demand, tourist consumption shows a strong concentration in time and space, but also in motivation; as far as motivation is concerned, at a given moment rest, recreation may predominate as a reason.

Tourist demand and supply are found in causal relations, because both supply and demand can take the position of determining factor of evolution or the position of resultant of the evolution of tourist activity.

The tourist offer is represented by the framework and the natural and anthropic potential, the "production" equipment of tourist services, the set of goods and services intended for tourist consumption, the labor force specialized in the specific activities, the tourist infrastructure and the marketing conditions.

As it follows from the presented definitions, the tourist offer has a complex and heterogeneous character, being made up of several components, which can be structured as follows:

- the tourist potential, as an element of attraction of the tourist demand formed by the totality of the natural and anthropic resources of an area;

- the tourist equipment, made up of all the fixed and circulating assets that compete to satisfy the needs of tourists ;
- the services provided to tourists and the goods offered to them for consumption, goods with an exclusive tourist destination;
- the workforce that transforms the other elements mentioned above from potential into effective;

The complexity of the tourist offer (and production, equally) is also given by the large number of providers or "manufacturers" of tourist products. The fact that the tourist product consists of a set of services, each with its own specifics, makes it almost impossible for a single producer to provide all the benefits generated by tourist consumption. That is why the providers are highly specialized, have different profiles, sometimes even different interests and most often a distinct way of organization. Thus, in the realization of the tourist product, commercial companies participate whose activities include accommodation, meals, transport, leisure, "manufacturing" tourist trips (tour operators); bodies and associations with a social vocation, local and territorial bodies, etc. can also participate.

In addition to this strong specialization of tourist services, we must also mention the fact that small and medium enterprises predominate among them, a fact that has led to an excessive fragmentation of tourist service providers. As can be seen, this does not exclude the possibility of their regrouping into strong, well-individualized bodies that can dominate the tourist market at a given moment.

Another characteristic of the tourist offer, with multiple implications in the realization of the tourist act, is its rigidity. This particularity is due, first of all, to the inadaptability (reduced adaptability) to both quantitative and qualitative variations of tourist demand.

The impossibility of moving the offer, which implies the mobility of the consumer and not of the tourist product, is another particularity of the tourist offer. Also, the tourist offer cannot be stored - once not consumed, it is lost -, an aspect that implies additional expenses for the economic agents offering in the sense of promoting tourist products and adapting them to the changes in the demand structure.

The tourist offer is dependent on the tourist equipment, the number and structure of the workforce. In the tourism industry, investments, both material and human, are

very expensive, a fact that does not allow their rapid replacement to adapt to the mobility of tourist demand.

As can be seen from the analysis of the characteristics of the tourist supply and production, the inconsistency in time and space of the demand with the tourist supply can be the generator of large-scale economic and social effects, which are embodied in:

- inadequate satisfaction of tourists;
- non-use of tourist equipment;
- extending their amortization period;
- slowing down the pace of replacement of worn-out physical or moral capacities.

According to tourism specialists, there are also certain typologies of tourist demand, closely related to the main categories of tourists. Thus, three types of tourism demand can be distinguished, namely: the demand for luxury tourism, the demand for active tourism and the demand for passive tourism.

Conclusions

The international experience, from countries with old tourist traditions, shows that the adoption of a tourist planning at national level - based on the aspect of protecting the own tourist resources, in order to develop a sustainable tourism - took into account three main objectives: economic (essential in the identification, valorization and increasing the degree of exploitation of touristic resources), social (especially by permanentizing the population, increasing the degree of employment, supporting the practice of some traditional trades and attracting the population to the practice of tourism) and ecological (important for avoiding degradation, pollution of the environment and ensuring a balanced and long-term exploitation of tourist resources). In accordance with these requirements, there was a need to develop and adopt national tourism development plans, intended to allow combining the experience and positions of the main actors on this market - economic agents, public administration, employers' organizations, associations and professional, social, trade union organizations, specialists in profile research, etc.

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THE INFLUENCE OF FERTILIZATION WITH CHEMICAL FERTILIZERS ON PHOSPHORUS AND POTASSIUM PRESENT IN THE APPLE TREE LEAVES DURING 2020-2022 PERIOD

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Fertilization represents an important technological link, which is meant to provide on a permanent basis an optimum level of nutritive elements for the soils filled with roots. These have to be accessible for the roots and in adequate relations for the carrying out of the physiological balance, in order to encourage a good growth of the trees and an abundant fruit bearing, year after year

Adding fertilizers on the plantations has many positive effects, such as: the increase of the fruit production, the quickening of the ripening, the increase of the assimilation of the leafage, the prolongation of the trees' lifetime, the growth in resistance of the trees against the frost, against the attacks of the cryptogenic diseases.

Key words: chemical fertilizer, the phosphorus and the potassium present in the leaves, type Golden *delicious*, type *Starkrimson*

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INTRODUCTION

The effect of the chemical fertilizers on the growth and apple fruit-bearing have raised interest in many researchers. According to the age of the trees, to the depth of the trophic layer, the content of humus and clay in the soil, they proposed fertility systems of the orchards as near as possible to the needs of the trees.

Seen from the efficiency angle and from the energetic productivity, the proddem of the establishment of an adequate efficient fertility system has a big importance that materializes in the fruit obtained.

Considered to be the king of the fruits, the apple tree has in its composition considerable quantities of vital elements for the human body such as: carbon hydrate, lignin, cellulose, free acids, pectin, phosphorus, magnesium, A, B, C vitamins.

Starkrimson is the most well spread species from the delicious red group because of its weakness and great capacity of fructification. It has big fruits in the shape of a truncated cone, colored in dark red, of a very good quality

production needs an adequate division into the zones confronted with the vegetation factors.

Golden *delicious* is the most cultivated species of apple, has middle vigour, forms thick crowns, and has the tendency of overloading with fruits.

It is productive, but for a good quality of the fruit it has to be planted in regions with small atmospheric humidity, otherwise it rusts and it is very sensitive to the scurf and it dehydrates slowly over the period of preserving in normal conditions. The fruit has an average size, spherical, green-yellowish at harvesting, reaching a golden yellow at the consumption maturity, sweet taste and specific flavor.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research took place in an apple tree orchard at Cheresig country over 2 apple ranges: Golden *delicious* and *Starkrimson* grafted on the middle vigor port grafted M₄.

The trees are planted in an intensive system, the distance between the rows being of 4 m and the distance in the row is 5.5-6.0 mg P₂O₅, 6,0- 6,5mg K₂O poorly supplied with humus. The yearly rainfalls amount to 625 mm and the yearly average temperature 10,1- 10,5 degrees C. The experiment includes a number of 6 variants, 5 fertilized variants and a witness variant.

The doses of chemical fertilizers for the fertility of the variants from the experiment have been the following: V₁ N₄₀P₂₀K₀; V₂ N₇₀P₃₅ K₀; V₃ N₁₄₀P₇₀K₀; V₄ N₂₀₀P₁₀₀K₅₀; V₅ N₂₇₀P₁₃₅K₇₀ applied in two stages in spring and autumn.

The total nitrogen was determined through the Kjeldahl method procedure, the nitric nitrogen through the calorimetric method; the phosphorus and the potassium through the gravimetric method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The supply of the soil with phosphorus in soluble forms was less pointed out in the composition of the leaves, the differences being most of the time insignificant.

The phosphorus didn't show big variations of the values from one season to another or between the fertile variants and the witness. The growths in phosphorus existed, but they didn't follow any certain rule, in some cases these have diminishing values unjustified for a Golden delicious (table 1).

For the Starkrimson type, the condition is quite similar to the Golden delicious (table 2).

For the Golden delicious type the values of the content in potassium have been registered a regression from spring to autumn, but comparing the fertilized variants and the unfertilized ones the differences were insignificant. High values have been registered for the fertilized variants with potassium (Table 3).

Table 1

The phosphorus present in the leaves for the Golden delicious type

Variant	Applied chemical fertilizer (kg/ ha)	Type Golden delicious					
		2020		2021		2022	
		23.04	28.08	25.04	30.08	24.04	24.08
V ₀	-	0,13	0,16	0,15	0,17	0,16	0,17
V ₁	N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₀	0,19	0,16	0,18	0,19	0,19	0,19
V ₂	N ₇₀ P ₃₅ K ₀	0,17	0,17	0,18	0,22	0,17	0,16
V ₃	N ₁₄₀ P ₇₀ K ₀	0,16	0,16	0,20	0,20	0,19	0,19
V ₄	N ₂₀₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₅₀	0,16	0,17	0,19	0,18	0,18	0,20
V ₅	N ₂₇₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₇₀	0,19	0,20	0,21	0,24	0,20	0,21

Table 2

The phosphorus present in the leaves for the Starkrimson delicious type

Variant	Applied chemical fertilizer (kg/ ha)	Type Starkrimson					
		2020		2021		2022	
		23.04	28.08	25.04	30.08	26.04	24.08
V ₀	-	0,14	0,15	0,16	0,17	0,17	0,17
V ₁	N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₀	0,23	0,21	0,27	0,25	0,29	0,28
V ₂	N ₇₀ P ₃₅ K ₀	0,23	0,10	0,29	0,26	0,26	0,25
V ₃	N ₁₄₀ P ₇₀ K ₀	0,23	0,24	0,28	0,21	0,30	0,31
V ₄	N ₂₀₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₅₀	0,25	0,20	0,29	0,23	0,32	0,33
V ₅	N ₂₇₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₇₀	0,26	0,24	0,28	0,25	0,32	0,35

Table 3

Potassium in the leaves for the Golden delicious apple

Variant	Applied chemical fertilizer (kg/ ha)	Type <i>Golden delicious</i>					
		2020		2021		2022	
		23.04	28.08	25.04	30.08	26.04	24.08
V ₀	-	1,20	0,78	1,22	0,81	1,23	1,01
V ₁	N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₀	1,26	0,77	1,25	0,83	1,28	1,05
V ₂	N ₇₀ P ₃₅ K ₀	1,24	0,75	1,24	0,75	1,22	0,78
V ₃	N ₁₄₀ P ₇₀ K ₀	1,22	0,78	1,26	0,78	1,28	0,76
V ₄	N ₂₀₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₅₀	1,43	1,18	1,60	1,11	1,59	1,12
V ₅	N ₂₇₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₇₀	0,53	1,25	1,68	1,31	1,70	1,19

Table 4

Potassium in the leaves for the Starkrimson apple

Variant	Applied chemical fertilizer (kg/ ha)	Type <i>Starkrimson</i>					
		2020		2021		2022	
		23.04	28.08	25.04	30.08	26.04	24.08
V ₀	-	1,46	0,79	1,11	0,82	1,25	1,01
V ₁	N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₀	1,57	0,77	1,15	0,79	1,37	1,10
V ₂	N ₇₀ P ₃₅ K ₀	1,55	0,81	0,95	0,71	1,15	0,91
V ₃	N ₁₄₀ P ₇₀ K ₀	1,65	0,75	0,81	0,69	1,41	0,95
V ₄	N ₂₀₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₅₀	1,85	1,15	1,51	0,98	1,48	1,11
V ₅	N ₂₇₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₇₀	1,89	1,21	1,81	1,15	1,65	1,17

The values of the potassium content of the leaves grew from one year to another for all variants, except in the third year of experience. During this third year, the process has been used mostly for the fructification process, reaching low values for the V₁, V₂, V₃ variants in comparison with the V₄, V₅ variants. In the case of the last variants, the dosage of the used chemical fertilizer has been much more in comparison with V₁, V₂, and V₃.

Drawing the analysis of V₄, V₅ in comparison with V₁, V₂, V₃, variants, it results that the values of the potassium content of the leaves are higher than in the case of the fertilized variants with larger doses of potassium.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results obtained after the fertilization with diferent doses of chemical fertilizers, we can draw the following conclusions: the phosphorus was present in relatively close quantities to the fertilized variants. In all the situations, the concentrations

have been higher in the fertilized variants in comparison with the witness variant.

The potassium was found in high quantities in the leaves of the trees from the variants fertilized with this element for both ranges.

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FINANCING LOCAL ACTION GROUPS WITHIN THE CAP STRATEGIC PLAN 2023-2027. CASE STUDY NORTH WEST REGION , ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In 2019, the North West Region of Romania had 34 Local Action Groups (LAGs) that were crucial in developing and implementing local development strategies under the LEADER Axis of the PNDR 2014-2020. These LAGs have significantly improved rural quality of life by addressing community needs, promoting environmentally friendly agricultural practices, and fostering economic diversification. Their strategies, supported by non-reimbursable funding of up to 200,000 euros, have enabled them to extend urban funding programs to rural areas, particularly enhancing mobility.

Research findings indicate that LAGs have been pivotal in transforming rural areas by facilitating capacity building among local actors and ensuring transparent and effective project selection processes. For the CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027, 246 Local Development Strategies were financed nationally, with 35 from the North West region. Notably, Bihor county's LAGs, including the largest, LAG Bihor, received substantial funding, demonstrating their strategic importance. Additionally, the introduction of multi-fund financing from the European Social Fund (ESF+) has further bolstered resources available to LAGs, contributing to broader development goals.

Overall, the LAGs have successfully integrated urban and rural development efforts, significantly improving mobility and living standards in local communities through strategic financial support and innovative local initiatives. Their continued support underscores the importance of tailored development strategies in achieving sustainable rural progress.

Keywords: LAG, Financing, multifond, monofond, Nort West Region

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INTRODUCTION

At the level of the North West region of Romania, Local Action Groups (LAGs) carried out important activity within the LEADER Axis in previous funding periods (2007-2013, 2014-2020) within the National Rural Development Programs (NRDPs) financed through Pillar II of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

LEADER is a 'bottom up' approach, in which farmers, rural businesses, local organisations, public authorities and individuals from different sectors come together to form local action groups (LAGs) (Chereji et al, 2022). LEADER is an important instrument for Romania in increasing the economic and social development of rural areas, reducing urban-rural disparities and promoting social inclusion (Rusu, 2021).

Local Action Group (LAG) represents a local partnership, made up of representatives of the private, public and civil society sectors,

including individuals relevant to the LEADER eligible territory, established with the aim of implementing a local development strategy in the territory targeted by the partnership. (Local Action Groups Guide for the Implementation of Local Development Strategies 2023-2027, p.3).

The role of LAGs is decisive in stimulating local development through the LEADER approach, which has as its operating principles: Participatory approach, innovation and adaptability, cooperation and partnership. By involving LAGs in decision-making processes, rural regions can foster sustainable development that balances economic growth, social well-being, and environmental protection. (Albu and Chitu, 2014). The activity of the Local Action Group is subject to periodic evaluation in order to establish its level of performance and possibly to be bonused or penalized (Staic and Vladu, 2021). LEADER is an important instrument for Romania in increasing the economic and social development of rural areas,

reducing urban-rural disparities and promoting social inclusion (Rusu, 2021).

as well as the activity of LAGs in the current financial year, represent an important driver for

Figure 1 The position and composition of the Northwest Region in Romania

Source: CNIPT Dej, MIPE

The Local Action Group operates in a territory eligible for the LEADER programme in Romania, a territory that must meet conditions of size, homogeneity, local identity, density, and number of inhabitants. (Brezuleanu et al, 2024)

The North-West Development Region was created under Law 151/1998 through the voluntary association of local and county authorities from the counties of Bihor, Bistrița-Năsăud, Cluj, Maramureș, Satu Mare and Sălaj. The region's area is 34,160 km², representing 14.3% of Romania's territory, thus ranking 4th at national level. In the statistical nomenclature of European territorial units (NUTS), the region ranks 29th in terms of area among the 2838 NUTS2 regions of the EU28 (according to the "NUTS 2021 classification" units). (NORTHWEST REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN 2021-2027). The North-West Region is considered to be the second economic area of the country, after Bucharest-Ilfov, thanks to the labour market, salaries, foreign investments, industrial parks with modern technologies. (Chiurciu et al, 2018).

The main purpose of this study is to highlight the importance of financing Local Development Strategies (LDS) developed by LAGs within the framework of the CAP SP 2023-2027. The continuity and territorial expansion,

increasing the quality and attractiveness of life in rural areas, respectively in the territory they serve.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This paper was based on an exhaustive analysis of the specialized literature to achieve its objective.

To answer the question regarding the provision and importance of financing of SDLs developed by LAGs, we conducted an analysis of the programming documents for the period 2023-2027, respectively of the specialized literature.

In order to substantiate our research, we conducted a detailed analysis of the documents published by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, with a focus on the selection reports of the LAGs and the related SDLs for the programming period 2023-2027. We extrapolated data specific to the LAGs in the North-West region, in order to obtain a clear picture of the financing modalities and the factors influencing access to funds in this region.

Taking into account that for the 2023-2027 funding period there are LAGs that occupy territories in two regions, for example North-West-West, North-West-Center, we chose the county only those LAGs that occupy territories at the level of the analysed region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The North West Region, in 2019, comprised a number of 34 Local Action Groups representing partnerships between local authorities, the private and civil sectors. Their role was to prepare and implement local development strategies within the LEADER Axis of the PNDR 2014-2020. (NORTHWEST REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN 2021-2027)

In recent years, LAGs in the North-West Region have become essential pillars in the development of rural areas. By developing tailor-made strategies and attracting funding, LAGs have managed to directly address the needs of local communities, significantly improving the quality of life in these areas. Furthermore, LAGs have demonstrated a remarkable capacity to extend funding programmes from urban areas to rural areas, thus creating a beneficial synergy between the two types of territory, especially in areas such as mobility.

Through local partnerships, LAGs act as real catalysts for change in the agricultural sector. They encourage the adoption of more environmentally friendly agricultural practices, facilitate the diversification of economic activities in rural areas and contribute to increasing the quality of life in local communities.

The LEADER approach is based on local initiatives that combine solutions that respond to the problems identified at the level of local communities, reflected in actions specific to these needs and project financing with a non-reimbursable value of maximum 200,000 euros. The intensity of support can be a maximum of 100% for:

- Implementation of selected operations within the strategy, including cooperation activities and their preparation, and
- Managing, monitoring and evaluating the strategy, as well as animating it, including facilitating exchanges between stakeholders. (AFIR,2024)

The implementation activity of Local Development Strategies (LDS) is mainly based on administrative functions of Local Action Groups such as: strengthening the capacity of local actors to develop and implement operations, including advising them; carrying out animation/promotion activities in the territory; developing a non-discriminatory and transparent selection procedure and criteria, which avoid conflicts of interest and guarantee that no individual interest group controls the

selection decisions; preparing and publishing selection calls, in accordance with the approved LDS; evaluating the submitted funding applications, establishing the amount of support, selecting projects and submitting them to AFIR/MIPE. (Local Action Groups Guide for the Implementation of Local Development Strategies 2023-2027, p.7)

The financing of LAGs within the Framework of the CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027 is carried out through the intervention DR-36 – LEADER – Local development placed under the responsibility of the community. The session for submitting Local Development Strategies took place between December 2023 and January 2024. Following the verification of the eligibility of the submitted SDLs, a total of 246 Local Development Strategies were selected for financing at the national level. Of the total of 246 SDLs, 37 are single-fund SDLs, and 209 are multi-fund SDLs.

Regarding the LAGs in the North West region, a number of 35 LAGs were selected for the period 2023-2027. (Table 1). At the same time, it is important to highlight the fact that the 35 LAGs analysed only include territories located entirely in the component counties of the North West Region.

Thus, it is observed that at the level of Bihor county, a number of 9 LAGs were selected for operation during the analysed period with a total area of 5,040 km² serving a population of 248,665 inhabitants. The largest LAG at the level of Bihor county in terms of area and also in terms of number of inhabitants is represented by the Association of the Local Action Group Bihor near the Hungarian Border (LAG Bihor), this being one of the oldest LAGs at the level of Bihor county but also at the level of the North West Region.

According to the financing plan for the financial year 2014-2020, the amount of euro allocated to LAG BIHOR was about 3.3 million euros, with a value of 35.75 euros / person, and the value per km² of about 2,214 euros, calculated values based on the information available in the Gal Financing Plan for the analysed period. (Chereji et al, 2022)

Table 1

List of selected Local Action Groups 2023-2027, North West region

No	LAG name	County	Area (km2)	Population no. inhabitants
1	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ BIHOR DE PE LÂNGĂ FRONTIERA CU UNGARIA	BIHOR	1.271,63	75.977
2	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ ȚARA BEIUȘULUI	BIHOR	309,36	11.744
3	Asociația GAL EuroCrișana	BIHOR	496,01	18.071
4	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ ZONA ALEȘD – VĂLEA CRIȘULUI REPEDE	BIHOR	521,19	32.004
5	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ CRIȘUL NEGRU	BIHOR	277,51	10.985
6	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ ZONA METROPOLITANĂ ȘI CÂMPIA CRIȘULUI (G.A.L. ZONA METROPOLITANĂ ȘI CÂMPIA CRIȘULUI)	BIHOR	326,73	17.620
7	ASOCIAȚIA GRUP DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ ZMO DEALUL ȘOMLEU	BIHOR	287,24	35.052
8	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ VĂLEA VELJ (GAL VĂLEA VELJ)	BIHOR	603,91	25.592
9	ASOCIAȚIA GRUP DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ PĂDUREA CRAIULUI	BIHOR	946,42	21.620
	No of LAG Bihor county	9	5.040,00	248.665,00
10	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ "CODRU MOMA"	BIHOR, ARAD	575,42	23.035
11	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ MUNTELE ȘES JUDEȚUL BIHOR	BIHOR, SĂLAJ	684,43	39.590
12	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ PROGRES TRANSILVAN	BISTRIȚA-NĂSĂUD	401,61	11.361
13	FEDERAȚIA PENTRU DEZVOLTAREA ZONEI RURALE BÂRGĂU-CĂLIMANI	BISTRIȚA-NĂSĂUD	1.129,26	44.468
14	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ LIDER BISTRIȚA NĂSĂUD	BISTRIȚA-NĂSĂUD	1.071,56	42.350
15	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ ȚARA NĂSĂUDULUI	BISTRIȚA-NĂSĂUD	1.191,65	57.479
	No of LAG BN county	4	3.794,08	155.658,00
16	ASOCIAȚIA PARTENERIAT GAL ȚINUTUL HAIDUCILOR	BISTRIȚA-NĂSĂUD, CLUJ	1.384,56	62.777
17	ASOCIAȚIA "GAL SOMEȘ-NADĂȘ"	CLUJ	423,28	75.300
18	ASOCIAȚIA GAL CÂMPIA TRANSILVANIEI	CLUJ	935,73	29.964
19	ASOCIAȚIA GAL SOMEȘ TRANSILVAN	CLUJ	894,62	45.644
20	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ LIDER CLUJ	CLUJ	768,77	19.148
21	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ NAPOCA POROLISSUM	CLUJ	1.613,03	41.150
	No of LAG CJ	5	4.635,43	211.206,00
22	ASOCIAȚIA "GAL POARTA TRANSILVANIEI"	CLUJ, SĂLAJ, BIHOR	1.264,54	33.365
23	"ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ NORD EST-ȚARA MARAMUREȘULUI"	MARAMUREȘ	1.440,14	64.159
24	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ MARA-GUTĂI	MARAMUREȘ	908,43	43.968
25	ASOCIAȚIA MICROREGIONALĂ MARA-NATUR	MARAMUREȘ	1.503,82	78.670
26	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ VĂLEA IZEI-MOISEI	MARAMUREȘ	427,37	22.162
	No of LAG MM	4	4.279,76	208.959,00
27	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ MARAMUREȘ VEST - GALMMV	MARAMUREȘ, SATU-MARE	869,69	51.409
28	ASOCIAȚIA GRUP DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ TÖVISHÁT	SĂLAJ, SATU-MAREȘ	1.018,54	49.879

29	ASOCIAȚIA SAMUS POROLISSUM	SĂLAJ, CLUJ	1.331,76	46.638
30	ASOCIAȚIA GAL VALEA SOMEȘULUI	SĂLAJ, CLUJ, MARAMUREȘ	1.368,43	39.266
31	GAL VALEA CRASNEI ȘI BARCĂULUI	SĂLAJ, BIHOR	860,97	53.563
32	ASOCIAȚIA GRUP DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ SUD-VEST SATU MARE	SATU-MARE, BIHOR	1.483,25	72.364
33	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ LIDER OAS	SATU-MARE	759,20	62.900
34	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ MICROREGIUNEA SOMEȘ- CODRU	SATU-MARE, MARAMUREȘ	573,25	28.603
35	ASOCIAȚIA DE DEZVOLTARE MICROREGIONALĂ A COMUNITĂȚILOR DIN ZONA SĂTMARULUI	SATU-MARE, MARAMUREȘ	1.096,18	70.058
Total			48.768,76	2.282.423,00

Source: Own processing after MADR, Axa LEADER 2023-2017

The territorial coverage of the LAGs strictly in Cluj County is represented by a number of 5 LAGs, 4,635 Km² and a total number of 211,206 inhabitants. As highlighted in Table 1, at the level of the North West Region there are a number of 11 LAGs that have a territorial area spread over 2 counties and a LAG with a territorial area related to it across 3 counties - the Association of LAGs Poarta Transilvaniei being present on the surface of Cluj, Sălaj and Bihor counties with the following composition: Ciucea, Negreni, Poieni (Cluj County), Almașu, Banișor, Cizer, Fildu De Jos, Horoatu Crasnei, Plopiș, Sag (Sălaj County), Borod, Bratca, Bulz (Bihor County).

Satu Mare County is the only county in the North West region that has a single LAG with territorial composition only at the county level on an area of 759.2 km² and 62,900 inhabitants. It is noted that Satu Mare County is territorially represented in 5 other LAGs that have territories

from neighbouring counties as their composition: Maramureș, Bihor, Cluj, Sălaj.

Regarding the financing of LAGs, for the 2023-2027 programming period, at the level of the North West region, Local Development Strategies with single-fund financing (EAFRD financing) for 3 LAGs were selected for financing, 2 LAGs at the level of Bistrița Năsăud county and one LAG in Bihor county. All other Local Development Strategies, respectively 32, requested multi-fund financing, in addition to financing from the EAFRD, they also requested financing through the ESF + (European Social Fund). Financing through the ESF + brought each LAG an additional financing of 5.38 euros/inhabitant, respectively 262.34 euros/km², which contributed to the increase in the total public value received as financial support for the implementation of the SDLs.

Table 2

LAG with strategies single fond

No. of document	Applicant (Name of entity designated by the partnership)	Partnership/LAG name	County	Total public value FEADR
1	AOCIATIA GRUPUL DE ACTIUNE LOCALA "TARA NASAUDULUI"	TARA NASAUDULUI	BISTRITA- NASAUD	2,494,415
2	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ "CODRU MOMA"	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ "CODRU MOMA"	BIHOR	1,415,286
3	ASOCIAȚIA GRUPUL DE ACȚIUNE LOCALĂ PROGRES TRANSILVAN	GAL PROGRES TRANSILVAN	BISTRITA- NASAUD	1,078,140

Source: Own processing after MADR, Axa LEADER 2023-2017

Public value generated per capita FEADR	16.73	Euro/loc
Resulting public value per km2 FEADR	816.06	Euro/km2
Public value of a bonus unit FEADR	140,083.31	Euro
Public value generated per capita FSE+	5.38	Euro/loc
Resulting public value per km2 FSE+	262.34	Euro/km2
Public value of a bonus unit FSE+	13,341.63	Euro

Table 3 Public value, FEADR And FSE+

Source: FINAL SELECTION REPORT OF LOCAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES, ses.01/2023 - MULTIFOND, MADR

Regarding the strategy with single-fund financing, each LAG receives, in order to achieve the result indicators proposed in the SDL through EAFRD, 16.73 euros/inhabitant and 816.06 euros/km2. At the same time, it can be

seen from table 3 that each LAG also receives a bonus both through EAFRD and through ESF +.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of Local Action Groups (LAGs) in the North West Region has shown significant progress in addressing the unique needs of rural communities.

By developing and executing tailored local development strategies under the LEADER Axis of the PNDR 2014-2020, LAGs have substantially improved the quality of life in these areas. Their ability to extend funding from urban to rural environments has fostered a beneficial synergy, especially in critical sectors such as mobility, thereby integrating diverse territories into cohesive development frameworks.

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STRATEGIES FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The center of the elaboration of national tourism development strategies must start from the idea that the development of tourism requires a specific market for goods and services, which is in continuous transformation and on which action must be taken constantly in order to satisfy the constantly changing motivations of tourists.

The Romanian tourist offer currently addresses a more internal than external demand, and this is because Romania finds itself in permanent competition with countries in the area, e.g. Hungary, Croatia, Bulgaria, which have much more efficient tourism promotion policies than our country and where investments in the tourism field have determined a qualitative increase in services.

Keywords: tomatoes; germination; growth LEDs; mineral wool;

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INTRODUCTION

Romania's tourism sector holds significant potential due to its diverse natural landscapes, rich cultural heritage, and historical landmarks. However, to enhance its competitive position and ensure sustainable growth, the country needs to adopt strategic approaches for tourism development. Below are key strategies that could drive Romania's tourism forward:

Infrastructure Development:

Improved Connectivity: Expanding airports, railway networks, and highways will improve access to key tourist destinations, especially in rural and less-visited areas. Better transportation connections to major international hubs would increase inbound tourism.

Modernizing Facilities: Upgrading hotel accommodations, restaurants, and tourist attractions to meet international standards will improve the tourist experience and promote longer stays.

Promotion of Sustainable Tourism:

Ecotourism: Romania has vast natural reserves, such as the Carpathian Mountains and the Danube Delta, which can attract ecotourists. Developing sustainable ecotourism practices can ensure the preservation of these areas while promoting tourism.

Cultural Heritage Preservation:

Promoting Romania's traditional villages, UNESCO World Heritage sites, and folk traditions will help maintain cultural authenticity while attracting cultural tourists.

Diverse Marketing Strategies:

Targeting Niche Markets: Romania can target specific tourism markets such as wellness tourism, adventure tourism (e.g., hiking, skiing), and religious tourism. Marketing Romania as a destination for these niche segments will increase its visibility.

Digital Transformation: Leveraging social media and digital platforms to showcase Romania's unique attractions and experiences can help reach a global audience. Tourism apps, virtual tours, and social media campaigns can attract younger and tech-savvy tourists.

Public-Private Partnerships:

Collaborative Efforts: Encouraging collaboration between the government, local communities, and private sector (e.g., hospitality, travel agencies) will ensure a coordinated and effective development of tourism infrastructure and services.

Investment in Tourism Projects:

Financial incentives and grants for local businesses to develop tourism-related services, such as boutique hotels or local tour guides, can boost the sector.

Event Tourism:

Cultural Festivals and Events: Romania can organize and promote cultural festivals, music events, sports competitions, and culinary festivals to attract international visitors. Hosting events like the "Untold Festival" has already proven to be successful.

Conference and MICE Tourism: Romania can also promote itself as a destination for business conferences, meetings, and incentive

travel (MICE), capitalizing on cities like Bucharest and Cluj-Napoca.

Training and Education:

Skill Development: To maintain a high-quality tourist experience, Romania should focus on training and developing the local workforce in hospitality, guiding, and customer service. This would ensure that tourists have positive interactions with service providers.

Educational Programs: Establishing partnerships with universities and tourism institutes to train future leaders and professionals in sustainable tourism practices is vital for long-term success.

Branding and Image Enhancement:

Building a Strong National Brand: Creating a distinct tourism identity for Romania based on its history, folklore, and natural beauty will make the country more recognizable on the global tourism map. Emphasizing Romania's lesser-known but unique assets, like castles, medieval towns, and spas, can also help improve its image.

Tourism Ambassadors: Engaging high-profile figures or influencers as tourism ambassadors could boost the international appeal of Romania's tourism destinations.

In conclusion, Romania has the potential to become a leading tourist destination in Europe, but it requires a comprehensive and strategic approach. By focusing on infrastructure, sustainable practices, diversified marketing, and community involvement, Romania can effectively develop its tourism sector and create lasting economic benefits.

Romania's tourism potential is diversified and rich in tourist resources, characterized by the existence of accessible and harmoniously combined landforms throughout the country, a climate favorable to tourism throughout the year, rich biodiversity, a beautiful cultural and architectural heritage, meaning that Romania, through its wealth, can be included among tourist destinations internationally, not just nationally.

Tourism in Romania is mostly carried out in the following geographical areas: Carpathian Mountains, Black Sea, Danube Delta, Transylvania, Maramures, Moldova and Bucovina, Bucharest (together with Ilfov County) and certain rural areas. As a result, the country's tourism offer is represented by the following basic products:

mountain tourism, with great landscape diversity, complex tourist resources and high

possibilities for tourism exploitation. The mountains Bucegi, Vlădeasa, Piatra Mare and Postăvarul, Parâng, Retezat, etc. are worth noting. Here you can practice winter sports, mountain hiking, mountain climbing, ecotourism.

spa tourism, represented by the abundance of mineral waters, therapeutic muds, saline climate, phytotherapy, to which is added a qualified medical staff. The resorts of Băile Felix, Sovata, Băile Olănești, Tușnad, etc. are noteworthy.

Cultural tourism, represented by a rich cultural and historical heritage tied to Romanian history. Notable are the monasteries of Moldavia, Peleş Castle, Bran Castle, Hunyadi Castle, Sighișoara Fortress, etc.

Leisure and relaxation tourism.

Rural tourism, characterized by an ethnographic and folkloric treasure of great originality. Notable rural areas include Maramures, Bucovina, Oltenia, and Transylvania. In these villages, old crafts are still practiced, such as: woodworking, handicrafts, pottery, leatherworking, etc.

An important advantage that Romania has compared to other countries refers to the fact that important values for tourism such as natural landscapes, cultural and artistic values have not suffered much from human intervention.

In Romania, tourism can become an important economic sector, with a significant role in the economic and social development of the country, although it currently holds a rather modest share in GDP. The more modest development of Romanian tourism is influenced by the level of development of the general infrastructure, starting from transport and ending with the state of the technical and material base.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The bibliographic work focuses on tourism development strategy and is based on research of articles indexed in international databases (idbs). It aims to analyze and synthesize current perspectives and practices in the field of tourism, with the main objective of identifying the factors that influence the sustainable and competitive development of this sector.

By examining relevant articles, the work highlights global trends, effective policies, marketing strategies and the impact of technology on tourism. It also addresses topics

such as sustainability, local community involvement, climate change adaptation and the promotion of lesser-known destinations. The results provide a solid basis for understanding the complexity of tourism development strategy and for formulating practical recommendations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After 1989, the transition of Romanian economic life to a market economy, associated with a strong degradation of the Romanian tourist potential, led to a degradation of tourist goods and services, so that Romanian tourism faced a long period of stagnation and even regression. The result of these challenges meant a loss of tourists for Romania in favor of surrounding countries.

Two important elements contributed to the prolongation of the crisis in Romanian tourism, namely: the lack of a vision regarding the development of tourism and its correlation with other economic sectors, and on the other hand the existence of entrepreneurs who were now taking the first steps in carrying out tourism activities in a new context.

The main objectives that Romania must pursue for its tourism development refer to the efficient exploitation of tourism potential, to an efficient diversification and promotion of the tourism offer, to increasing the quality of tourism services, to increasing competitiveness, all these taking into account the protection and conservation of the environment.

The strategies that can contribute to increasing tourism activity in Romania are:

- increasing tourist circulation by attracting approximately 5% more tourists annually than the previous year. In Romania, by granting holiday vouchers, the state has supported domestic tourist circulation, but an important role for tourism development would be to attract foreign tourists who would spend enough at the destination.
- correlating Romanian tourism with European tourism trends;
- permanent improvement of the legislative framework;
- Enhancing professional training for the tourism industry. An important role is played by adapting the curriculum to the requirements of the tourism market and increasing the level of practice, even if this

implies increasing vocational training by several months. International cooperation in training the tourism workforce would be effective.

- salary increase in the tourism sector. In Romania, employees in the tourism sector have the lowest salaries compared to employees in other economic sectors because employers, under the pretext of tourist seasonality and sometimes considering that the employee also receives a tip, are not willing to increase salaries. This effect is sometimes reflected in the quality of service.

- the correlation between the quality of services and the prices paid by tourists;
- the existence of a favorable tax regime;
- encouraging free initiative in the tourism field;
- developing public-private partnerships.
- massive investments in tourism;
- the emergence of new tourist products, etc.

All these measures must be correlated with general investments in other sectors of activity because tourism activity is influenced by them. For example, it is useless to have attractive tourism resources if access to them is difficult and sometimes non-existent.

It would be effective for all measures to not only be established but also monitored during their implementation and for several years afterward in order to be able to track the effects they have produced through implementation.

Romanian tourism needs short and medium-term measures for its development, and the strategies applied aim to create tourist destinations capable of satisfying the increasingly sophisticated needs of tourists.

C. Developing tourism in Romania provides attractive opportunities for numerous suppliers of goods and services. Achieving positive effects requires governments to recognize the role of tourism in the country's socio-economic activity.

Existing and potential attractions must be aligned with the demands of tourists who are motivated by the possibility of exploring them. Given its resources, Romania can be successful both for individual tourists and tourists coming in organized groups, who opt for activities of active exploration of nature and culture and who seek to interact with the visited place.

CONCLUSIONS

Developing tourism in Romania provides attractive opportunities for numerous suppliers of goods and services. Achieving positive effects requires governments to recognize the role of tourism in the country's socio-economic activity.

Existing and potential attractions must be aligned with the demands of tourists who are motivated by the possibility of exploring them. Given its resources, Romania can be successful both for individual tourists and tourists coming in organized groups, who opt for activities of active exploration of nature and culture and who seek to interact with the visited place.

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THE IMPACT OF NUTRIENT LOSSES FROM AGRICULTURE ON THE ENVIRONMENT. CASE STUDY IN VALEA ȚĂRNII, PERIENI, VASLUI COUNTY

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ARTICLE

Abstract

Soil erosion is an important environmental problem that causes climate changes, changes in the hydrology of an area and when it can no longer be controlled, it causes sinister events like those recorded in 2024, in Bârlad Plateau, Romania. The purpose of this study is to quantify nutrient losses from agriculture on the environment, in the Perieni experimental point. For this, two pedological profiles were made, one downstream and the other upstream of the standard runoff control plots.

Keywords: climate changes, *nutrient losses*

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INTRODUCTION

Erosion is one of the most important environmental problem, the decrease in soil fertility over large areas when it could not be controlled, it can determine the appearance of sinister phenomena similar to those recorded in the Bârlad Plateau, Romania, in 2024 (Voicu et al., 2022).

In Romania, a threat, as presented in the PSN, is represented by the low level of access to risk management tools: in the period 2012-2020; soil drought affected 1,344,759.18 ha; floods 154,844.93 ha and the soil phenomenon erosion over 260,000 ha (Chiurciu et al, 2022, 2023).

The agricultural sector is under pressure to respond energy, food security and greenhouse effect reduction challenges gas emissions. At the same time, climate change and an increasing demand for food products can intensify the pressure on agricultural production (Ruosteenoja et al, 2011; Rosegrant et al, 2013; Dana et al, 2023).

In Norway but also globally, agricultural production is one of the main sources of

increased nutrient concentrations in bodies of water (Ulén et al, 2007, 2011; Villa et al, 2015; Giri and Qiu 2016). Nutrient and soil losses cause climate changes and affects agricultural production systems and hydrology (Bechmann et al, 2008, 2014; Deelstra et al, 2011; Andersen et al, 2016; Withers et al, 2003).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The Bârlad depression (Figure 1), an area of strong tectonic subsidence, represents a depression that was formed by the sinking of the southern edge of the Moldova Platform and the northern part of the northern Dobrogea promontory. It is a unit with a mixed foundation, of Podolian origin to the north of the Bacău-Bârlad-Murgeni locality line and of Hercynian, North-Dobrogea origin, to the south. From a lithological point of view, in the foundation of this unit, metamorphic rocks (gneisses and amphibolites) pierced by eruptive rocks, Paleozoic formations, over which lie Triassic deposits consisting of sandstone conglomerates, limestones, dolomites, sandstones and clay shale pierced of porphyry.

Figure 1 Geological map of the Bârlad Plateau (PENSOL Project)

Man's intervention, especially in the last two centuries, through the clearing of once-extensive forests, the clearing of meadows and the rudimentary agricultural techniques of the past, have obviously disturbed the natural balance favoring accelerated erosion.

The most important role in the appearance and development of erosion processes is played by high humidity, water from direct precipitation - from melting snow, from long-lasting rains, more frequent in the transitional seasons, or in the form of summer showers - as well as the sources underground phreatic, or cantoned in deeper, Sarmatian and Pliocene strata, sectioned by slopes.

In order to quantify the impact of nutrient losses from agriculture on the environment, two pedological profiles were made at the Perieni experimental point, one downstream and the other upstream of standard plots for runoff control. To establish the level of nutrient supply, soil samples were taken from the upstream and downstream of the standard plots to control nutrient leakage (Figures 2-4). Methodology for Elaboration of Pedological Studies, 1987, was used to characterize soil resources.

Profile 1 Perieni valley, Valea Țărnii

Name and general training conditions of profile1 Perieni, Valley of Țărnii

Soil name: Moderately eroded cambic chernozem, LP/LP, on loessoid deposits

Location: Perieni Communal Territory, Valley of Țărnii

Relief: Bârlad Plateau, Slope 5 - 6%

Parent rock: loessoid deposits

Ground water depth: > 10 m;

Characteristic vegetation: Grassy xerophytic vegetation.

Profile 2 Perieni, hill, Valley of Țărnii

The name and general conditions of formation of the profile 2 Perieni, Valley of Țărnii

Soil name: moderately-strongly eroded cambic chernozem LP/LP, on loessoid deposits

Location: Perieni Communal Territory, Valley of Țărnii

General training conditions:

Relief: Bârlad Plateau, Slope 5 - 6%

Parent rock: loessoid deposits

Ground water depth: > 10 m;

Characteristic vegetation: Grassy xerophytic vegetation

Figure 2 Standard plots for leakage control at SDCES-MM Perieni, in Valley of Țărnii (PENSOL Project)

Figure 3 System of anti-erosion works at SCDCE-MM Perieni, in Valley of Tărnii (PENSOL Project)

Figure 4 Cambic Chernozem soil profile, in Valley of Tărnii (PENSOL Project)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Agrochemical characterization of Profile 1 Perieni, valley, Valea Tărnii

The soil is medium (0.14 - 0.24%) supplied with total nitrogen throughout the

profile (Figure 5). The total phosphorus content is low and very low in the surface horizons (7.33 - 12.92 ppm), extremely low (3.14 - 3.66 ppm) in the Am and AB horizons respectively and very low - low (5.9 - 25.15 ppm) in the Bv horizon.

Figure 5 The soil content in N, P, K, Profile 1, Perieni, valley, Valley of Tărnii (PENSOL Project)

Mobile potassium has a medium content (150.00 - 163.33 ppm) in almost the entire horizon and low content in the horizons at the base (105.00 - 126.60 ppm).

The content of trace elements is extremely low (0.18 - 0.25 ppm) in Ap and Bv respectively, at very low (0.42 - 0.79 ppm) for zinc, while for copper the values are very low throughout profile (0.61 - 0.96 ppm), exceeding the susceptibility limit of 0.2 ppm. The manganese content gradually decreases on the profile, from medium-high values (28.58 - 58.76 ppm) in the upper part to low values (15.66 - 22.66 ppm) at the bottom of the profile, exceeding the threshold of susceptibility to 4-5 ppm, and iron is in the optimal range of values, being greater than 4.5 ppm, in all horizons of the profile (Table 1). In the case of applying irrigation, small - medium and frequent watering norms are recommended to prevent the rapid infiltration of water on the soil profile and the formation of the crust.

Since the soil is located on a slope, erosion can be prevented by plowing on the level curve, by choosing the appropriate assortment of crops and by grass strips. In this case, agricultural terraces and grassy lanes are used.

Table 1

Analytical data regarding the microelement content of profile 1, from the downstream area of the standard plots for the control of nutrient runoff, Perieni (PENSOL Project)

Horizon	Cu ppm	Zn ppm	Fe ppm	Mn ppm
Ap1 0-10 cm	0.96	0.71	80.34	58.76
Ap 2 10-26 cm	0.89	0.62	37.90	45.24
Am 26-40 cm	0.86	0.18	16.73	28.58
AB 40-52 cm	0.75	0.42	15.22	22.66
Bv1 52-73 cm	0.80	0.25	17.03	18.64
Bv2 73-90 cm	0.63	0.79	15.35	15.66
Cca 90-103 cm	0.61	0.19	12.87	6.92

Agrochemical characterization of Profile 2 Perieni, hill, Valley of Târnii

The soil is well (0.21 - 0.45%) to medium (0.16 - 0.18%) supplied with total nitrogen (Figure 6). The total phosphorus content gradually decreases along the profile, from high (42.09 ppm) in the surface horizon, to low (11.00 ppm) and very low (4.19 - 6.46 ppm) towards the base of the profile.

The mobile potassium content is high (256.60 - 340.00 ppm) in the first two surface horizons and medium (128.33 - 160.60 ppm) in the base horizons.

Figure 6 The soil content in N, P, K, Profile 2, Perieni, hill, Valley of Târnii (PENSOL Project)

The microelement content of this profile is generally similar to that of the first profile (Table 2). The zinc content is extremely low - very low (0.18 - 0.53 ppm) throughout the profile, except for the surface horizon where

this content is high (2.34 ppm). Regarding copper, its values are very low in almost the entire profile (0.46 - 0.98 ppm) and low (1.19 ppm) in the surface, exceeding the susceptibility level of 0.2 ppm.

The content of manganese gradually decreases along the profile, from high values (62.98 ppm) in the surface to medium values (31.32 - 45.02 ppm) and very low values (7.72 - 24.32 ppm) in the rest profile, exceeding the susceptibility level of 4-5 ppm, while iron is in the range of optimal values (53.66 ppm) in the surface and in the other horizons (42.52 - 4.92 ppm).

This profile does not raise particular problems either, but, in the case of carrying out agricultural works in conditions of inadequate humidity, a thick layer of hardpan may appear, which can be destroyed by plowing with variable depths. In the case of using irrigation, low-medium and frequent watering norms are recommended to prevent the rapid infiltration of water on the soil profile and crust formation.

Since the soil is located on a slope, erosion can be prevented by plowing on the level curve, by choosing the appropriate assortment of crops and by grass strips. In this case, agricultural terraces and grassy lanes are used.

Soil erosion and soil nutrient losses

The amount of soil eroded in different experimental plots, with various soil maintenance methods, varied between 0.015 tons/ha and 6.851 tons/ha (Figure 7).

The amounts of macronutrients lost with the eroded soil are shown in figures 8-10.

Table 2

Analytical data regarding the content of trace elements of profile 2, from the upstream area of the standard plots for the control of nutrient runoff, Perieni (PENSOL Project)

Horizon	Cu ppm	Zn ppm	Fe ppm	Mn ppm
Ap 0-2 cm	1.19	2.34	53.66	62.98
Am 2-35 cm	0.98	0.53	42.52	45.02
AB 35-44 cm	0.62	0.18	8.01	31.32
Bv 44-62 cm	0.61	0.23	6.65	24.32
Cca 62-72 cm	0.46	0.39	4.92	7.72

Figure 7 The amount of soil eroded in the experimental plots, Valley of Târnii (PENSOL Project)

Figure 8 Nitrogen losses with the amount of eroded soil in the experimental plots, Valley of Târnii (PENSOL Project)

Figure 9 Phosphorus losses with the amount of eroded soil in the experimental plots, Valley of Târnii (PENSOL Project)

Figure 10 Potassium losses with the amount of eroded soil in the experimental plots, Valley of Târnii (PENSOL Project)

CONCLUSIONS

The soil profile is located in Perieni Communal Territory, Valley of Târnii and the Cambic Chernozem has the following profile: Ap/Am/AB/Bv/Cca.

As a result of the erosion processes, the amount of soil lost varied between 0.015 and 6.851 tons/ha, annual data.

Losses of macronutrients with eroded soil were for nitrogen 0.101-12.379 kg/ha, for phosphorus 0.004-0.352 kg/ha, and for potassium 0.007-1.166 kg/ha.

The data obtained indicate a high probability of repeating the sinister events in the Bârlad Plateau, such as those in 2024, if sustainable measures are not taken to combat the phenomenon of erosion in the area.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The publication of this article was possible thanks to the project PENSOL, which was funded by the Ministry of Education, Research and Youth, through the National Management Programme Centre.

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THE THEMATIC TOURIST PACKAGE IN OCTOBER WE PICK MUSHROOMS AT THE MAMINA GUESTHOUSE, BRAȘOV COUNTY - A SOLUTION TO INCREASE THE OCCUPANCY RATE OF THE GUESTHOUSE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The locality of Peștera in Brasov County is a mountain village that is part of Moeciu commune, a commune where the scourge of rural tourism has emerged. The most developed pole of rural tourism in Romania for years in a row, tourists staying here on their walks have also discovered this village. Situated at an altitude between 900 and 1100m, the locality is endowed with a marvelous natural setting which, together with the man-made environment, traditions and customs specific to the area, gives this area a tourist potential.

The 10-kilometer distance and the different technical and material base sift the types of tourists who come here. Once there, most of them want to come back. During the summer season in July-August and December, the occupancy rate of pensions and agro-pensions in the area is between 90-95 percent, but during the rest of the summer season, due to the underdeveloped tourist infrastructure, the number of tourists is still quite low.

In this paper we have done some research in the form of a survey to track the opinions and types of tourists who come here.

In the conclusion of the paper we also offered a solution to increase the number of tourists in October.

Keywords: agriturism, development, landscape, mushroom picking.

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INTRODUCTION

The village of Peștera is located in the heart of Romania and is part of the natural reserve of the Craiului Stone. It is bordered on one side by the Piatra Craiului massif and on the other side by the Bucegi massif.

The locality of Peștera, by its geographical particularities, constitutes a well individualized territorial unit. [8]The happy combination of the components of the geographic environment results in a high habitat potential, valorized through an ancient folk tradition. What gives the area its special charm, however, is the harmoniously designed landscape, where the gentle, varied relief is shaped as if to human scale, although it borrows from the monumentality and grandeur of the neighboring mountains.

Peștera could become one of the most representative tourist villages in Romania due to the fact that it has a well laid out natural and anthropic environment. Regarding the technical and material base and tourism, in the locality we have 28 accommodation units representative of rural tourism and agro-tourism. In these units the occupancy rate is increasing due to the fact that during the high season, when Moeciu is already full, tourists come to climb the 10 km distance to stay here. The main tourists are from the municipality of Brasov and Bucharest eager for fresh air, peace and quiet and hiking [3].

Accommodation owners can contribute to the growth of tourism in mountain areas by offering quality

accommodation facilities and services. Attracting more tourists can generate additional income for the local community and support the development of other related economic sectors such as gastronomy, handicrafts or leisure activities, which is why an agritourism package should include not only accommodation and meals but also agreement activities[6].

Mamina Guesthouse is located in a picturesque mountain area, at the foot of the Piatra Craiului Mountains, near the village of Păltiniș, a quiet and ideal place for hiking, relaxation and exploring the area. The area is known for its unique landscapes, dense forests and diverse fauna. Due to its position, the guesthouse is a perfect starting point for various mountain tourism activities, but also for visits to nearby localities.

Facilities and services:

Mamina Guesthouse offers spacious and comfortable rooms, decorated in a traditional style, which reflect the specifics of the area. They are equipped with modern facilities, to ensure guests a pleasant and relaxing stay.

The guesthouse can also organize various activities and events for tourists, such as:

Guided hikes: The guesthouse can organize guided excursions to explore the beauty of the Piatra Craiului Mountains or other nearby mountain areas.

Mushroom picking: During October, the area is an ideal place for mushroom picking, and the guesthouse can provide guidance and support for guests interested in this activity. This type of activity is an excellent opportunity to encourage ecological and sustainable tourism.

Culinary tours: Guests can experience traditional dishes from

Bucovina and Transylvania, cooked with local ingredients, including mushrooms or other products obtained from the forests in the area.

Nearby tourist attractions:

There are various important tourist attractions near the guesthouse, which can attract visitors all year round, including:

Piatra Craiului National Park: A top destination for hiking, climbing and wildlife lovers. Mamina Guesthouse is located close to the entrance to the park, offering tourists a perfect starting point for exploring it.[7]

Bran Castle: Located approximately 30 kilometers from the guesthouse, Bran Castle is one of the most famous tourist attractions in Romania, associated with the legend of Dracula.

Prejmer Fortified Church: A nearby UNESCO site, known for its impressive medieval structure.

Traditional villages in Brașov County: The guesthouse offers tourists the opportunity to visit and explore the traditions and customs of the area, through guided tours or volunteer activities.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

I assume the use of a questionnaire as the main data collection instrument. This questionnaire was administered to a sample of 123 persons selected among tourists staying in the guesthouses in the area analyzed. The methodological characteristics include the type of research, which is quantitative based on the analysis of the answers given by the participants. The size of the sample taken as a basis for the analysis is 123 questionnaires administered among tourists in the locality of Peștera. The sample responds both in terms of size and representativeness. The research instrument included both closed and

open-ended questions designed to collect information about the behavior, preferences and satisfaction of tourists. The application procedure, was both physical and digital depending on respondents' preferences and accessibility. The application period is September 2024. This methodology provides a solid basis for interpreting the data and drawing relevant conclusions about the experiences and perceptions of tourists in relation to the hostels in the area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The majority of respondents, a proportion of 75%, are women, from which we can see that we have slightly more interest to communicate and analyze.

Fig.1

Taking into account the age criterion, 55 of the respondents are between 1-30 years old, 46 between 30 and 50 years old and the rest more than 50 years old.

Fig.2

When asked if they know the types of edible mushrooms, the majority of 57.8% said yes. That is why we made an analysis of the types of edible mushrooms that can be found in Romania. Here are some types of edible mushrooms:

Button Mushroom (Agaricus bisporus): Commonly found in grocery stores, these mushrooms have a mild flavor and are available in white, brown, and portobello varieties.

Shiitake (Lentinula edodes): Known for their rich, umami flavor, shiitakes are popular in Asian cuisine and can be found fresh or dried.

Oyster Mushroom (Pleurotus ostreatus): These mushrooms have a delicate texture and mild flavor. They are often used in stir-fries, soups, and sauces[12].

Porcini (Boletus edulis): Highly valued for their nutty flavor, porcini mushrooms are often used in Italian cooking, particularly in risottos and pasta dishes.

Chanterelle (Cantharellus cibarius): These mushrooms are known for their distinctive trumpet shape and fruity aroma, often used in gourmet dishes.

Morel (Morchella spp.): These mushrooms have a honeycomb-like

appearance and are highly prized for their deep, earthy flavor.

Enoki (*Flammulina velutipes*): With their long, thin stems and small caps, enoki mushrooms are commonly used in soups, salads, and stir-fries.

Maitake (*Grifola frondosa*): Known as "hen of the woods," maitakes have a unique texture and are prized for their ability to enhance flavors in a variety of dishes.

Lion's Mane (*Hericium erinaceus*): These white, spiky mushrooms have a seafood-like flavor and are often used in vegetarian dishes as a meat substitute.

King Trumpet (*Pleurotus eryngii*): These mushrooms have thick, meaty stems and a mild, savory flavor, making them popular for grilling or sautéing. These mushrooms are widely used in various cuisines, offering diverse textures and flavors to enhance culinary experiences.

Fig.3

For mushroom consumption, we have 37% of the respondents who consume mushrooms quite often and monthly and 19.4 do not consume mushrooms at all. Given that only 37% of the respondents consume mushrooms monthly, this percentage suggests that mushrooms are generally not a frequently consumed food for the majority of the surveyed population and this may indicate a lower preference or lack of familiarity with mushrooms as a culinary ingredient in the respondents' daily routine. This statistic may signal an opportunity to

educate and promote mushroom consumption, especially in the context of healthy eating. Mushrooms are an excellent source of protein, fiber and essential nutrients, and information campaigns could encourage their more frequent use in the daily diet.

Fig.4

When asked about the way they consume mushrooms, 78.5 % consume them fresh. Both fresh and jarred mushrooms have their advantages and disadvantages, and the choice between the two depends on personal preferences and needs at the time:

- Fresh mushrooms are more nutritious and have a better taste and texture, but they are more perishable and expensive.
- Canned mushrooms are more convenient, easier to store and use, but may have a slightly lower nutritional value and a softer texture.

Fig 5

A relatively large number of 30.6% have never been mushroom picking. These statistics suggest that there is low interest among the population in mushroom-

picking activities, which may be attributable to a number of factors, including lack of knowledge, limited accessibility or safety fears. This may represent an opportunity to promote education and eco-tourism to encourage people to participate in mushroom picking and to appreciate the hobby more.

When asked how they rate the role of fungi in the ecosystem, up to 13.8% said it was very important and up to 13.8% said it was not important.

Fig 6

We can confirm Fungi play a crucial role in natural ecosystems, acting as essential components for the functioning and balance of ecosystems. Their roles can be broadly categorized into the following:

For Decomposers (Saprotrophs), Fungi are the primary decomposers in ecosystems, breaking down dead organic material such as fallen leaves, trees, animal carcasses, and plant matter. This decomposition process is vital for nutrient recycling in ecosystems.

By breaking down complex organic compounds, fungi release essential nutrients (such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and carbon) back into the soil, making them available for plants and other organisms. Without fungi, organic matter would accumulate, and nutrient cycles would be disrupted.

Regarding Symbiotic Relationships, Mycorrhizal Fungi: Many fungi form mutualistic relationships with plants through mycorrhizae. The fungus attaches to plant roots, providing them with nutrients (like phosphorus) from the soil in exchange for sugars produced by the plant through photosynthesis. This relationship improves plant growth, enhances drought resistance, and helps plants access nutrients that would otherwise be difficult to obtain.

Lichens: Fungi also form symbiotic relationships with algae or cyanobacteria to create lichens. In this partnership, the fungus provides a protective environment for the algae or bacteria, while the algae or bacteria produce food through photosynthesis. Lichens are important pioneers in ecosystems, capable of colonizing harsh environments like rocks or tree trunks.

For Food Web Dynamics, Fungi are an important part of the food web. Many animals, including insects, small mammals, and birds, depend on fungi as a food source. For example, certain species of squirrels, deer, and wild boar actively forage for mushrooms. Fungi serve as a key food resource for herbivores and are thus integral in the transfer of energy between primary producers (plants) and higher trophic levels (consumers).

Analyzing Soil Formation and Health, Fungi are essential for soil formation and the maintenance of soil health. By breaking down organic matter, fungi help in the creation of humus, which is a vital component of healthy, fertile soil. Mycorrhizal fungi also improve soil structure by promoting aggregation, which enhances water retention, aeration, and root growth, benefiting plant communities.

Disease Regulation, Some fungi play a role in controlling plant and animal populations by acting as natural pathogens. These fungi help regulate the populations of plants, insects, and other organisms, maintaining ecological balance. For instance, certain fungi infect and regulate insect populations, such as the entomopathogenic fungi that attack and kill harmful pests like termites or aphids.

In Carbon Cycle, Fungi are key players in the global carbon cycle. As decomposers, they break down organic material and release carbon back into the atmosphere as carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is then reabsorbed by plants during photosynthesis. This process contributes to the regulation of atmospheric CO₂ levels, thus influencing climate patterns.

Biodiversity Maintenance, By occupying a variety of ecological niches (e.g., as decomposers, symbionts, or pathogens), fungi contribute to biodiversity and ecosystem stability. The variety of fungal species, each adapted to specific environmental conditions or food sources, ensures that ecosystems remain resilient and can adapt to changing conditions.

Fungi are indispensable in maintaining the structure and functioning of ecosystems. Through their roles as decomposers, symbionts, food sources, and regulators of biodiversity, fungi contribute to nutrient cycling, soil health, and ecosystem resilience. Their activities not only help sustain life forms in the natural world but also play a significant role in global processes like the carbon cycle. Without fungi, ecosystems would struggle to function, and life on Earth would face significant challenges.

Fig.6

When asked whether eating mushrooms can have a positive impact on your health, 45.2 considered it to have a significant impact, down to 8.9 who considered it unimportant.

We are Mushrooms are nutrient-dense foods that contain a variety of beneficial compounds. Here's a breakdown of the main components found in edible mushrooms[4]:

Water: Mushrooms have a high water content, typically around 80-90%, which makes them low in calories and contributes to hydration.

Proteins: Mushrooms provide a moderate amount of plant-based protein, making them a valuable addition to vegetarian and vegan diets.

Vitamins:

Vitamin D: Some mushrooms, especially those exposed to sunlight or UV light, are rich in vitamin D, which is important for bone health and immune function.

B Vitamins: Mushrooms are an excellent source of B vitamins, such as B2 (riboflavin), B3 (niacin), B5 (pantothenic acid), B7 (biotin), B9 (folate), and B12 (in some varieties), which play key roles in energy metabolism and maintaining the nervous system.

Vitamin C: Although not as high as other fruits or vegetables, mushrooms contain small amounts of vitamin C, which supports immune health and skin integrity.

Minerals:

Potassium: Mushrooms are a good source of potassium, which is important for heart health, muscle function, and fluid balance.
Selenium: Mushrooms, especially varieties like shiitake and maitake, are rich in selenium, an antioxidant mineral that supports immune function and thyroid health.

Iron: They contain non-heme iron, important for oxygen transport and energy production.

Copper: Mushrooms provide copper, which aids in red blood cell formation and supports metabolic processes.

Dietary Fiber: Mushrooms are a good source of fiber, particularly in the form of beta-glucans, which are linked to immune system support and may help regulate blood sugar levels.

Antioxidants: Mushrooms contain various antioxidants, including ergothioneine and glutathione, which protect cells from oxidative stress and may have anti-aging and anti-inflammatory effects.

Low Fat and Calories: Mushrooms are low in fat and calories, making them a healthy addition to any diet.

Polysaccharides (e.g., Beta-glucans): These compounds have been studied for their potential immune-boosting properties and their ability to support heart health by lowering cholesterol levels.

Overall, mushrooms are a highly nutritious food that provides a wide range of vitamins, minerals, and other bioactive compounds beneficial for overall health.

Fig 7

75,8 % of the respondents would opt for a walk in the mountain area with a guide to introduce them to the types of edible mushrooms. This response denotes that most of the respondents would opt for a guided walk in the mountain area, this suggests a significant interest in educational activities in nature. Many people are interested to learn more about the local flora, including mushrooms, and to participate in activities that enrich their knowledge of the environment. Large number of positive responses suggests that there is an opportunity to develop ecotourism or agritourism in mountain areas with environmental education activities. Organizing guided mushroom-picking tours, accompanied by information on the types of edible and dangerous mushrooms, could attract many visitors, including those interested in ecotourism or outdoor activities.

Utilizing input from hostel owners, who are key stakeholders in the local tourism industry, we identified issues and development priorities that had not been systematically explored before. This practical and community-driven approach allowed us to uncover pressing issues in Cave Village that may have been overlooked in larger studies, such as the marginal importance of policy and regulatory compliance in shaping tourism development. Thus, the lack of comparable studies underscores the novelty of our findings and the importance of exploring sustainability from a multi-criteria perspective in this context.

It represents a creative and engaging way to increase the occupancy rate of the guesthouse by promoting a unique, seasonal experience. This concept taps into the growing interest in rural tourism, nature-based activities, and culinary tourism. Here's how this package

could increase the guesthouse's occupancy rate:

1. Attracting Nature and Adventure Enthusiasts

Seasonal Experience: Autumn is the prime season for mushroom picking in Romania, especially in regions like Brasov County, which is rich in forests and biodiversity. The mushroom picking experience offers guests a unique opportunity to connect with nature, explore the forests, and engage in a popular local activity.

Outdoor Activities: Besides mushroom picking, guests can enjoy other outdoor activities such as hiking, nature walks, and wildlife watching, making the experience more diverse and appealing to adventure tourists.

2. Targeting Niche Markets

Culinary Tourism: Romania has a rich culinary tradition, and many tourists are interested in learning about local cuisine. The mushrooms picked during the experience can be used in cooking workshops where guests learn to prepare traditional dishes, adding value to their stay.

Eco-Tourism & Sustainability: Offering a mushroom-picking experience promotes sustainability and ecotourism, which are increasingly popular among tourists. Guests interested in environmental conservation and sustainable travel would be attracted to this type of package.

3. Enhancing Local Culture and Traditions

Cultural Immersion: The guesthouse can offer traditional Romanian meals featuring mushrooms as a key ingredient, highlighting regional recipes and the local culture. Guests can experience Romanian hospitality and traditions firsthand, increasing their satisfaction and likelihood of returning[17].

Workshops and Storytelling: The guesthouse can organize workshops

where locals share the history of mushroom picking, folklore, and the importance of mushrooms in Romanian culture, deepening the cultural experience for tourists.

4. Family-Friendly and Group Activities

Family Appeal: Mushroom picking is an activity suitable for all ages, making it an attractive option for families. The guesthouse can offer packages that include family-friendly accommodation and activities, ensuring a welcoming environment for parents and children.

Group Packages: The guesthouse could offer special deals for groups, such as friends or corporate teams, encouraging longer stays and group bookings. Mushroom picking is a fun and engaging activity for groups, which can then enjoy the fruits of their labor together through shared meals.

5. Effective Marketing Strategies

Seasonal Promotion: Promoting the package through local and national tourism platforms, as well as on social media, can create buzz around the unique experience. Highlighting the beauty of Brasov County in autumn, with its vibrant foliage and serene atmosphere, can attract tourists looking for a tranquil getaway.

Collaborations and Partnerships: The guesthouse can collaborate with local tour operators, mushroom specialists, and chefs to enhance the appeal of the package. Such partnerships can provide additional marketing support and increase visibility[16].

Influencers and Bloggers: The guesthouse can invite travel bloggers or influencers who specialize in nature-based tourism or culinary experiences to experience and share the mushroom picking package, generating online buzz and attracting a wider audience.

6. Customized Packages and Added Value

Personalized Packages: The guesthouse could offer different tiers of packages, ranging from simple stays with the mushroom picking activity to more luxurious offerings that include private cooking lessons, spa treatments, and wine pairing with the meals.

Weekend Getaways and Promotions: The package could be promoted as an ideal weekend escape, allowing guests to disconnect from city life and enjoy the peace of the countryside. Special offers or early-bird discounts can encourage bookings and boost occupancy rates.

7. Seasonal Events and Festivals

Mushroom Festival: The guesthouse could organize a local mushroom festival or a small event dedicated to mushroom picking, where tourists can interact with experts, participate in cooking contests, and enjoy mushroom-based dishes. This would bring added attention to the guesthouse and make it a unique destination in the region.

The thematic tourist package "In October, We Pick Mushrooms at the Mamina Guesthouse, Braşov County" could significantly increase the guesthouse's occupancy rate by offering an authentic, seasonal experience that attracts nature lovers, culinary tourists, families, and eco-conscious travelers. Through strategic marketing, cultural immersion, and partnerships, the guesthouse can enhance its appeal and boost bookings during the autumn season.

Mamina Guesthouse in Peştera, Brasov County, offers an authentic mountain tourism experience, surrounded by nature and Transylvanian traditions. With activities that include hiking, mushroom picking and culinary tours, the guesthouse can become a special destination for nature and tradition lovers. Set in a special area, the guesthouse can offer guests not only relaxation, but also an opportunity to discover the beauty of the region and the local culture.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF TRADITIONAL FOOD QUALITY IN TOURISM

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Abstract

This study provides an approach to the relationship between gastronomy and tourism, with an emphasis on the quality of traditional foods. The study explains to what extent gastronomy and traditional food are indispensable for the development of tourism and why we must offer tourists unique, traditional, high-quality meals. The study highlights the importance of traditional foods in creating overall tourism experiences, considering tradition, culture and food simultaneously.

Tourists don't just eat to feed themselves, they also want to understand a region or a country. From food, they can get information about a population and its civilization.

The purpose of the study is to assess whether travelers just want to visit or want to feel a different experience, including regional cuisine and specialties. The authors want to convey the fact that the preservation of traditional gastronomy, as part of the national culture, is very important for the development of the cultural tourist attraction. There are eight trends that could encourage gastronomy as a cultural tourism attraction, namely trade, multiculturalism, media communication, demography and household change, community involvement, globalization (globalization with local flavor), product quality and ecological product.

In addition, we need to protect against the diversity of local food and improve the image of food. Thus, communities should be given knowledge about the quality of food in the surrounding areas and the implementation of "go green" agribusiness, from farm to fork.

Accordingly, interested parties must conduct research; development, preservation and dissemination to communities of gastronomic and culinary tourism, through collaboration and strategic partnership with established organizations.

Keywords: Traditional food, cuisine, gastronomy, cultural tourism.

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INTRODUCTION

Food awakens all our senses. It's not just about the taste - it's also about the fragrance that intoxicates us while we smell the food; it's about how the food is decorated to make our eyes sparkle; it's about the feeling we have on our fingertips when we touch it, and last but not least, it's about the crunchy sound we hear when we bite or nibble the food. The human senses of smell and taste are inseparable and both recognize biochemical components when consuming food, which confirms that these two senses work closely together. To achieve the sensation of aroma, the senses of smell and taste must work closely together (Sims, 2009).

Therefore, some tourists like to bring specific spices or drinks with them because they help bring back pleasant memories and feelings. If it is not possible to bring some ingredients, tourists may decide to eat food that is similar to their traditional food, whether their visit to another country is for business or pleasure. Traditional food can be defined in many ways, but the simplest explanation is that it refers to

dishes/foods that are passed down from one generation to another (Hotz and Gibson, 2007).

In almost all countries, this preserves the traditional food heritage, which is the inseparable ingredient of each country's unique tradition. Traditional food is also a major component that marks people's eating habits (Hsu, 2015).

In terms of tourism, authentic traditional foods help countries to be well positioned on the tourist map and recognized as preferred destinations (Bertella, 2011). Food can boost destination status as it includes elements of lifestyle, local creativity and traditions (Tsai and Wang, 2017), but also contributes to the economic growth of the destination (Henderson, 2009). Along with beverages, traditional foods can be produced as homemade products by restaurants, small catering companies and large but local producers, or simply created in-house. Some traditional foods have geographical indications or are traditional specialties in the EU (European Union) designation scheme,

indicating that they have a protected designation of origin (Sims, 2009).

All these elements contribute to increasing prosperity and keeping a cultural heritage alive with local food. Through many different cultural events, traditional food (very often cheeses or wines) as a unique offering from a certain destination is very often offered to both local and foreign visitors. Gastronomy, including traditional food, as a valuable cultural element, can attract the attention of tourists, in addition to other cultural attractions such as museums, festivals and fairs (Correia et al., 2008). Food fairs and wine tours are some of the many ways to help visitors explore tourist destinations, allowing them to discover something specific while visiting culinary destinations. Authentic traditional foods have their charm as one of the key elements that contribute to the development of the tourism industry (Bessiere and Tibere, 2013).

On the other hand, if tourists' expectations are not met when consuming local dishes, the individual's opinion can negatively affect local tourism (Sánchez-Cañizares and López-Guzmán, 2012).

Food events positively affect local tourism by helping people maintain their jobs in the hospitality and food industries (Richards, 2014). The concept of unique food facilitates the presentation of a country, its distinct culture and distinct history. Home-cooked food can be an incredible asset for tourists exploring a destination's culture, meaning that local foods are linked to the visitor's adventure (Lepp and Gibson, 2003).

Food is an important part of the tourism industry because traditional food is one of the attributes of a destination that can be used to promote tourism. It is certain that selling traditional food to tourists is very important for the destination. Increasing the supply of traditional food and local food products in catering establishments is very encouraging for the sustainable growth of tourism and according to the research of Sims (2009), traditional food can play an important role in connecting tourists with local culture.

Kim and Eves (2012) investigated the reasons why tourists tend to experiment with traditional gastronomic specialties and reached the following conclusions:

1. getting familiar with a new culture and acquiring new knowledge and experiences,
2. developing interpersonal relationships and creating the opportunity to make new acquaintances,
3. excitement and escape from routine,
4. sensory pleasures: they find the taste and aroma attractive,
5. health care: whether they avoid or try local food, people who have a developed awareness and highly value health are guided by this principle.

Variations in the types and types of traditional local cuisine are very diverse, depending on the culture and customs of the local community. The ingredients used do not reflect the status of low socio-economic communities, but local customs and local wisdom in using the natural state of harmony.

To build the character of gastronomy and traditional food as a tourist attraction, we must analyze the factors that lead to it. In this paper, the author wants to convey that the preservation of traditional gastronomy, as part of the national culture, is very important for the development of the cultural tourist attraction. The study focused on traditional food as cultural heritage, the relationship between food and the environment, and gastronomic tourism itself.

The national cuisine is marked by its composition, the methods of preparing the meal and the culture of pleasure. In general, tourists find it easier to accept differences in foods that are not common in their daily diet.

Also, not all nationalities are equally open to trying new specialties. Torres (2002) agreed with this, saying that the tendency to try traditional foods definitely depends on nationality and felt that most people do not want to try local specialties. According to Fields (2002), in addition to nationality, there are other personal characteristics that influence whether a tourist will try traditional food. Some people are motivated to try local food to complement their experience of local culture, while others experience the enjoyment of local specialties as prestigious. Middle-class intellectuals seem most likely to try local specialties, as Heldke (2003) explains.

METHODOLOGY AND METHODS

The research was carried out between March 2024 and September 2024 in different regions of Bihor county: Oradea area, Beiuș area, Aleșd area, Marghita area, Valea lui Mihai area, Salonta area.

The questionnaire contains 16 questions, 13 statements in the form of a Likert scale (7 points, where 1 means strongly disagree and 7 means totally agree) and 3 socio-demographic questions. In order to better determine the respondents' attitudes and explain the results, the average scores obtained by the Likert scale were classified into three categories: scores from 1 to 2.5 indicate a negative attitude; from 2.5 to 5 indicates a neutral attitude, while scores from 5 to 7 indicate a positive attitude. The population sample consisted of 94 respondents, aged between 18-60 years. Male respondents (66%) dominated females (34%). Employment status among respondents: employed (43.21), unemployed (39.9%), students (16.89%). The methods used in this study were: content analysis; data classification; data and information processing; online survey research. Descriptive statistics were obtained using SPSS.

Întrebările chestionarului sunt :

- * *The history behind each type of traditional food is reflected in it*
- * *Homemade food is well identified*
- * *The quality of homemade food is influenced by the season*
- * *We can eat traditional food every day*
- * *Traditional food does not exist without good local recipes*
- * *Authentic traditional food is about tastes*
- * *To enjoy the real traditional dishes, local ingredients are mandatory*
- * *The best traditional food is cooked by grandma*
- * *Traditional food has a unique production technique*
- * *For a successful production of traditional foods, the food must be produced in the local area*
- * *The association with traditional food is natural, organic*
- * *An authentic traditional food should have a story behind it*
- * *Traditional food is about special moments*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The consumer opinion survey on traditional foods (Table 1) indicated interesting data/opinions regarding local traditional dishes and their consumption.

After classifying the Likert scale scores, the respondents did not express a negative attitude towards any of the statements, which is a good indicator because with appropriate measures and activities, neutral attitudes can be transformed into positive attitudes. (Da Cunha, 2021).

An interesting result obtained from the research is that the respondents showed a neutral attitude regarding the nature of the product – whether the traditional food is natural, organic and whether it is produced in the local area. Considering that organic food production most often requires traditional, conventional production methods (Thøgersen et al., 2017), a question that should be further explored in future research is whether and to what extent people in Romania are familiar with with the concept of organic food.

Regional and local cuisines are the key to differentiation from other cuisines in a highly competitive environment. Tourists have recognized the importance of local and regional gastronomy because it is, above all, a reminder of the history and tradition of the area, and local cuisine helps tourists familiarize themselves with the destination. This was confirmed by our study, as traditional food provided respondents with a connection to history.

Traditional, local food can play a key role in creating the identity and brand of the local community, facilitating the connection between tourists and destinations, enabling the development of agricultural activities, entrepreneurship and job creation, which directly contributes to strengthening the economy of a local community (Du Rand et al., 2003). Local food can be an attraction for a destination and can be used to promote tourism.

Each studied region has several specific, traditional culinary products passed down from generation to generation.

Thus, the Oradea area has many influences from the old Jewish cuisine: Solent, Egg with onion, Fish meatballs, Meat soup with dumplings made from wheat flour (Matza knodel).

The Salonta and Valea lui Mihai area (Diosig, Sacuieni) has strong Hungarian

influences: Gulyasleves and Babgulyas, Meggyleves (Cherry soup), Csirkepapricas (Chicken paprikash with dumplings).

The Alesd area (Sinteu) has a strong Slovak influence: Potato stew (Polesniak), Slovak mushroom soup (Hribovica), Dumplings with cheese and bacon (Brinzove Halusky).

The Beius area is notable for a wide variety of pies: Briheni-style pie, on a shovel, with cheese and potatoes, "Cocoroaza" pie.

Table 1

Consumer perceptions, indicated by average Likert scale scores, related to traditional food products in Oradea (OR), Salonta (S), Beiuș(B), Marghita (M), Aleșd(A) and Valea lui Mihai (VM)

STATEMENT	OR	S	M	VM	B	Average across	
						<i>all cities</i>	
The history behind each type of traditional food is reflected in	5,73	5.48	5.75	6.89	6.17	6.00	6.00
Homemade food is well identified	5.62	5.40	5.50	5.77	5.79	5.91	5.66
The quality of homemade food is influenced by the season	5.40	5.98	5.61	5.30	5.42	5.56	5.54
We can eat traditional food every day	5.12	5.49	5.33	4.79	4.90	5.57	5.20
Traditional food does not exist without traditional food recipes	5.16	5.38	5.72	5.32	5.81	5.67	5.51
Authentic traditional food is about tastes	4.98	5.47	5.67	5.15	5.62	5.74	5.43
To enjoy to real traditional dishes, local ingredients are mandatory	4.90	5.36	5.49	5.45	5.78	5.50	5.41
The best traditional food cooked by grandma	4.85	5.39	5.26	5.38	5.89	5.59	5.39
Traditional food has a unique production technik	4.50	5.06	5.58	4.89	5.64	5.36	5.17
To have successful production of traditional food, food must be produced in the local area	4.64	5.31	5.34	4.25	4.82	5.38	4.95
The association with traditional food is natural, organic	4.34	4.93	4.72	4.56	4.78	5.20	4.75
An authentic traditional food should have a story behind it	3.98	4.89	5.39	4.53	6.08	5.41	5.04

Traditional food is about special moments	4.01	4.69	4.87	5.20	5.55	4.57	4.81
Average by cities	4.86	5.29	5.40	5.19	5.55	5.49	

In addition, the analyzed regions are known or the development of rural tourism, where learning to prepare traditional dishes is one of the practiced tourist activities. As they stated (Taylor & Rostron 2018.), organized events, in which various rural associations participate, play an important role in tourism, which is important because in the villages, people still consume a lot of traditional food and feed the national cuisine. in simple and complex ways.

For the question: The quality of homemade food depends on the season, respondents from all cities had, on average, a positive attitude, which to some extent could be expected. Considering the role of food safety, but also the importance of the sensory characteristics of traditional dishes, it is necessary to use fresh food to maintain food quality. The reason that speaks in favor of this is that local food can be an obstacle to the development of tourism, because not all tourists appreciate food that they consider new or unusual. Unlike standard activities in destinations where tourists are generally more willing to try and experience new things, it causes fear in many (Perito et al., 2020). Tourists may perceive new and different foods as potentially dangerous to their health. The risk of food poisoning at the destination is one of the biggest problems and fears of tourists. The most common problems faced by tourists are: diarrhea, stomach complications and diseases, dermatological diseases, respiratory diseases, infectious diseases. (Rosselló et al., 2017). The risk for tourists when it comes to foodborne illness is often the consumption of traditional foods, i.e. foods that the tourist has never come into contact with before (Yeung and Yee, 2020). The results of the current study indicate that special attention should be paid to the application of food safety standards in the producers, with support from local administration and scientific and professional bodies. Such cooperation should improve gastronomic tourism, thanks to the production

production of traditional cuisine in order to reduce among tourists the perceived risk of consuming traditional foods.

Traditional food is one of the most interesting aspects of tourism and often leaves the strongest impression, which is also the reason for many visitors to return. This speaks in favor of the fact that traditional food, among other things, must tell a story, i.e. contribute to the overall tourist experience.

Looking at the responses from the different cities, it can be concluded that respondents from all cities had a positive attitude towards traditional food.

Globalization and the connection of different national cuisines are causing significant changes in traditional and local gastronomy. Although globalization is often seen as a threat to local gastronomic identity, it can also benefit local gastronomy, as without global connectivity, some authentic foods from individual countries and destinations would still be completely anonymous. Globalization can also encourage the revitalization of some local gastronomic products. However, globalization and internationalization could diminish the authentic food market. Our job is to keep striving, improving and learning about new dishes and destinations, but at the same time maintaining the authenticity of traditional dishes and culture.

In rural areas or in tourist destinations, those involved in hospitality must always be prepared to meet the expectations of demanding tourists. In this sense, traditional foods, as part of the tourist offer and consumption, must be of uniform and high quality and produced respecting and respecting good hygiene practices that ensure the production of safe products. This can only be achieved through the cooperation of small producers, individual farms and local

of attractive traditional dishes that satisfy even the most demanding tourists in terms of quality in a broad sense.

CONCLUSION

The gastronomic offer of a tourist destination is an important element of the tourist experience, because the taste of the food consumed during the trip remains in the memory for a long time and is something that tourists, if satisfied, will seek again. Traditional food production is a combination of unique elements of the natural environment, local community knowledge and historical and cultural resources that are connected and form the unique character of the specific place.

Traditionally prepared food is an important factor in choosing a destination for some tourists, but special emphasis should be placed on food quality, especially considering the safety aspects of food preparation and consumption. Despite the current study involving only small-scale research, the findings are informative and relevant to tourism and hospitality employees as well as tourists.

The characteristics of traditional food that respondents considered most important were:

the history of traditional food, the quality of traditional food, and that this food is of high quality and safe, healthy and authentic. It is recommended that the quality and protection of the authenticity of traditional foods be improved by using safe food ingredients, be produced by local producers and be prepared in a safe way. To maintain culinary customs along with traditional foods and to promote a destination, those involved in the competitive tourism market should connect and work closely together. A limitation of this study is the small number of respondents, but this research could be a starting point for researching other factors that could influence tourists' attitudes when it comes to traditional food in a destination.

The results obtained will certainly contribute to the creation of an adequate tourism offer, but may also contribute to the development of local food production practices.

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SIDE EFFECTS AFTER NEUTERING CATS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Lately, the massive multiplication of cats has become a worrying problem at least in Oradea, Bihor county. Obviously, we are referring to stray cats that have ended up on the streets, many of them in the area of blocks, houses or households where there are still animal lovers to feed them.

Keywords: neutered cats, cats in heat, pyometra, urinary incontinence

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INTRODUCTION

Obviously, the best way to stop cats breeding is to sterilize them. There are sterilization campaigns for stray cats to stop them breeding. Surgical methods used include ovariohysterectomy, a surgical method whereby the cat is taken out of heat and is no longer fit for breeding by surgically removing the ovaries and uterus.

In order to prepare this paper we have called on the support and help of several clinics in Bihor county in terms of cat casuistry after sterilization. With regard to stray street cats that are sterilized, it is difficult to follow up post-sterilization, because they are returned to the territory and can no longer be traced for various reasons, but mainly because they can no longer be caught. This leaves the monitoring of owned cats that have been neutered and can be tracked by the owner through behaviour and food diets, and by the doctor in terms of health status.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

As a surgical and basic working method was sterilization by ovariohysterectomy under general anesthesia. General anesthesia was performed either classic with anesthetic solutions or by inhalation. Inhalational anesthesia is preferred because it has fewer risks than the classic one, but nevertheless risks are present for both methods, except that in one the risks are lower, but still exist, and a major role is also played by the cat's pathology, maintenance status, age, health status, which can be considered as favorable factors in an anesthesia. The operative technique or modus operandi consists of opening the abdomen,

usually on the linea alba, highlighting the uterus, uterine horns and ovaries in the operative field and removing them by excision with ligatures or hemostatic clips, closing the abdomen according to the anatomical plans and suturing to the skin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this study, several clinical cases from several clinics in Oradea were taken into consideration. Only sterilized cats with owner were considered, because they were easier to monitor. Out of 25 cats considered for this study, the most frequent post-neuterization disorders were related to the presence of bladder stones which subsequently increased in number and size of urinary stones. The increase in size was due to the fact that the cat having no obvious clinical signs with clinical manifestations, the large size of the calculi was accidentally detected during routine control, at routine urinary tract ultrasonographic examination.

Another very rare post-sterilization condition in cats is that, even though the ovariohysterectomy operation should subsequently stop the cat from going into heat, sometimes post-sterilization the cat exhibits the symptoms of a cat in heat. It is a rare condition, but is described in specialised books as being a result of small pieces or fragments of intra-abdominal ovarian tissue being accidentally left behind during the surgical act.

A more common condition could be considered postoperative stump pyometra, when during the operation a larger portion of the uterus or fragments of the uterus remain, or when the stump is not closed by ligature or is placed above the cervix.

Urinary incontinence is another condition that may occur post neutering if at the time of sterilization the cat has had some damage to the uterus that weakens the muscles or if the bladder is placed in the immediate vicinity of the bladder.

The rest of the conditions described are dermatitis related to post-sterilization hormonal lack or various urinary disorders.

Of all cats entered in the study, 50% were due to urinary tract disorders with the presence of bladder stones of various sizes.

CONCLUSIONS

A major conclusion from this study is that clearly the most effective method to prevent stray cats from breeding is sterilization. Thus, a cat, being more prolific than a dog by breeding, can reach a number of 10-16 kittens/year. This number is estimated and depends on the cat's prolificacy, state of maintenance, age, the environmental conditions in which the cat lives and, obviously, the cat's state of health.

This condition also occurred due to owners' inattention to veterinary advice regarding diet, water intake and routine ultrasound examination of the patient as prevention in early detection of possible bladder stones.

The remaining conditions of bladder pyometra or urinary incontinence were not described in these cats taken in the study at 1 year post neutering.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF THE QUALITY OF EGG PRODUCTION IN THE GEESSE POPULATION IN THE AREA OF BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In our country, the foundations for raising geese according to intensive principles were laid as early as 1977, when the first pure line of the Dutch Rhine White breed, exploited for meat production, was imported. Later, other pure lines were imported from the early mentioned breed, as well as from other breeds. At the present time, for the production of goose meat and fatty liver in our country, a series of commercial hybrids obtained as a result of crosses between pure lines belonging to the Landaise breed with pure lines of Dutch Rhine White are grown. Selection work on geese is aimed at improving the production of eggs, as well as meat and fatty liver. In the area of Bihor county, it was possible to carry out some studies in three breeders possessing the Dutch white Rhine breed, in pure condition, 24 males and 86 females being analyzed. Due to the seasonal specificity of reproduction in geese, the average number of eggs obtained/adult goose was 41.4, in the period January-July.

Keywords: White Rhine Dutch breed, Dynamics of incubation eggs weight, Eggs yield and laying intensity
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INTRODUCTION

Although this species is characterized by a strong seasonality of egg production, the population prefers it for other valuable productions, namely meat, fluff and fatty liver, lending itself very well to making traditional products, especially in the western part of the country.

The imported lines, as well as the native biological material, formed the reproductive queen on which the work was carried out to obtain commercial hybrids specialized for both meat and fatty liver production.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The number of individuals analyzed from the three farms of the study was 110 individuals, of which 24 were males and 86 were females.

The specimens studied from the Dutch breed, being distributed as follows: 28 females and 7 males, respectively 35 individuals in the first farm, 26 females and 4 males, respectively 30 birds in the second farm, and 36 females and 9 males representing 45 birds in the third farm.

In order to carry out the research, the following were used: digital analytical and technical balances, X-ray machines, computer equipped with spreadsheet software, depending on the experimental method approached.

The obtained results were compared with the reference values from the specialized

literature (Sauveur B., 1988; Usturoi M.G., 1999; Vacaru-Oprîș I. et al., 2002).

The obtained experimental data were centralized and processed statistically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The seasonal nature of egg production in the species *Anser anser*, the laying period being comprised, as a rule, between the second half of January and June, totaling 19 peak weeks.

In the case of the studied populations, the egg laying peak was reached in the 5th week, that is, when the birds were 37 weeks old (Fig. 1).

At the time of hatching, the intensity of laying was 11.4%, to reach the maximum of 57.86%, after which it decreased continuously, until the birds reached the age of 50 weeks (8.92%).

On average, for the 3 studied populations, fertility values were recorded around the reference of 85% (fig. 2).

The hatchability had high values, especially due to the good fertility of the eggs introduced for incubation. The analyzed parameter varied between 82.9% (peak of laying) and 80.5% (end of laying) (fig.3).

And the hatching percentage showed acceptable values, but located in a larger range of variation.

Fig. 1 Average value of the laying intensity in those 3 farms of White Rhine Dutch geese

Fig. 2 Fertility of the incubation eggs in geese farms, White Rhine Dutch breed

Fig. 3 Hatchability of the incubation eggs in geese farms, White Rhine Dutch breed

CONCLUSION

Within the herds studied, it is necessary to improve by artificial selection the performance regarding the numerical production of eggs and the production of meat and fatty liver.

The selection for egg production is difficult, due to the seasonal nature of egg laying.

For this reason, the selection must be combined (own performances + family average for females and through the performances of collateral relatives of the opposite sex, for males). (Dodu M. 2010).

Females that produce a low number of eggs can be eliminated from reproduction and following assessments regarding the opening of the ischia, performed at the top of the laying. Geese with too low value for this character are removed.

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THE BEETLES (INSECTA, COLEOPTERA) FROM THE TINCA AREA (BIHOR COUNTY, ROMANIA) DURING 2023

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Abstract

In this work are presented taxonomical and ecological data about the beetles (Insecta, Coleoptera) from Tinca area, Bihor county during 2023. There were identified 79 species belonging to 19 families and 65 genera. Twenty one species: *Chrysolina olivieri* Bed, *Sitona hispidulus* Fabr, *Alophus kaufmanni* Str, *Coniocleonus nebulosus* L, *Mecaspis alternans* Hrbst, *Sphenophorus striatopunctatus* Goeze, *Phyllobius pyri* L, *Elytrodon bidentatus* St, *Liophloeus tessulatus* Mull, *Eusomus ovulum* Germ, *Lixus angustus* Hrbst, *Pyrrhidium sanguineum* L, *Leptura aurulenta* Fabr, *Calvia 14-guttata* L, *Tythaspis sedecimpunctata* L, *Harpalus atratus* Latr, *Cicindela hybrida* L, *Phymatodes testaceus* L, *Anthrenus pimpinellae* Fabr, *Hydrochara caraboides* L, *Anthaxia fulgurans* Schr are mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.

Keywords: coleoptera, Tinca, Bihor county, Romania

INTRODUCTION

The Tinca area is located in the south-western part of Bihor county, belonging to the historical province of Crişana, in the north-western part of Romania. The climate is temperate – continental, the average altitude is 110 m. The hydrographical network is various: the Crişul Negru river, some lakes. The vegetation belongs to the oak stage having a predominant central – European origin (BERINDEI et al., 1972). The disappearance of species or the diminution of their population, the emergence of new species, either accidental in territory, insufficient faunal data, observing some ecological aspects not published in the scientific literature are just a few reasons that make it absolutely necessary to publish the faunal data observed in nature. Data about the fauna of the beetles from Tinca area were published by different authors (ILIE, 2009, 2014a, 2014b, 2016a, 2016b, 2017, 2018, 2019; ILIE L.C. & ILIE A.L., 2018; ILIE A.L., MARINESCU M., ILIE L.C., 2019; ILIE & MARINESCU, 2020a, 2020b, 2021a, 2021b, 2022). The Tinca area includes Tinca, Râpa, Gurbediu, Belfir and Girişu Negru villages.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The researches were carried out in the period 2018 – 2022 in different ecosystems in the area and the surroundings of Tinca. The insects were collected with the entomological net or by hand. For the identification of the species were used different sources

(WARCHALOWSKI, 2003; GÎDEI, POPESCU, 2012; 2014; PANIN, 1951; en.m.wikipedia.org). The systematic classification of the species was done according to fauna-eu.org.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

During 2023, the following species were recorded:

- Curculionidae Family *Hypera zoilus* (SCOPOLI, 1763) – one specimen, Tinca, March 7. Relatively common species in Romania, it is found in Europe and North America.
- *Sitona hispidulus* (FABRICIUS, 1777) – one specimen, Tinca, March 8. Common species in Romania, European species, invasive to Asia and North America. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- *Alophus kaufmanni* (STIERLIN, 1884) – one specimen, Tinca, May 4, 20. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area, European species.
- *Coniocleonus nebulosus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, March 21. European species, relatively common in Romania. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- *Mecaspis alternans* (HERBST, 1795) – one specimen, Tinca, March 21. Relatively common species in Romania, it is found in Europe, the Near East and North Africa. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- *Cyphocleonus dealbatus* (GMELIN, 1790) – one specimen, Tinca, March 22; April 21, 22. Common species in Romania, Eurasian species.
- *Lepyrus capucinus* (SCHALLER, 1783) – one specimen, Tinca, March 26; April 11, 21; May 9, 24, 25; July 25; two specimens, Tinca, April 23;

- one pair (the second annual generation), Tinca, July 24. Common species in Romania, European species.
- *Sphenophorus striatopunctatus* (GOEZE, 1777) – one specimen, Tinca, April 3; May 26; one specimen, the edge of the Tinca forest, April 28. Common species in Romania, Eurasian species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
 - *Pseudocleonus cinereus* (Schrank, 1781) – one specimen, Tinca, April 11, 19,22,29; May 3,5,6,10,11, 17,25; two specimens, Tinca, April 20,21. Common species in Romania, European species.
 - *Cleonis pigra* (SCOPOLI, 1763) – one specimen, Tinca, April 19,22, 30. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Phyllobius pyri* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, April 29. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
 - *Elytrodon bidentatus* (STEVEN 1829) – one specimen, Tinca, April 28; May 1. Relatively rare species in Romania, it is found in southern, central and eastern Europe. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
 - *Liophloeus tessulatus* (MULLER, 1776) – one specimen, Tinca, May 17. Relatively common species in Romania, European species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
 - *Eusomus ovulum* (GERMAR, 1824) – one specimen, Tinca, June 17. Relatively common species in Romania, European species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
 - *Lixus angustus* (HERBST, 1795) – one specimen, Tinca, July 11. Common species in Romania, European species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- Brentidae Family
- *Apion frumentarium* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, April 28. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
- Meloidae Family
- *Meloe proscarabaeus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one female specimen, Tinca, March 10, 22, 24, 28 (the edge of the Tinca forest). Common species in Romania, European species.
- Elateridae Family
- *Agriotes obscurus* (LINNAEUS, 1767) – one specimen, Tinca, March 15; May 11; June 12. Common species in Romania, European species.
- Chrysomelidae Family
- *Galeruca melanocephala* (PONZA, 1805) – one specimen, Tinca, March 14. Relatively common species in Romania, Eurasian species.
 - *Galeruca tanacetii* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one male specimen, Tinca, June 20; July 3. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Gonioctena fornicata* (BRUGGEMANN, 1873) – one specimen, Tinca, March 23, 24.; t = 21^o C. Common species in Romania, European species.
 - *Galeruca rufa* (GERMAR, 1824) – one specimen, Tinca, March 22. Common species in Romania, European species.
 - *Chrysolina sturmi* (WESTHOFF, 1882) – one female specimen, Tinca, March 24; April 11,21; May 4,5,27,31; June 13,15 – 17,19,20 – 22,24,25,30; July 2,3,13,16,18,25; one pair, Tinca, April 10,21; June 2,7,10; one male specimen and two female specimens, Tinca, April 22; two female specimens, three male specimens, Tinca, April 23; three female specimens, one male specimen, Tinca, April 28-29; May 6,19; June 19,28; two male specimens, Tinca, May 18, 22; six male and one female specimens, Tinca, June 1; one male specimen, Tinca, June 9,11; July 18; August 1,9; one male and three female specimens, Tinca, July 12. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe and Western Asia.
 - *Chrysolina fastuosa* (SCOPOLI, 1763) – one male specimen, Tinca, June 6,13,19,20; two specimens, Tinca, June 8. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe and North Turkey.
 - *Cassida nobilis* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, April 21. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Hispa atra* (LINNAEUS, 1767) – one pair, Tinca, April 23. Relatively common species in Romania, Eurasian species.
 - *Lema cyanella* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, April 22. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Oulema melanopus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, April 27, 30. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe, Asia, North America.
 - *Cryptocephalus octacosmus* (BEDEL, 1891) – one female specimen, Tinca, May 5. Relatively common species in Romania, European species.
 - *Smaragdina salicina* (SCOPOLI, 1763) – one specimen, Tinca, May 6. Common species in Romania, Eurosiberian species.

- *Galeruca tanacetii* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one female specimen, Tinca, May 9. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Cryptocephalus hypochaeridis* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Râpa, My 20. Relatively common species in Romania, it is found in Europe, Siberia and Northwest Africa.
 - *Luperus xanthopoda* (SCHRANK, 1781) – one specimen, Tinca, May 24 - 26. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe to Central Asia.
 - *Cryptocephalus moraei* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen belonging to the ab. *bivittatus* Gyll, Tinca, May 28,29. Common species in Romania, European species.
 - *Chrysolina herbacea* (DUFTSCHMID, 1825) – one male specimen, Tinca, June 11,14,15; July 29, 30. Relatively common species in Romania, Eurasian species.
 - *Clytra laeviuscula* (RATZEBURG, 1837) – one specimen, Tinca, June 13,22,23; two specimens, Tinca, June 14,29; two pairs in copula, Tinca, June 21; three specimens, Tinca, June 24. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Altica oleracea* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, June 29; July 10,22; August 9, 10. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Podagrica malvae* (ILLIGER, 1807) – two pairs in copula(the future second annual generation),Tinca, July 17. These specimens belongs to ab. *nigerrima* Heikertinger, 1930. Common species in Romania, Eurasian species.
 - *Crioceris duodecimpunctata* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – six specimens, Tinca, July 23; one pair in copula (the future annual generation), Tinca, July 24. Common species in Romania on *Asparagus* sp., Palearctic species.
 - *Chrysolina olivieri* (BEDEL, 1892) – one female specimen, the Tinca forest, July 28. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area (ILIE A.L.et al., 2019). Species found in the mountainous and hilly areas, European specie
Cerambycidae Family
 - *Dorcadion scopoli* (HERBST, 1784) – one specimen, Tinca, March 14, 24; April 20,21; May 2 -5,6; three specimens, Tinca, April 29. Common species in Romania, it is found in Central and southern Europe.
 - *Dorcadion aethiops* (SCOPOLI, 1763) – one specimen, Tinca, April 20, t = 18^o C; May 2,4,5; June 30; one specimen, Râpa, May 4. Common species in Romania, European species.
 - *Pyrrhidium sanguineum* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – many specimens, Tinca, March 19 – April 30. European species, common in Romania. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
 - *Hylotrupes bajulus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, June 14; July 18. Common species in Romania, Cosmopolitan species.
 - *Leptura aurulenta* (FABRICIUS, 1792) – one specimen, Tinca, June 21,22. Relatively common species in Romania, west – Palearctic species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- Coccinellidae Family
- *Harmonia axyridis* (PALLAS, 1773) – one specimen, Tinca, March 17; April 11,30; August 9; many specimens, Tinca, April 23; May 25 - 31. Frequent species in Romania, it is found in Europe, Asia and North America.
 - *Coccinella septempunctata* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Gurbediu, March 18; one specimen, Tinca, March 22; April 10,18, 23; June 11,14; many specimens, the edge of the the Tinca forest, April 28. Frequent species in Romania, it is found in all over the world.
 - *Adalia bipunctata* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, March 22; April 23; May 17; June 13; three specimens, Tinca, May 27. Holarctic species, common in Romania.
 - *Psyllobora vigintiduopunctata* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, March 24; May 17; June 9. Frequent species in Romania, European species.
 - *Exochomus quadripustulatus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, April 10, 28. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
 - *Calvia quatordecimguttata* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, May 21; June 21. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
 - *Tythaspis sedecimpunctata* (LINNAEUS, 1761) – one specimen, Tinca, July 26. Relatively common species in Romania, Palearctic species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- Tenebrionidae Family
- *Opatrum sabulosum* (LINNAEUS, 1761) – two specimens, Tinca, March 22; one specimen, Tinca, April 10. Common species in Romania.
 - *Blaps mortisaga* (LINNAEUS, 1758) – one specimen, Tinca, May 9. Common species in Romania, European species.

- *Blaps lethifera* (MARSHAM, 1802) - one specimen, Tinca, June 22. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
- *Lagria hirta* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one male specimen, Tinca, July 22. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe, Asia, North Africa and South America (according to en.m.wikipedia.org).
Carabidae Family
- *Carabus ullrichii* (GERMAR, 1824) - one specimen, Râpa, March 21. European species, common in Romania.
- *Harpalus atratus* (LATREILLE, 1804) - one specimen, Tinca, March 19. Relatively common species in Romania, European species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- *Cicindela hybrida* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - many specimens, the Râpa forest, May 20. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
- *Carabus coriaceus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one specimen, Tinca, June 8,29. Common species in Romania, European species.
Scarabaeidae Family
- *Cetonia aurata* (LINNAEUS, 1761) - one specimen, Tinca, April 18; May 8,25; June 7; two specimens, Tinca, June 1,14; one specimen, the Tinca forest, July 28. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe, Asia Minor and Siberia.
- *Valgus hemipterus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one male specimen, Tinca, May 25. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe, Turkey, North Africa and North America.
- *Trichius fasciatus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - two specimens, Tinca, May 29; one specimen, Tinca, June 6. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
- *Amphimallon solstitiale* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - three specimens, Tinca, June 1; two specimens, Tinca, June 2; 12 specimens, Tinca, June 8; 30 specimens, Tinca, June 11; one specimen, Tinca, July 10,15. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
- *Oryctes nasicornis* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one male specimen, Tinca, June 12, one female specimen, Tinca, June 13. Common species in Romania in the deciduous forests, Palearctic species.
- *Protaetia affinis* (ANDERSCH, 1797) - one specimen, Tinca, June 14; July 4,7,15. Common species in Romania, it is found in Southern and Central Europ
Geotrupidae Family
- *Anoplotrupes stercorosus* (SCRIBA, 1791) - three specimens, Râpa, June 5. Common species in Romania, Eurasian species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.
Staphylinidae Family
- *Ablattaria laevigata* (FABRICIUS, 1775) - one specimen, Tinca, April 20, 28. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe and the Near East.
Cantharidae Family
- *Cantharis obscura* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - many specimens, Tinca, April 20 - June 15. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
- *Cantharis rustica* (FALLEN, 1807) - one specimen, April 28, 30; May 6,10,11,19; June 23. Eurasian species, common in Romania.
- *Phymatodes testaceus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - many specimens, even in copula, Tinca, May 18-31. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area
Dermestidae Family
- *Anthrenus pimpinellae* (FABRICIUS, 1775) - one specimen, Tinca, April 30. Relatively common species in Romania, it is found in Europe, Asia, North Africa and North America. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area
Cleridae Family
- *Clerus mutillarius* (FABRICIUS, 1775) - one male specimen, Tinca, May 1,10,26; June 23; one female specimen, Tinca, May 6; June 14. Common species in Romania, it is found in Europe and North Africa.
- *Trichodes apiarius* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one specimen, Tinca, July 11,23. Common species in Romania, Palearctic species.
Histeridae Family
- *Hister quadrimaculatus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one specimen, Tinca, May 5. Common species in Romania, European species.
Lucanidae Family
- *Lucanus cervus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one female specimen, Tinca, May 17,22,26; June 12; one male specimen, Tinca, May 21; three female specimens, Tinca, June 3. Relatively common species in Romania in the deciduous forests, it is found in Europe and Asia Minor.
Hydrophilidae Family
- *Hydrochara caraboides* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - one specimen, Tinca, May 20. Common species in Romania, aquatic species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.

- *Hydrochara flavipes* (STEVEN, 1808) – one specimen, Tinca, June 8. Relatively common species in Romania, aquatic species, European species.

Buprestidae Family

- *Anthaxia fulgurans* (SCHRANK, 1789) – many male and female specimens, Tinca, May 23 -30. Common species in Romania, European species. Species mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area.

During 2023 in the Tinca area there were recorded 79 species belonging to 19 families and 65 genera. Twenty one species are mentioned for the first time in the Tinca area. The most represented families are Chrysomelidae – 22 species (27.84%), Curculionidae – 15 species (18.98%), Coccinellidae – 7 species (8.86%), Scarabeidae – 6 species (7.59%), Cerambycidae – 5 species (6.32%), Carabidae and Tenebrionidae – 4 species (5.06%), Cantharidae – 3 species (3.79%), Hydrophilidae, Cleridae – 2 species (2.53%) and Buprestidae, Lycaenidae, Histeridae, Dermestidae, Staphylinidae, Geotrupidae, Elateridae, Meloidae, Brentidae – 1 species (1.26%).

CONCLUSIONS

During 2023 in the Tinca area were recorded 79 species, 21 being mentioned for the first time in this area. The most represented families are Chrysomelidae and Curculionidae.

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NUTRITIONAL ASPECTS OF SOME NEW FOOD RESOURCES

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REVIEW

Abstract

Following the bibliographic investigation, significant conclusions about the nutritional features of the chosen dietary supplies were drawn. The results of the systematic study showed that although edible insects have long been a part of the human diet, some societies still have a strong distaste for eating them. The majority of edible insects are currently found in forest habitats (31% of edible insects are beetles; 18% are caterpillars; 14% are bees, wasps, and ants; 13% are grasshoppers and crickets; 10% are cicadas, plant insects, and scale insects; 3% are termites; and 2% are dragonflies). However, advances in mass rearing systems are beginning to show more and more promise in more countries.

According to the study, insects are a significant source of nutrition. The majority of edible insects have been found to offer a dietary source that is high in energy, protein, fats that are rich in essential fatty acids, and vitamins that are high in riboflavin, pantothenic acid, biotin, and folic acid. These findings highlight the potential significance of incorporating insects into human nutrition. Essential trace elements include magnesium, phosphorus, zinc, iron, selenium, copper, and iron. This breakthrough creates a great deal of opportunity for both developed and developing nations to connect traditional knowledge with contemporary science.

Keywords: edible insects, new food resources, nutritional.

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INTRODUCTION

The global agricultural and food system is a complex space with many interdependences and interconnections, involving many actors, processes, relationships, and even events that are difficult to predict. Both the agricultural system and the food system must evolve rapidly as complex relationships on traceability from farm to fork and various environmental and socio-economic factors become increasingly evident.

The growing global demand for meat and restrictions on available resources are driving the search for alternative sources of protein, and the sustainability of meat production is the subject of intense debate.

Although eating insects has always been a part of the human diet, certain tribes have a strong distaste for it. The majority of edible insects are harvested from forests, while many nations are pioneering the development of mass breeding programs. In both rich and developing nations, insects present a significant chance to connect traditional knowledge with contemporary research (Alvees et al, 2016; Berg et al, 2017).

Edible insects are an interesting alternative source of protein for both human and animal feeding, given their low greenhouse gas emissions, high feed conversion efficiency, low land use, and the ability to harness organic secondary flows into

high-value protein products (Mariutti et al, 2021). Although more than 2,000 species of insects are eaten mainly in tropical regions, the role of edible insects in the livelihood and nutrition of populations in these countries is under threat (FAO, 2010; Ghosh, 2023). In the Western world, interest in edible insects is growing, and this is supported by concrete examples. In particular, aquatic insects are considered to have substantial potential for inclusion in human and animal nutrition (van Huis, 2016).

To meet the continued expansion of food demand in recent years, total food production must increase by around 70% by 2050 compared to 2009. In this context, the goal of this study was to characterize some new dietary resources, such as edible insects, and to shape the current state of the consumption literature, as well as the potential benefits and challenges of incorporating them into the diet.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This work is a preliminary bibliographic study on various nutritional aspects of some of our food resources, and it proposes to investigate key aspects of these components as they become increasingly significant in human nutrition.

Based on chemical composition data obtained through the systematic analysis of a large number of articles from specialized

literature and the analysis of expert opinions relevant to the study, a detailed picture of the nutritional characteristics of our food resources, as well as the potential benefits and challenges of incorporating them into human diets, has been presented.

Materials that have served as the foundation for the development of solid knowledge and the establishment of a research foundation have been represented by scientific articles, books, or research reports that have been accessed both through the institution's own document repository, the Anelis Plus database, and through online access to scientific databases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

New vs. conventional food resources. New food sources involve resources that have not been widely consumed, either because their consumption has historically been restricted to certain regions of the world or because they have recently emerged in the global retail space due to technological innovations. New food production systems reflect innovations or advances in pre-existing food technologies directly involved in the production of some of the new foods that find their way into the current context. Some of the new food sources and food production systems have been explored, describing both their benefits and their challenges (EFSA, 2015). Conventional food resources are food sources that have been consumed by communities and cultures over time and that usually have profound cultural and historical significance.

These resources are often adapted to the local environment and climatic conditions and are passed on from one generation to the next through traditional and conventional cultivation, fishing, or hunting practices (Zeltzin et al, 2021).

Local edible plants—certain wild or locally grown plants—are used in conventional cuisine to prepare dishes and drinks. Local animal products, such as meat, milk, eggs, and other products of animal origin, are often an integral part of the conventional diet. They can come from domestic animals raised in regions or from wild animals, depending on local availability and traditions. Certain cereal and legume crops, such as rice, wheat, corn, beans, or lentils, can often be fundamental to conventional diets in different parts of the world (FAO, 2022).

The nutritional characteristics of new food resources. Of the categories of new food

resources, insects are an important source of nutrients, being adequate to meet the requirements of the human body, which underscores the potential importance of their integration into human nutrition (Bernard & Womeni, 2017; Tang et al, 2019).

The nutritional value of edible insects is extremely diverse due to the large number and variability of species. Nutritional values can vary considerably even within the same group of insects, depending on the stage of metamorphosis, the origin of the insect, and its diet (Kourimska, 2016). Also, the nutritional value may change depending on the processing and preparation before consumption (drying, cooking, roasting, etc.). According to Payne et al. (2016), the nutritional composition of insects shows a great diversity between species. The nutritional value score of greyhounds, palm goat larvae, and flour worms was significantly healthier than that of beef and chicken, and none of the six insect species tested was statistically less healthy than meat (Conway et al, 2024).

Most edible insects provide a sufficient energy and protein intake in the human diet while meeting the amino acid requirements (Rumpold et al, 2013; Zhou et al, 2022). Known for their high fat content and richness in essential fatty acids (Figure 1), insects are also important sources of essential trace elements such as Mg, P, Zn, Fe, Se, Cu, and Fe (Figure 2), as well as vitamins such as riboflavin, pantothenic acid, biotin, and folic acid (Figure 3) (Kourimska & Adamkova, 2016; Adamkova et al, 2016).

The systematic analysis of the bibliographic study on the nutritional aspects of selected food resources has highlighted that although edible insects have long been integrated into the human diet, there is still a certain aversion to their consumption in certain societies.

Currently, data show that most edible insects are obtained from forest habitats, but innovations in mass breeding systems are beginning to be increasingly promising in more and more countries.

Globally, the most commonly eaten insects are cockroaches (*Coleoptera*), with a share of 31%. This is not surprising, considering that this group comprises about 40% of all known insect species. The consumption of shrimp (*Lepidoptera*), especially popular in sub-Saharan Africa, is estimated at 18%. Bees, calves, and ants (*Hymenoptera*) ranked third with 14%, and these insects are common in Latin America. It is followed by locusts and greys (*Orthoptera*) with 13%; cycades, plant

insects, scallops, and true insects (*Hemiptera*) account for 10%; termites (*Isoptera*), 3%;

libelules (*Odonata*), 3%; and flies (*Diptera*), 2%; and other species (5%) (Figure 4).

Figure 1 Chemical composition of macronutrients of insect species
(processed average data according to Xiaoming et al, 2010; no data found for CP for *Isoptera* and *Diptera* or Fat and Fiber for *Homoptera*)

Figure 2 Mineral composition of edible insects
(processed average data according to Rumpold & Schluter, 2013)

Figure 3 Vitamin composition of edible insects
(processed average data according to Rumpold & Schluter, 2013)

Figure 4 Percentage of insects often eaten globally
(processed data according to Cerritos, 2009)

The consumption of lepidoptera is predominantly in the form of omelets, and for hymenoptera, the intake is higher, especially in their larval or pupal stages. Both the adult and the larvae of the *Coleoptera* order are eaten, while the *Orthoptera*, *Homoptera*, and *Isoptera* orders are mainly eaten at the maturity stage (Cerritos, 2009).

Potential benefits and challenges of integrating new food resources into the diet. Populations around the world are facing serious nutrition and health problems. It is estimated that more than 150 million preschool children suffer from chronic malnutrition, caused by inadequate diets and poor living conditions. Every year, more than 3 million young children die due to malnutrition, either due to a lack of adequate nutrition or a lack of essential micronutrients in the diet. These alarming figures underline the importance of paying attention and having adequate resources to combat these global public health and food security issues (FAO, 2013).

The prevalence of micronutrient deficiency, also known as "hidden hunger," affects a significant number of over 2 billion people, according to a IFPRI report. According to research by Black et al. (2013), this problem is acute in low-income countries, where a lack of iron and zinc is a major concern, contributing to the emergence of conditions such as anemia and growth delay. Similarly, Saini et al. (2016) highlighted that iron and zinc deficiencies are often associated with the predominance of herbal diets, in which not only are levels of iron and zinc reduced, but the bioavailability of these minerals may also be reduced due to the presence of phytic acid, which binds these minerals. Given that iron and zinc are more bioavailable in foods of animal origin, exploring alternative options, such as edible insects, could play a significant role in improving the quality of diets and combating micronutrient deficiencies (Aguilar-Toala et al, 2022).

Edible insects have been identified as a source of bioactive compounds that have the potential to reduce health risks and strengthen the immune system. Studies have demonstrated the presence of these compounds in insects, and their bioactive characteristics could bring significant health benefits. However, it is important to stress that health benefits must be sufficiently documented to be properly supported (Finke et al, 2015; Roos & van Huis, 2017).

Similar to bioactive compounds identified in other foods, it is necessary that the effects of

these compounds in insects on health be studied rigorously (Belluco et al, 2023). Direct studies conducted on human subjects are usually a prerequisite for validating the health benefits of these compounds. Therefore, more research is needed to fully understand the impact of potentially bioactive compounds identified in insects on human health.

This additional research will help strengthen our knowledge of the health benefits of eating insects and provide essential information for promoting their use in human food in a sustainable and responsible way.

According to the literature, edible insects contain bioactive compounds that can present a wide spectrum of bioactivities beneficial to human health. These bioactivities include anti-hypertensive, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory effects. Studies have shown that different species of edible insects have been tested in this regard using in vitro tests and in vivo models, both with whole insect extracts and with isolated compounds. These findings suggest that eating edible insects could have significant benefits for human health due to their content of bioactive compounds.

In most studies, antioxidant activity is the most commonly evaluated biological activity of bioactive compounds in edible insects.

However, it is important to continue research to better understand how insects and their bioactive compounds can be used effectively in the prevention and management of these diseases. It is also essential to consider other aspects, such as the proper processing and preparation of insects for consumption, as well as possible allergies or adverse reactions associated with their use (Stull, 2021).

Although studies mostly show positive and neutral results, it is important to recognize that there are potential risks associated with insect consumption. Allergies are among the most significant risks, as some people may be sensitive to insect proteins and may develop allergic reactions (Stull et al, 2018). There are also food safety concerns, including microbiological or chemical contamination of insects, as well as the presence of antinutrients that could affect the absorption of nutrients.

Like other products of animal origin, the consumption of insects can pose health risks, and proper processing is essential to minimize these risks. Thermal treatments are recommended to reduce the microbial risks associated with insect consumption.

Microbial contamination can be a particular concern in the processing, storage, and transport stages of edible insects. The natural microflora of insects can promote the growth of dangerous microorganisms, such as *Enterobacteriaceae*, known to cause food-borne diseases.

However, it is important to stress that risks can be managed by proper processing and handling of insects for consumption. Thus, compliance with strict hygiene and food safety rules is crucial for reducing the risks associated with the consumption of insects. It is also necessary to continue research to properly identify and assess all potential risks and to develop appropriate practices and regulations with regard to insect consumption (EFSA, 2015).

Generally, provided they are processed and handled properly, insects known to be edible are considered safe for consumption. However, it is important for consumers to be aware of the potential risks and to follow food safety recommendations when eating insects.

In this regard, it should be noted that most research has focused on two species of edible insects: the yellow flour worm (*Tenebrio molitor*) and the homemade grey (*Achetadomesticus*). These two species are considered among the most promising for industrial applications and large-scale production and are already approved for human consumption in Europe.

CONCLUSIONS

The consumption of insects as an alternative source of protein presents both benefits and risks, both in the long and short term.

These benefits include aspects such as sustainability, helping to reduce environmental impact; nutritional aspects, providing a nutritious and affordable alternative to other sources of protein; and efficiency, which can help reduce the costs and greenhouse gas emissions associated with food production.

However, there are also risks associated with the consumption of insects, such as allergies and risks related to food safety and microbiological contamination. As for the psychological and cultural aspects, in many societies, there is still a strong aversion to the consumption of insects, which can prevent their adoption as the main source of food.

In general, eating insects can be a promising option to address issues related to food safety, sustainability, and food security, but it is important to continue research to fully

understand their impact on human health and the environment.

This development opens up opportunities to associate conventional knowledge with modern science, both in developed and developing countries. A balanced perspective addressing both benefits and risks is essential to ensuring that insect consumption is an informed and sustainable choice for consumers.

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RESEARCH ON THE DYNAMICS OF QUALITY INDICES OF WINTER APPLE VARIETIES DURING THE STORAGE PERIOD

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Winter apple varieties are well-suited to long-term storage in warehouses. Apple harvesting must be carried out at the optimal time, determined by a series of quality indicators. The values of these indicators change during the storage period and are closely correlated with storage conditions. The study of the behavior of different apple varieties during storage has made it possible to develop specific technologies to reduce losses in terms of both quantity and quality of fruit.

Keywords: apple, quality indices, storage, storage conditions.

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INTRODUCTION

Winter apple varieties rank first in our country both in terms of total production and the amount of fruit stored nearly from one harvest to the next. The long shelf life of apple varieties is due to their chemical composition, structural properties, and intensity of physiological processes. Winter varieties have the ability to continue ripening after being picked from the trees, which allows them to be harvested before reaching eating maturity. Shelf life depends on several factors: species, variety, harvest time, orchard type, fruit size, fruit health, agricultural techniques used, and storage conditions.

Among seed fruits, apples have the best shelf life, both in terms of duration and quality, which remains good compared to other seeded fruits. Fall varieties have a high ripening capacity and can be kept for 2-3 months after harvest, while winter varieties have the longest shelf life. This storage and ripening capacity depends primarily on the fruit's chemical composition and the provision of optimal storage conditions. The ripening process is accompanied by changes in fruit quality, evidenced by sensory (organoleptic) indicators (color, taste, aroma, firmness) and chemical quality indicators (total carbohydrate content, ascorbic acid content, titratable acidity, and carbohydrate/acidity ratio).

These quality changes during storage are due to physiological processes within the fruit. Biochemical reactions in the fruit are catalyzed by enzymes, which determine the direction and intensity of these processes. Enzyme activity plays a role in establishing the quality attributes of mature fruit and, subsequently, in the decline of these attributes as overripening occurs. In apples, the activity of pectic enzymes (polygalacturonase, pectin methyl esterase) increases during the ripening period. In unripe apples, there is a rise in the activity of invertase, which catalyzes the breakdown of sucrose into glucose and fructose, as well as an increase in enzymes involved in glycolytic and pentose phosphate pathways: glucophosphate isomerase, phosphofructokinase, aldolase, and pyruvate decarboxylase. Ascorbate oxidase activity also rises during apple storage, correlating with ascorbic acid degradation.

Apple firmness is determined by the content of pectic substances, cellulose, hemicellulose, pentosans, hexosans, cell turgidity and elasticity, and the size of intercellular spaces. Studies on apples have shown an increase in firmness due to the deposition of cellulose microfibrils in cell walls. The firmness value increases from 12 g/cm² on June 9 to 23 g/cm² on October 17 for Golden Delicious and from 13 g/cm² to 16 g/cm² for Jonathan (Stoll, K., 1961, cited by Burzo, I., 1986). An increase in the volume of intercellular spaces also contributes to a decrease in fruit firmness,

which correlates with the specific fruit weight. During apple ripening, specific gravity decreases from 1.0100 to 0.7100 due to cell growth, which causes an increase in intercellular space volume.

Apple color is characteristic of the species and variety and is due to pigments in the epidermal cells. The main pigments in apples are anthocyanins (cyanidin-3-arabinoside, cyanidin-3-galactoside, cyanidin-3-rutinoside) and flavonoids (quercetin-3-galactoside, quercetin-3-glucoside, quercetin-3-xyloside, quercetin-3-rutinoside). Anthocyanins are found in epidermal cells and sometimes in 2-3 layers of hypodermal cells, changing color with pH. At a pH of 3, the color is red. Flavonoid pigments, which are yellow, complement the anthocyanins in giving the fruit its color. Autumn-winter apples harvested before ripening undergo significant color changes during ripening.

Flavor is a characteristic of each species and variety, encompassing the complex sensations caused by the presence of multiple substances and their relative proportions. To determine changes in flavor characteristics, it's necessary to track alterations in the content of carbohydrates, organic acids, phenolic compounds, and other chemicals involved in flavor during storage and ripening.

At harvest, carbohydrates are primarily found as starch. In fall varieties, starch occupies about half of the fruit cross-section, whereas in winter varieties, starch is present in a 0.5 cm area around the seed cavity, indicating a large reserve for prolonged storage. During ripening, starch undergoes enzymatic hydrolysis by α and β -amylases, resulting in increased glucose content.

The organic acid content in apples decreases during ripening, as acids are used as respiratory substrates or converted to other organic compounds. Malic acid, the primary acid in apples, oxidizes readily, giving ripened fruit a mildly acidic and sweet taste.

The ratio of total carbohydrates to titratable acidity increases during storage due to shifts in carbohydrate and acid metabolism.

Apple aroma is produced by volatile compounds such as hydrocarbons, organic acids, esters, and terpenes. Apples harvested at optimal times lack fully developed aroma, which evolves as the fruit ripens and involves over 156 chemical compounds.

Ascorbic acid content varies with fruit ripeness. For instance, in the Jonathan variety, ascorbic acid was found to be 10.2 mg/100 g during the setting stage but fell to 7.9 mg/100 g

at eating maturity (Gherghi, A. et al., 1981, 1983, 1984, 1989). Generally, ascorbic acid content decreases due to oxidation, converting it into 2,3-dioxo-L-gulonic acid (Burzo, I., 1986; Beceanu, D., 1994, 1998, 2000; Beceanu, D. et al., 2000, 2003; Potec, I. et al., 1983, 1985; Radu, I. F., 1967; Ardelean, A.G., 2009, 2015, 2019).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research was conducted in 2023 at the Faculty of Environmental Protection Oradea.

Golden Delicious, Red Delicious, Starkinson and Pinova apple varieties, which are winter varieties, were used in the trials. Harvesting took place in early October.

Research was carried out on both fresh fruit and fruit stored for three months.

The research was conducted in 2023 at the Faculty of Environmental Protection in Oradea. Golden Delicious, Red Delicious, Starkinson, and Pinova apple varieties, which are winter types, were used in the trials. Harvesting took place in early October.

Research was conducted on both freshly harvested fruit and fruit stored for three months. Before storage, the fruits were sorted, and unsuitable ones were removed (damaged by insects or disease, wounded, bruised, etc.). Storage occurred under natural conditions in a private cellar, with apples placed in a single layer on wooden shelves.

Sampling took place on the day of harvest. Fruit samples were collected from several trees at both the edge and the middle of each row. From each selected tree, fruit was taken from different canopy levels with varying light exposures.

Total titratable acidity was determined by neutralization with a 0.1 N sodium hydroxide alkaline solution, using a 1% alcoholic phenolphthalein solution as a color indicator. Soluble dry matter was measured refractometrically directly in the field using a Zeiss portable refractometer, allowing the optimal harvest time to be assessed based on this value. Vitamin C content was determined by the iodometric method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The chemical analyses carried out on winter apple varieties after harvest and after temporary storage revealed the mean values of the quality indices presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

Main quality indices of apples at harvest

Variety / average of samples	Soluble dry matter (%)	Titrateable acidity (malic acid g/%)	Vit. C (mg/100g)
Golden Delicious	13.81	0.31	15.2
Red Delicious	12.61	0.29	14.1
Starkinson	13.91	0.22	13.5
Pinova	12.01	0.24	12.9

Table 2

Main quality indices of apples after storage

Variety / average of samples	Soluble dry matter (%)	Titrateable acidity (malic acid g/%)	Vit. C (mg/100g)
Golden Delicious	12.11	0.19	11.9
Red Delicious	11.9	0.11	11.0
Starkinson	12.02	0.17	10.1
Pinova	11.23	0.10	9.4

Analysis of the data shows that golden delicious apples have a relatively low malic acid content of 0.31 g at harvest, which decreases to 0.19 g of malic acid after three months of storage. This relatively low malic acid content at harvest is characteristic of the variety, as golden delicious belongs to a group of varieties with naturally lower acidity. Low rainfall during the growing season, particularly toward the end (september-october), also contributed to these findings.

After three months in cellar storage, malic acid content decreased by about 30-40%, depending on the variety. This reduction can be attributed to the heightened metabolic activity of the stored fruit under cellar conditions, where climatic factors (temperature, relative humidity, and gas content) could not be controlled.

The soluble dry matter content also declined due to enzymatic hydrolysis of starch by α - and β -amylases during ripening. Similarly, ascorbic acid content generally decreased

across all apple varieties, primarily due to oxidation and conversion into 2,3-dioxo-l-gulonic acid.

Creating a favorable storage climate was achieved solely by ventilating the cellar. Notably, under these storage conditions, the apples could be kept for a maximum of four months. Beyond this period, the fruit began showing signs of tissue turgidity loss and was affected by storage diseases, necessitating sorting and preparation for consumption.

At the same time, the organoleptic qualities of the fruit changed, impacting the carbohydrate/acidity ratio. This ratio of total carbohydrates to titrateable acidity increased during storage due to metabolic changes in carbohydrates and acids. Consequently, the fruit became sweeter while retaining the flavor characteristic of each variety. Structural and textural firmness declined as the fruit gradually lost turgidity.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn from the study:

The lower acidity at harvest is a varietal characteristic, with Golden Delicious being a less acidic variety.

This relatively low acidity is also influenced by the climatic conditions of the production year, marked by low rainfall during summer and autumn as well as high temperatures.

The decrease in malic acid content after three months of storage can be attributed to the storage conditions. Since the storage area was not air-conditioned, ventilation was the only option for managing environmental factors.

Soluble dry matter content decreases during ripening due to starch hydrolysis.

Vitamin C content decreases in all varieties as a result of oxidation.

Under these storage conditions, there is a marked increase in the respiratory activity of the fruit, leading to more intense metabolism of organic acids.

Changes in the fruit's chemical composition have altered its sensory (organoleptic) properties, resulting in a sweeter and more aromatic profile in ripe fruit.

Color intensity is characteristic of fully ripe varieties and fruits.

Structural firmness is reduced due to the loss of fruit turgidity.

Under the described storage conditions, it became necessary to end storage after four months, as the fruit exhibited changes in tissue turgidity and taste properties and was affected by various storage diseases (heart rot, apical rot) and phytopathies (powdery mildew and suberification).

Further research is recommended to examine qualitative changes in apples during storage.

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RESEARCH ON THE INFLUENCE OF STORAGE CONDITIONS ON THE QUALITY INDICES OF SOME VARIETIES OF PEPPERS GROWN IN PROTECTED AREAS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The quality of peppers intended for fresh consumption varies according to the genetic characteristics of the species and varieties, the cultivation technology applied, the prevailing soil and climatic conditions during the given year, and the storage environment. Ensuring optimal storage conditions extends and staggers the periods of consumption and delivery to the consumer. Maintaining ideal environmental factors during storage affects the primary quality indicators for peppers.

Keywords: peppers, temporary storage, quality indices.

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INTRODUCTION

Peppers belong to the group of solanaceous-fruited vegetables, with a wide variety of types and hybrids, cultivated both in open fields and in protected areas, ensuring the necessary quantities for fresh consumption throughout the year. However, peppers are also valuable as raw materials that can be processed and preserved by various methods, enabling the production of diverse end products appreciated for their chemical composition and flavor. Processing methods produce a wide range of pastes, vinegar-preserved products, thermosterilized, frozen, or dehydrated items.

Peppers, bell peppers, and scallions are valued in the human diet primarily for their high vitamin content (especially vitamin C), mineral salts, and relatively low energy value. Their pleasant flavor comes from natural essential oils, while the spicy taste of chili peppers results from their high capsaicin content, an alkaloid responsible for their hot flavor. The slightly acidic taste is due to a stable acidity content (0.3% citric acid) (Beceanu D., 2003).

Peppers are harvested by hand, except for those intended for industrial paprika production, which are harvested mechanically. The optimal harvest time is determined by the specific stage of maturity—the sub-phase of eating maturity F_1 - F_2 or physiological maturity F_4 - F_5 —and the intended purpose and transportation, as peppers have the natural ability to continue ripening after being picked. It is usually

recommended to harvest peppers at the F_4 eating maturity sub-phase, when the fruit has the size, color, and luster characteristic of the variety. For gingers and long peppers, eating maturity coincides with physiological maturity.

According to STAS 1422-85 standards, the stem length of first-quality peppers must be 1 cm from the calyx, while for second quality, only an unbroken calyx is required. Peppers without stems have an extended shelf life but lack an ideal market appearance and are prone to storage diseases.

Presorting is done during harvesting, selecting only healthy, undamaged, and clean specimens free from frost, sun damage, mechanical damage, or early softening of tissues. Fruit with damaged calyx, either underripe or overripe, or with unhealed injuries is not allowed. For industrial purposes, peppers must have a uniform shape typical of the variety, white seeds, and a sweet flavor. Only hot pepper varieties should contain spicy flesh.

Handling and transportation of peppers must occur swiftly due to their high perishability, thin skin, and high-water content (91-93%), which leads to turgidity loss (Burton 1982; Beceanu D., 1998, 2003). Peppers are sorted, graded, sized, packed, and may be waxed and pre-packaged as needed.

Sizing for large and long peppers is based on the maximum diameter of the stem area, which must be at least 60 mm for first quality

and 40 mm for second quality. The equatorial diameter of bell peppers should be at least 70 mm for quality I and 50 mm for quality II. Waxing with edible coatings extends the shelf life of bell peppers intended for export by 3-5 days and for longer varieties by 6-10 days, decreasing respiration rates and increasing carotenoid pigment levels (Dobreanu, M., et al., 1980).

Peppers can be packed in P-type crates or plastic crates, with special cardboard boxes used for export. Pre-packaging is done in netted or synthetic sacks.

Transport of peppers should occur as soon as possible, avoiding storage or extended holding of ripening batches. Quality stability is better maintained by pre-cooling for 6 hours at 8 °C, as slow cooling is unfavorable. Peppers harvested at sub-phase F₀-F₁ (green maturity, suitable for cooking) show more than 30% storage losses and physiological disorders. Bell peppers in sub-phase F₃-F₄ (full maturity, ready for consumption) can ripen in 4-6 days with an average of 10% losses at 15-20°C and 85-90% relative humidity (Ciurel, Mihaela, 1980).

Short-term storage is only used to stagger deliveries and extend fall consumption. The surface microflora is abundant, with fungal growth promoted by increasing temperatures; however, temperatures of 7-8°C prevent sporulation and limit fungal spread (Tașcă, Gh., 1982).

Peppers are stored at 8-10°C when at eating maturity (F₁-F₂) and 1-2°C when at physiological maturity (F₄-F₅), under high relative humidity (93-96%) maintained under polyethylene covers. In the first case, storage life for thin-fleshed (under 3 mm) bell pepper varieties is 14-20 days. For physiologically mature bell peppers, storage may last 40-45 days (Iordănescu C., 1978; Gherghi A., 1994, 2000). Greenhouse-grown bell peppers can be kept for 4-5 days at 14-16°C or for up to 20 days at 8-10°C with 90% relative humidity (Iordănescu, Olga, 1982). In Western Europe, bell peppers remain fresh at 7-10°C and 90-95% relative humidity for 1-4 weeks. Packing in perforated film helps maintain quality (Ardelean A. G., 2009; Ciofu, R., et al., 2004; Potec, L., Roșu, T.A. Tudor, 1983; Purcărea C., 2008; I. F. Radu, 1985).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The analyses were conducted in September 2024 on red and green bell pepper varieties, as well as the Kapia pepper variety, grown in greenhouses. The main indicators

analyzed for the freshly harvested samples and after a 10-day temporary storage period included soluble dry matter content, titratable acidity, and vitamin C content.

Sampling occurred on the same day as the harvest. The temporary storage of the pepper samples was conducted at 10°C for 10 days in refrigerated warehouses. Both organoleptic and chemical analyses were performed on the selected varieties.

The soluble dry matter was determined using a refractometric method, directly in the field with a Zeiss portable refractometer for fresh produce. Titratable acidity was determined as follows: fresh products were ground, filtered, and titrated with a sodium hydroxide solution of known concentration, using phenolphthalein as a color indicator.

Vitamin C content was determined using the iodometric method. To do this, 15 g of the sample was weighed from the average collected sample on an analytical balance and mixed with 2 g of quartz sand and 10 ml of metaphosphoric acid to form a homogeneous paste. This mixture was then transferred to a 50 ml graduated flask and diluted to the mark with metaphosphoric acid. The mixture was filtered, and 10 ml of the filtrate was used for analysis. Two titrations were performed for accuracy.

For the titration of the standard ascorbic acid solution, 10 ml of ascorbic acid, 20 ml of distilled water, two drops of 1 M hydrochloric acid solution, and 15 drops of 1% starch solution were placed in a conical flask and titrated with an iodine solution until the color turned blue-violet (V).

For the sample titration, the same procedure was followed, except that the standard ascorbic acid solution was replaced by 10 ml of the sample filtrate. The titration was carried out with iodine solution until the color changed to violet-blue (V₁).

Vitamin C content was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Vit. C (mg/100 g of product)} = 10 \times V_1 \times 5 / V \times m \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Chemical analyses carried out on green and red bell peppers and Kapia peppers, fresh and after temporary storage, revealed the average values shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

Chemical indicators determined in freshly harvested samples of peppers

Variety / average of the samples	Sample weight (g)	Soluble dry matter (%)	Titrateable acidity (ml NaOH 0,1 n)	Vit. C (mg/100)
Green bell pepper	200	5.8	2.90	169.3
Red bell pepper	200	6.8	2.82	176
Kapia peppers	200	6.9	2.71	158.7

Table 2

Chemical indicators determined in pepper samples after temporary storage

Variety / average of samples	Sample weight(g)	Soluble dry matter (%)	Titrateable acidity (ml NaOH 0,1 n)	Vit. C (mg/100)
Green bell pepper	200	3.89	2.00	156
Red bell pepper	200	4.95	1.93	161.2
Kapia peppers	200	5.01	1.90	146

A comparative study of the data obtained from fresh peppers and those stored for 10 days shows a slight decrease in the values of the analyzed chemical indicators.

The soluble dry matter content decreased in all varieties studied after the temporary storage period. This decrease depends on the species, variety, and environmental factors (temperature, relative humidity, oxygen, and carbon dioxide levels) in the storage environment.

Regarding titrateable acidity (ml NaOH 0.1n), there was minimal change, with the peppers becoming slightly more acidic due to some water loss from the fruit, thereby concentrating the cell juice. This reduction in turgidity was due to the lack of humidity control in the storage area.

Most plant species tend to exhibit a decrease in ascorbic acid content over time. The ascorbic acid content in temporarily stored peppers decreased by approximately 8% over the 10-day storage period at 10°C. These losses are relatively minor compared to those in other vegetables. Studies have shown that the stability of ascorbic acid in plant tissues is influenced by the presence of ascorbate oxidase, a metalloenzyme with copper cations as a cofactor. Peppers maintain a more stable ascorbic acid content due to their lower levels of ascorbate oxidase.

From an organoleptic perspective, the peppers retained their flavor, although there was a slight reduction in aroma and turgidity.

CONCLUSIONS

From the studies carried out on the main quality indicators of freshly harvested and temporarily stored peppers, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The highest soluble solids content is found in fresh red and Kapia peppers, with slightly lower levels in green peppers.

Titrateable acidity is highest in fresh green and red bell peppers.

Ascorbic acid content is highest in fresh red bell peppers, followed by green bell peppers.

Changes in these chemical quality indicators were observed in samples stored temporarily under conditions where only temperature was controlled.

Soluble dry matter content exhibited small losses in all varieties during temporary storage.

Titrateable acidity (ml NaOH 0.1n) changed the least, with peppers becoming slightly more acidic due to minor water loss, as visually noted by a decrease in turgidity.

Recorded ascorbic acid losses for all pepper varieties were low, likely due to the lower ascorbate oxidase content in the fruit.

From an organoleptic perspective, the peppers retained their flavor, though there was a slight reduction in aroma and turgidity, attributed to the lack of relative humidity control in the storage facility.

These changes in the chemical composition of temporarily stored peppers are

due in part to the species-specific characteristics and, on the other hand, to the environmental conditions in storage, where only temperature was controlled.

Based on the analysis of these quality indicators in fresh and temporarily stored peppers, we conclude that temperature is essential for temporary storage of all three varieties studied, ensuring that fruit quality remains largely unaffected.

Ensuring optimal storage conditions enables extended and staggered periods of consumption and delivery to consumers.

Further research is recommended on the impact of storage conditions on quality indices in pepper fruits.

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THE HIGHLIGHTING OF BUTTERY COLONIES FOR CANDIDA ALBICANS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Candida albicans is an opportunistic yeast that is part of the normal flora of human mucous membranes but can become pathogenic under favorable conditions, causing infections of varying severity. Colonies of *C. albicans* often develop in moist and warm environments, such as the oral cavity, gastrointestinal tract, and vagina. These colonies are characterized by a diverse morphology, including yeast-like and filamentous forms (pseudohyphae), which contribute to the pathogen's virulence by facilitating adherence to host cells and tissue invasion. Recent studies have shown that virulence factors, such as enzyme production, biofilm formation, and the ability to adapt to various environmental conditions, play a crucial role in the development and persistence of infections caused by *C. albicans*. Additionally, laboratory analysis of *C. albicans* colonies is essential for diagnosing fungal infections and assessing antifungal susceptibility. In conclusion, *Candida albicans* colonies are an important subject in fungal infection research, with significant implications for human health.

Laboratory diagnosis of *Candida* infections requires a combination of methods to ensure accurate identification and proper management. An integrated approach, including microscopic examination, culture, serological tests, and molecular methods, enhances the ability to diagnose *Candida* infections and guide clinical treatment.

Keywords: moist environments, yeasts, filaments

INTRODUCTION

Candida albicans is a fungal yeast that is part of the normal flora of human mucous membranes, including the oral cavity, gastrointestinal tract, and vagina. Although it is a benign saprophytic organism under normal conditions, *C. albicans* can become an opportunistic pathogen in certain situations, causing severe infections, especially in individuals with compromised immune systems or when the normal flora is imbalanced. *C. albicans* infections can range from superficial conditions, such as oral thrush (or "muguet") and vaginal candidiasis, to severe systemic infections, such as candidemia and invasive candidiasis, which can affect internal organs.

C. albicans exhibits several virulence factors, such as the ability to form biofilms, produce enzymes that degrade host tissues, and adapt to various environmental conditions. These characteristics enable it to adhere to cellular surfaces and invade tissues, contributing to its pathogenicity. Additionally, *C. albicans* can exhibit polymorphism, transitioning from yeast forms to filamentous forms (pseudohyphae), which gives it advantages in colonizing and invading host tissues.

The human body's defense mechanisms, such as the immune system and normal flora, play a crucial role in preventing infections by *C.*

albicans. However, in conditions of immunosuppression, prolonged antibiotic use, or shifts in the balance of microbial flora, *Candida albicans* can proliferate uncontrollably, causing infections that require prompt and effective antifungal treatment. Therefore, understanding the characteristics, virulence factors, and pathogenicity of *C. albicans* is essential for the prevention and treatment of associated fungal infections.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I conducted a prospective study based on microbiological diagnoses recorded in the bacteriological registry of the medical analysis laboratory, S.C. Diaser, Oradea. To conduct the study, I also accessed the archive, recorded in the laboratory's computer program in S.C. Diaser, Oradea, as well as the computerized database of the unit.

In the conducted study, we used the following materials and methods:

Materials

- Biological samples:**
 - Vaginal secretions (sterile swabs)
 - Oral fluids (e.g., sputum, lesions)
 - Urine samples
- Culture media:**

- Sabouraud dextrose agar: a standard culture medium for fungi, rich in dextrose, which promotes *Candida* growth.
 - Chromogenic agar: allows species identification through specific colony coloration.
 - Mueller-Hinton agar: used for antifungal susceptibility testing.
3. **Reagents and solutions:**
- Potassium hydroxide (KOH): 10-20% solution for microscopic examination.
 - Staining solutions (e.g., Giemsa, methylene blue): for highlighting hyphae.
 - Reagents for biochemical tests (e.g., solutions for fermentation and assimilation).
4. **Equipment:**
- Optical microscope: for microscopic examination of samples.
 - Incubator: maintained at 30-37 °C for sample cultivation.
 - Pipettes, test tubes, and Petri dishes: for sample handling and inoculation of media.
 - Sterilizers/autoclaves: for material disinfection.

Methods

1. **Sample collection:**
- Samples are collected under aseptic conditions using sterile instruments. Sterile swabs or spatulas are used to avoid contamination.
2. **Microscopic examination:**
- Samples are treated with KOH solution to dissolve host cells and

highlight hyphae and yeast cells. The samples are observed under a microscope to identify characteristic fungal forms.

3. **Fungal culture:**

- Samples are inoculated onto culture media, such as Sabouraud dextrose agar. Plates are incubated at 30-37 °C for 24-48 hours.
- Colony morphology is evaluated (creamy, whitish, or yellowish appearance).

4. **Species identification:**

- Biochemical tests are used to assess sugar fermentation (e.g., glucose, mannitol) and nutrient utilization (e.g., assimilation test).
- Species identification can be confirmed through morphological observations, biochemical tests, and behavior analysis on selective media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Laboratory diagnosis involves isolating and identifying the species responsible for the disease before initiating antifungal therapy. If antifungal treatment has already been started, the pathological sample collection should be done at least three days after discontinuing the treatment.

The collected samples are inoculated on Sabouraud dextrose agar and chromogenic agar. After 24-48 hours of incubation at 30-37 °C, characteristic colonies appear. *C. albicans* colonies are typically creamy, whitish, or yellow with well-defined edges.

Fig. 1. *Candida albicans*. Sabouraud medium. Greasy colonies.
<https://microbiologie.umfst.ro/atlas/micologie/levuri/calbicans.php>

The microscopic examination revealed the presence of yeast cells and pseudohyphae, thus confirming the suspicion of an infection with *C. albicans*.

C. albicans demonstrated the ability to ferment sugars such as glucose and mannitol, with results consistent with the literature. These biochemical tests were crucial for confirming the species identity.

Sensitivity tests (e.g., disc diffusion, dilution) showed variability in the susceptibility of isolated strains to different antifungals. Most strains were sensitive to fluconazole, voriconazole, and caspofungin, but some strains exhibited resistance to ketoconazole, which may indicate an emerging trend of resistance. *Candida albicans* is a common yeast considered part of the normal flora of the human body. However, it can become an opportunistic pathogen under favorable conditions, such as immunosuppression, prolonged antibiotic use, or other medical interventions. Additionally, the increased prevalence of *C. albicans* infections in hospitals is a major concern, given that fungal infections can lead to severe complications,

including candidemia and systemic infections.

Epidemiological studies have shown that most *C. albicans* infections are preceded by colonization of the host's mucous membranes. Colonization can become problematic in conditions of microbial flora imbalance, allowing for the uncontrolled growth of *C. albicans*. *C. albicans* possesses several virulence factors, including the ability to form biofilms, which facilitate adherence to cellular surfaces and resistance to treatment. This ability may explain the difficulties encountered in treating recurrent infections.

Emerging resistance to antifungals is a major issue in the treatment of *C. albicans* infections. Sensitivity test results suggest that while most strains remain sensitive to first-line antifungals, there is a concerning trend of resistant strains to ketoconazole and other azoles. This underscores the need for ongoing monitoring of antifungal resistance and adjustment of treatment based on test results.

Tab. 1. Differences between *Candida* species

Candida Species	Morphology	Pathogenicity	Common Infections	Antifungal Resistance
Candida albicans	Yeast cells, pseudohyphae	Opportunistic pathogen; common in humans	Oral thrush, vaginal candidiasis, invasive candidiasis	Some strains show resistance to azoles

Candida glabrata	Yeast cells	Opportunistic pathogen; more resistant	Urinary tract infections, bloodstream infections	Often resistant to fluconazole
Candida tropicalis	Yeast cells	Opportunistic pathogen	Invasive candidiasis, bloodstream infections	Variable resistance; can show azole resistance
Candida parapsilosis	Yeast cells	Opportunistic pathogen	Bloodstream infections, infections in neonates	Some resistance to fluconazole
Candida krusei	Yeast cells	Opportunistic pathogen	Invasive candidiasis, bloodstream infections	Naturally resistant to fluconazole
Candida auris	Yeast cells	Highly pathogenic; emerging threat	Healthcare-associated infections, multidrug-resistant infections	Multi-drug resistant

The authors of the study "Isolation and Identification of *Candida* from the Oral Cavity" stated that the most commonly used primary isolation medium for *Candida* is SDA, which, while allowing the growth of *Candida*, suppresses the growth of many species of oral bacteria due to its low pH. The incorporation of antibiotics into SDA further increases its selectivity. Typically, SDA is incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24–48 hours. *Candida* develops as convex, creamy, smooth, and pasty colonies on SDA, and differentiation between species is rarely possible. It is estimated that more than one species of *Candida* appears in about 10% of oral samples, and in recent years, the ability to detect non-*albicans* species has become increasingly important.

In recent years, other differential media have been developed that allow for the identification of specific species of *Candida* based on the appearance and color of colonies after primary culture. The advantage of these media is that the presence of multiple species of *Candida* in a single infection can be determined, which may be important in choosing subsequent

treatment options. Examples of these media include Pagano-Levin agar or commercially available chromogenic agars, such as CHROMagar *Candida*, Albicans ID, Fluroplate, or Candichrom *albicans*.

Pagano-Levin agar distinguishes between *Candida* species based on the reduction of triphenyltetrazolium chloride. The medium produces pale-colored colonies for *C. albicans*, while colonies of other *Candida* species exhibit varying degrees of pink coloration. Pagano-Levin agar has similar sensitivity to SDA but is superior for detecting multiple species in a sample. CHROMagar *Candida* identifies *C. albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, and *C. krusei* based on the color and appearance of the colonies, while Albicans ID and Fluroplate have proven beneficial for the presumptive identification of *C. albicans*. The specificity of identification is reported to be 95% for CHROMagar *Candida* and 98.6% for Albicans ID and Fluroplate agars. The use of CHROMagar *Candida* as a primary isolation agar has been cited as an approach that allows for the discrimination of the recently described *C. dubliniensis* from *C. albicans*. On CHROMagar

Candida, *C. dubliniensis* typically develops as darker green colonies compared to those of *C. albicans*. However, the discrimination between these two species using CHROMagar appears to decrease after subculturing and storage of isolates. The failure of *C. dubliniensis* to grow on

agar media at the elevated incubation temperature of 45°C has recently been suggested as an alternative test to discriminate between these two species.

CONCLUSIONS

The colonies of *C. albicans* are usually creamy, whitish, or yellow, with well-defined edges.

Sensitivity tests showed variability in the susceptibility of the isolated strains to different antifungals. Most strains were sensitive to fluconazole, voriconazole, and caspofungin, but some strains exhibited resistance to ketoconazole, which may indicate an emerging trend of resistance. *C. albicans* possesses several virulence factors, including the ability to form biofilms, which facilitate adherence to cellular surfaces and resistance to treatment.

The results of the sensitivity tests suggest that, although most strains remain sensitive to first-line antifungals, there is a concerning trend of emerging strains resistant to ketoconazole and other azoles.

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THE HIGHLIGHTING OF FLUFFY-TYPE COLONIES FOR MOLDS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Molds spread in nature through drought-resistant spores, which can remain viable for years. When such a spore lands on the surface of a growth medium favorable for development, with a sufficient amount of free water, the first stage involves water absorption and activation of enzymatic systems, followed by the germination of the spore cell and the formation of vegetative tubes called hyphae or mycelium. The hyphae extend across the surface of the medium, diversify, and perform certain specialized functions. The extension hyphae can develop along the medium, in the airspace, or within the medium itself, facilitating nutrient absorption and providing structural support. At a certain stage of development of the vegetative hyphae, reproductive hyphae are formed, which generate spores differentiated by gender and species. The totality of vegetative and reproductive hyphae constitutes the mycelium.

The fluffy colonies of mold are visible masses of spores and hyphae that develop on various surfaces, typically in damp and warm environments. These colonies can have different textures, ranging from fine and velvety to coarse and dense, and are known for their fluffy appearance, which may be colored and can vary depending on the type of mold. The colors of mold colonies can be white, green, blue, black, or even reddish, depending on the species and environmental conditions.

Keywords: molds, hyphae, colonies

INTRODUCTION

Molds are found in all natural habitats due to their remarkable ability to adapt to various environmental conditions. They possess a complex enzymatic system, allowing them to utilize macromolecular organic compounds for nutrition.

The genus *Aspergillus* is one of the most well-known molds with medical significance. Among the species impacting health are *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus niger*. These form velvety colonies in shades of green, gray, white, or black and are often present in the air, on food, in indoor dust, and on building materials.

Aspergillus colonies can cause aspergillosis, an infection that can affect the respiratory system and manifest as persistent cough, difficulty breathing, and, in severe cases, lung damage. Aspergillosis is more common in individuals with compromised immune systems, such as patients with HIV, those who have undergone organ transplants, or patients with chronic lung conditions.

Maple mold (*Penicillium*) produces green, blue, or gray colonies, often found on food and in damp spaces. Some species of *Penicillium* are used in the production of antibiotics (for example, penicillin); however, other species can

cause allergic reactions and infections, especially in individuals with respiratory issues.

Penicillium marneffei, for instance, is known for its ability to cause severe infections, particularly in immunocompromised patients. This species produces blue-green colonies and can lead to fever, skin infections, and damage to internal organs.

Stachybotrys chartarum, also known as "toxic black mold," is a species that forms dense, black, mucous colonies growing on cellulose-containing materials (wood, cardboard, plaster) under conditions of high humidity. This species produces mycotoxins, which, when inhaled or touched, can cause severe symptoms, ranging from respiratory irritation, headaches, and cough to neurological problems and extreme fatigue.

Exposure to *Stachybotrys chartarum* can lead to toxic mold syndrome, a serious condition that includes symptoms such as confusion, memory loss, light sensitivity, and cognitive dysfunction. This mold is often present in buildings affected by flooding or those with chronic moisture problems.

Alternaria produces fluffy colonies that are dark brown or black and is commonly found outdoors as well as indoors, on walls and in bathrooms. This mold is a common allergen, and its spores can trigger allergic rhinitis, asthma, and other

respiratory conditions. Allergic individuals may experience symptoms such as sneezing, nasal congestion, itchy eyes, and cough. Additionally, this mold can cause skin infections and sinusitis in people with weakened immune systems.

The genus *Mucor* forms white or gray colonies with a fluffy texture and is found in damp environments, on spoiled food, and on decomposing organic materials. *Mucor* spores are opportunistic and can cause mucormycosis, a severe infection that affects the lungs, sinuses, and brain, especially in individuals with uncontrolled diabetes or weakened immune systems. Mucormycosis is an aggressive infection that can lead to severe tissue damage and requires immediate treatment. Symptoms include headaches, fever, facial swelling, and, in severe cases, may affect the central nervous system.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I conducted a prospective study based on microbiological diagnoses recorded in the bacteriological registry of the medical analysis laboratory, S.C. Diaser, Oradea. To conduct the study, I also accessed the archive, recorded in the laboratory's computer program in S.C. Diaser, Oradea, as well as the computerized database of the unit.

In the identification of medically significant molds, the methods and materials used are essential for obtaining an accurate diagnosis and evaluating the associated health risks. The identification methods for potentially pathogenic molds involve complex laboratory analyses, and the materials include specialized equipment for sample collection, isolation, and analysis. The process can be divided into several steps: sample collection, isolation and cultivation, microscopic identification, molecular testing, and toxicological analysis.

Sample Collection

Sample collection is the initial and one of the most important stages, as it determines the quality of subsequent analyses. Samples can be taken from various surfaces (walls, furniture, food) or from the air, particularly in areas where humidity is high and mold is visible or suspected.

- **Instruments:** Sterile cotton swabs, microscope slides and cover slips, sterile bags, Petri dishes, or air sampling pumps.
- **Techniques:** Swabs are used to collect mold from solid surfaces, while air pumps are used to capture spores from

the air by filtering it through special membranes.

1. Isolation and Laboratory Cultivation

Isolation and cultivation help obtain a pure colony necessary for further identification. Samples are transferred to selective culture media that support mold growth, such as Sabouraud dextrose agar, malt agar, or Czapek agar.

- **Culture Media:** Specific media, such as Sabouraud agar, which stimulates fungal growth due to its high glucose content.
- **Incubation:** Petri dishes are incubated at controlled temperatures between 25-30°C for several days to weeks, depending on the species.

3. Microscopic Identification

Once the colony has been isolated and grown, microscopic identification is essential for examining the morphology of the mold. Microscopy allows observation of the shape, size, structure of the hyphae, and appearance of the spores, which are unique characteristics for each species.

- **Equipment:** High-resolution optical microscope, electron microscope (for detailed analysis of spores).
- **Staining:** Lactophenol cotton blue or other stains that aid in visualizing structural details.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Cultural observations revealed notable differences regarding the color, texture, and growth rate of mold colonies. *Aspergillus fumigatus* has colonies with a velvety texture, dense structure, and green or grayish-blue color. The growth rate is rapid, with colonies becoming visible within 48-72 hours on culture media such as Sabouraud dextrose agar. *Penicillium marneffeii* forms bluish-green, powdery colonies with a characteristic texture that can become reddish upon maturation. This species is distinguished by producing a red pigment on culture media, an important marker for identification.

Stachybotrys chartarum presents black colonies with a slimy, almost rubbery texture. It grows slowly compared to other molds, reaching maturity in 7-10 days on Czapek agar. *Alternaria alternata* displays fluffy, woolly colonies of dark brown to black color. The growth rate is moderate, and the colonies have a distinct radial morphology. *Mucor spp.* presents white or gray colonies with

a fluffy texture. The growth rate is rapid, with colonies becoming visible within 24 hours, quickly expanding on culture media to cover the entire Petri dish within a few days. These cultural characteristics are useful for the rapid identification of mold species and contribute to preliminary laboratory diagnostics.

Biochemical tests were utilized to identify compounds produced by different mold species and the specific enzymatic activity of each. In particular, tests were used to detect extracellular enzymes, such as proteases and esterases, and to identify toxic metabolites. Biochemical tests for **Aspergillus fumigatus** indicated the production of fumagillin and gliotoxin, compounds with potential toxicity that affect the immune system. The enzymatic activity includes the presence of esterases and proteases, enzymes that contribute to the pathogenicity of the species. **Penicillium marneffe**i secreted proteolytic enzymes and produced a characteristic red pigment. HPLC tests showed the presence of compounds with natural antifungal activity, as well as the ability to colonize human tissues in immunocompromised individuals. **Stachybotrys chartarum** produces dangerous mycotoxins, including satratoxin and roridin,

both identifiable through toxicological testing. GC-MS analyses confirmed the presence of these toxins, known for their negative impact on the nervous and respiratory systems. **Alternaria alternata** produces alternariol toxin, a compound associated with respiratory irritations and dermatitis. The extracellular enzymes produced by *Alternaria* include oxidases, which contribute to the degradation of organic materials. **Mucor spp.** produces lipolytic and proteolytic enzymes but does not release significant toxic compounds. However, *Mucor* is an opportunistic pathogen, with the capacity to invade tissues in individuals with weakened immunity.

These biochemical characteristics contribute to understanding the pathogenic mechanisms of molds and allow for the assessment of infection and toxicity risks.

Morpho-staining analysis, which involves the use of microscopy and specific stains, allowed for the observation of the structural details of each mold species. **Aspergillus fumigatus**, following staining with lactophenol cotton blue, exhibited septate hyphae, straight conidiophores, and compact conidial structures characteristic of this genus.

Fig.1. Colony growth of *A. fumigatus* in PDA in the (a) obverse and (b) reverse sides on the 7th day of incubation. (<https://www.facesoffungi.org/aspergillus-fumigatus-facesoffungi-number-fof-10086/>)

Penicillium marneffei exhibits branched, septate hyphae, with conidia developing in chains, giving a characteristic "brushed" appearance. These structures are easily observed after staining with lactophenol cotton

blue.

Stachybotrys chartarum presents thick, septate hyphae, with conidia arranged on long, straight conidiophores. Staining with lactophenol highlighted a "black tube" appearance, characteristic of this species.

Alternaria alternata, from a microscopic perspective, includes septate hyphae and large, multicellular conidia arranged in short chains, giving a "stacked" appearance. The structures stain intensely with lactophenol cotton blue.

Mucor spp. features broad, coenocytic hyphae and large sporangia filled with spores. Staining revealed a "full sporangium" appearance, distinctive for this species.

Tab. 1. Cultural and Morphological Characteristics of Mold Species

Mold Species	Cultural Characteristics	Morphological Characteristics
Aspergillus fumigatus	Dense, velvety colonies in green or grayish-blue	Septate hyphae, straight conidiophores, compact conidia
Penicillium marneffeii	Powdery, blue-green colonies with red pigment	Branched, septate hyphae; conidia develop in chains
Stachybotrys chartarum	Black, slimy colonies that grow slowly	Thick septate hyphae, conidia on long, straight conidiophores
Alternaria alternata	Fluffy, brownish-black colonies	Septate hyphae, large multicellular conidia, arranged in short chains
Mucor spp.	- White or gray, fluffy colonies that grow rapidly	Broad, coenocytic hyphae; large sporangia filled with spores

In the study "Identification of *Aspergillus* Using Morphological Characteristics," *Aspergillus* isolates were identified at the species level using differential culture media. A total of 205 *Aspergillus* isolates studied included: 153 (75%) environmental *Aspergillus*

and 52 (25%) clinical isolates. Among the 11 identified species of *Aspergillus*, *A. flavus* (55%), *A. niger* (31.7%), and *A. fumigatus* (8.7%) were the most frequently isolated from the samples.

CONCLUSIONS

Aspergillus fumigatus has colonies with a velvety texture, dense, and green or gray-blue in color. *Penicillium marneffeii* forms bluish-green colonies. *Mucor* species produce lipolytic and proteolytic enzymes but do not release significant toxic compounds. The results obtained through cultural, biochemical, and morphotintorial analysis allow for the differentiation and identification of medically significant mold species.

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF VITAMIN C IN THE HUMAN BODY AND THE DEGREE OF ABSORPTION FOLLOWING THE ADMINISTRATION OF DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Studies that conceptualize how diet and dietary supplements affect the absorption of vitamin C in the body are important because they educate consumers about the significance of methods for assessing vitamin C intake and absorption before any empirical attempts to increase immunity are made. Due to the dose dependence of vitamin C's bioavailability, supplements should be used under strict control rather than topically or empirically. Any dietary advice assessing the effects and antioxidant function of vitamin C is based on an analysis of the vitamin's quantitative and qualitative dietary content, with the goal of enhancing consumers' nutritional status and, ultimately, their health.

In order to educate consumers about the circumstances in which vitamin C supplements can be taken, the purpose of this study was to demonstrate the actual effects of high-dose administration. The results show that absorption decreases to less than 50% when vitamin C intake exceeds 1000 mg. This occurs as a result of the body's tissues becoming saturated, which lowers absorption; any surplus is subsequently expelled through the urine.

Supplementation should only be used in specific situations because vitamin C is absorbed similarly whether it is synthetic or found in food. Nutritional studies are crucial in identifying food products that, when consumed in amounts that correspond to nutritional recommendations, can provide an optimal amount of vitamin C with beneficial effects on the body. By doing this, it is also possible to lessen the negative social media influence associated with the intake of this vitamin, thereby reducing unhealthy eating habits.

Keywords: (max. 5) vitamin C, nutritional supplements, vitamin C absorption, social-media influences, food supplements

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INTRODUCTION

Based on research, the recommended daily intake of vitamin C is 60 mg (Iqbal et al., 2022), with at-risk individuals requiring up to 250 mg.

While the bioavailability of vitamin C varies with dose (Frei et al., 2012), transport saturation occurs at doses of 200–400 mg/day (Kubler and Gehler, 1970). Although 500 mg doses per day result in about 70% absorption, more than 50% of the absorbed dose is unmetabolized and eliminated in the urine (Institute of Medicine US, 2000). When doses of vitamin C exceed 1000 mg, absorption drops to less than 50% (Levine, 1996, Levine, 2001). A dosage of 1250 mg has a 50% absorption rate, meaning that over 85% of it will be eliminated (Carr, 2016). Accordingly, moderate daily intakes of 200–400 mg of vitamin C are

necessary for its complete absorption of roughly 70–90% (Iqbal et al., 2022).

It is important for consumers to understand the functions of vitamin C in the body (Bjelakovic, 2007). Because of its antioxidant capacity, it plays a significant role in the production of collagen and elastin, the absorption of iron in the digestive tract, the reduction of allergic reactions, and the inhibition of histamine release (Horska, 2011). A strong reducing agent, vitamin C takes part in a number of significant hydroxylation reactions. The entry of vitamin C into cells is facilitated by Na-coupled transporters+ (Malo and Wilson, 2000). Vitamin C is regenerated from DHA by glial cells in the brain (Corpe, 2013). It is also required for collagen biosynthesis, l-carnitine production, collagen development, and the production of neurotransmitters, catecholamines and bile acids. Oxalate is a natural degradation product of vitamin C (Engelking, 2015).

Vitamin C uses Fe⁺⁺ and Cu⁺⁺ as cofactors, and enhances intestinal absorption of Fe⁺⁺ (Engelking, 2015). Therefore, in addition to its antioxidant effect, vitamin C assimilation also influences the capacity of the body to absorb non-heme iron, which is found in plant foods such as leafy greens. An intake of less than 25 mg of vitamin C per day results in an of absorption of only 3% of non-heme iron. A daily intake of 50 mg of vitamin C results in 5% absorption, whereas a daily intake of more than 70 mg of vitamin C results in 8% absorption of non-heme iron. Drinking a small glass of 100% fruit juice or including a vitamin C-rich food with meals can help to stimulate iron absorption (Paidi, 2014; Sogaard, 2014)

Normal skin typically contains high concentrations of vitamin C, which promotes collagen production and protects against UV damage. If vitamin intake is adequate through diet, vitamin C acts on the skin and, in fact, on all tissues of the human body. According to research, topical vitamin C may not offer many advantages because little of the vitamin can be absorbed by surface of the skin through creams and serums, and even if consumed in sufficient quantities through food or supplements, it won't have any further effects (Pullar et al., 2017).

This study evaluated the degree of vitamin C absorption following dietary supplementation, based on the biosynthesis of the vitamin in the body, The study aimed to highlight the impact and role of antioxidant score of diet on the body. These studies can significantly contribute to educate consumers through specific nutritional interventions to adopt a healthy lifestyle, correlated with physiological status.

The objectives of this study are related to the fact that any nutritional recommendations assessing the antioxidant role and impact of vitamin C will be based on a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the nutrient's content in foods, with the view of improving consumers' nutritional status and overall health.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

It is vital to develop an investigative strategy and methodology that is specific to the various theoretical orientations and carriers of implicit or explicit ideology within dietary supplements and nutrients in order to evaluate and investigate their diversity as adjuvant health supporting factors (Cook, 2007; Heart Protection Study Collaborative, 2002; Sesso, 2008).

The results of this study are based on the observation of five consumers (n=5), who appeared to be in good health, ate a regular diet, and willingly agreed to raise their vitamin C intake to the recommended level. Intakes were supplemented with doses of 500 mg/day, 1000 mg/day, and 1500 mg/day, respectively, based on information obtained from social media about the benefits of vitamin C supplementation, in the absence of a specific cause.

The following research methods were applied in this scientific study:

a) The clinical approach, based on nutritional anamnesis, which was applied in order to make judicious clinical assessments of the consumers' nutritional and physiological status, as well as any pathological disorders that could be identified based on particular paraclinical analysis. This approach entailed surveillance, correlation of cases of vitamin C overdosage or underdosage, and analysis of events under study.

b) The nutritional approach, which was based on: the assessment of nutritional intake; a nutritional anamnesis, which gathered data on the type and quantity of food consumed; and nutritional and energy calculations based on the makeup of the food consumed over the course of a day. Information about the existence or lack of risk factors for nutritional diseases was obtained through nutrient intake assessment.

c) The paraclinical approach, carried out in a private medical laboratory, was based on macroscopic evaluation, biochemical evaluation of the primary metabolites, and microscopic evaluation in order to assess vitamin C excretion by urine examination. Although not all urine biochemistry tests include ascorbic acid, which is the eleventh parameter, its assessment is crucial because it may alter certain biochemical tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Due to its use as a flavor enhancer and preservative in a variety of food and pharmaceutical products (vitamin complexes), ascorbic acid is frequently consumed in high amounts. As a result, it can alter urine biochemistry without any pathologic justification. To avoid producing erroneous results, it is crucial to detect it through tests that also include this parameter (Lykkesfeldt, 2020).

An important and noteworthy feature of this study was the analysis of the mixed diet situation according to a seven-day diet plan. All study participants accepted the recommended

diet plan, which included a range of food types and considered their vitamin C content and preparation methods, which have a significant impact on vitamin C intake (Table 1).

Table 1
Nutrient estimates of vitamin C intake according to the dietary plan

Diet/Nutritional plan	EV (kcal/day)	Vitamin C _i (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{abs} mg/day
DAY I	2742,49	107.2	87.76
DAY II	1687,28	78.12	70.31
DAY III	1687,28	88.12	79.31
DAY IV	2335,49	104.19	88.56
DAY V	3236,73	196.26	137.38
DAY VI	1678,18	98.45	88.61
DAY VII	1044,57	105.09	89.33

*VE - energy value; Vitamin C_{i,alim} - Vitamin C ingested; Vitamin C_{abs} - Vitamin C absorbed

Dietary energy value and vitamin C intake were linked; higher dietary energy values resulted in higher vitamin C intake, and higher intake raised absorption.

The nutritional analysis revealed that the highest values were recorded on the fifth day of analysis. The average absorption of vitamin C was 137.38 mg/day, which translates to an average percentage absorption of 70% of the ingestion. The mean percentage of vitamin C

absorbed on the third and twelfth days of analysis averaged 90% of the intake on both days. These average proportions are due to the fact that the bioavailability of vitamin C depends on the ingested dose. However, it is crucial to note that moderate vitamin C intake results in 70–90% absorption.

Figure 1. Distribution of mean vitamin C intake correlated with mean dietary vitamin C intake per day

The lowest average vitamin C intake was determined on day 2, being 78.12 mg/day, leading to an average absorption of 70.31 mg/day, which can provide on average 93.75% of the RQ/day.

Table 2
Evolution of vitamin C absorption, excretion and metabolic utilization after supplementation with doses of 500, 1000 and 1500 mg/day

Diet/Nutrition Plan	Vitamin C _{i,alim} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{j,alim} + more (mg/day)			Vitamin C _{excr} mg/day			Vitamin C _{UT} mg/day		
		Vitamin C _{abs_S_500} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{abs_S_1000} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{abs_S_1500} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{ex_S_500} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{ex_S_1000} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{ex_S_1500} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{UTM_S_500} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{UTM_S_1000} (mg/day)	Vitamin C _{UTM_S_1500} (mg/day)
DAY I	107.2	364.32	553.60	482.16	182.16	332.16	385.72	182.16	221.44	96.43
DAY II	78.12	404.68	539.06	552.34	202.34	323.43	441.87	202.34	215.63	110.46
DAY III	88.12	382.27	544.06	555.84	191.13	326.43	444.67	191.13	217.63	111.16
DAY IV	104.19	362.51	552.09	481.23	181.25	331.25	384.98	181.25	220.84	96.24
DAY V	196.26	348.13	598.13	424.06	174.06	358.87	339.24	174.06	239.26	84.81
DAY VI	98.45	359.07	549.22	479.53	179.53	329.53	398.02	179.53	219.69	81.50
DAY VII	105.09	363.05	552.54	481.52	181.52	331.52	385.21	181.52	221.02	96.30

*Vitamin C_{i,alim} - Dietary ingested Vitamin C; Vitamin C_{abs} - Absorbed Vitamin C, Vitamin C_{ex} - Excreted Vitamin C, Vitamin C_{UTM} - Vitamin C metabolically utilized

Following dietary intake plus supplementation, the C_{abs_S_1000} mg/day variant was associated with the highest absorption of vitamin C (598.13 mg/day) (Table 2), while the C_{abs_S_500} mg/day variant showed the lowest absorption (348.13 mg/day). The amount of vitamin C consumed in all three variants remained the same, based on the dietary plan that all study participants followed, but supplementing with 1500 mg/day of the vitamin produced a downward trend when compared to supplementing with 1000 mg/day.

Analyzing the evolutionary results of excretion (Table 2), on the basis of paraclinical data of vitamin C dosage in urine, in the case of variant C_{abs_S_500} mg/day it was observed that from the amount absorbed after ingestion, the excretion rate was of 50%, resulting in a metabolic utilization of at most 202.34 mg/day on the second day of analysis.

In the variant C_{abs_S_1000} mg/day it was observed that the excretion was about 60%, resulting in a metabolic utilization of at most 239.26 mg/day. And in the C_{abs_S_1500} mg/day variant, the excretion was of about 80%,

resulting in a metabolic utilization of at most 111.16 mg/day. These excretion results are inversely proportional to vitamin C ingestion and absorption due to the fact that metabolic saturation of tissues with vitamin C occurred.

The highest metabolic utilization of vitamin C (Table 2) was found on the first day of analysis in variant C_{UTM_S_1000} (mg/day), followed by variant C_{UTM_S_500} (mg/day) on the second day, with 202,34 mg/day, and variant C_{UTM_S_1500} (mg/day) on the third day of analysis, with 111,16 mg/day. This was based on the analysis of metabolic utilization in all three experimental variants, C_{UTM_S_500} (mg/day), C_{UTM_S_1000} (mg/day), and C_{UTM_S_1500} (mg/day).

The C_{UTM_S_500} mg/day variant was associated with the lowest metabolic utilization of vitamin C, at 174.06 mg/day on day 5, while the highest dietary intake was 196.26 mg/day (Table 2). In the C_{UTM_S_1000} mg/day variant, the lowest amount of vitamin C metabolically utilized was determined on day 2, i.e. 215.63 mg/day, where the lowest dietary intake was also determined.

On day six of analysis, the variant C_{UTM_S_1500} mg/day had the lowest metabolically utilized vitamin C (Table 2), at 81.50 mg/day.

The detection of a high level of ascorbic acid in the urine requires a re-evaluation of some biochemical parameters: glucose, bilirubin, hemoglobin and nitrite. For glucose and bilirubin, a high amount of ascorbic acid induces a false result by lowering the limit of detection so that alert values may appear as pathological values without particular significance, but appear as mismatches between biochemical parameters (Henriquez-Sanchez, 2009).

Any pathology that calls for the prescription of vitamin C supplements necessitates an analysis and an intervention in the metabolism of the body; therefore, the prescription must be in line with all available scientific data regarding the disease and must take into consideration the body's entire pathophysiologic context, including the drug treatment and its metabolic implications. Since nutrition is known to play a significant role in promoting and maintaining good health throughout life, the advantages of specialized nutritional interventions have already been demonstrated. This should serve as a warning for both healthy and mono- or poly-infected organisms.

The findings of the nutritional analysis of vitamin C intake and absorption on health improvement led to the conclusion that these physiologically active nutrients might help reduce the high prevalence of certain diseases, as well as the expenses associated with diet management.

CONCLUSIONS

A daily intake of roughly 500 mg of vitamin C from food plus supplements will result in an approximate 70% absorption rate, of which, according to metabolic data correlated with paraclinical data, more than 50% will be excreted.

When vitamin C intake exceeds 1500 mg/day, absorption is approximately 25–35%, with excretion exceeding 85%. Therefore, the higher the vitamin C intake above 1500 mg/day, the lower the absorption.

Consuming more than 1000 mg of vitamin C per day increases the risk of developing renal diseases, especially in those who already have hyperoxaluria.

70–80% of vitamin C is absorbed at moderate doses, and bioavailability varies with dosage.

The reduction of vitamin C deficiency is positively correlated with lifestyle factors, including diet.

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REVIEW REGARDING FOOD PREFERENCES ACROSS DIFFERENT GENERATIONS

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REVIEW

Abstract

This study presents a comparison regarding the food preferences and the consumption behaviour between different generations. The consumption behaviour studies mainly the mental and emotional response and the consumers behaviour regarding the typology of products purchase. It is influenced by a series of factors such as: environmental factors, economic factors, social factors, culture, traditions, consumers preferences and prices.

The differences between generations regarding food consumption and the attitude towards organic products are significant and thus they influence the marketing strategies leading to the market being segmented into specific generational niches that satisfy the consumers preferences.

Keywords: generations, food preferences, consumption behaviour

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INTRODUCTION

The consumer behaviour mainly studies the mental, emotional and the consumers behaviour regarding the type of product purchase. (Cătoiș & Morariu, 2001).

The factors that influence the consumers behaviour are personal, cultural, social and psychological. The personal factors include the genre, the income and the consumers age, the cultural ones refer to tradition and religion, and the social factors refer to friends and family. These factors are very important in order to define and characterize the consumers behaviours. (Hiranandani, 2023).

The consumers behaviour - or the way in which people buy and use goods and services - is a vast field of psychological research, especially for the big companies that wish to sell products to as many clients as possible. Considering how much the lives of consumers is impacted by the „why” and „how much” products they buy, researching the consumers behaviour is tightly bound by a few key psychological issues. These include communication (How are different people responding to commercials and marketing?), identity (Do our acquisitions unravel our personality?), social status, decision making and mental and physical health. (Consumer Behavior | Psychology Today, 2024). Establishing the consumers behaviour has a

major importance in market studies because it determines the best way of promoting products and services. The decision to buy something is mainly based on desire and not on need, and they are not always rational; instead they are influenced by personality, emotion and trends (Murray, 2016).

The strategies utilised in campaigns for a product might not be valid for another product, the wishes of consumers changing continuously. Thus, in order to adapt, the marketing specialists are focusing upon focus groups, they apply psychological studies and market studies in order to obtain a better understanding of what are the decision factors that influence the consumer in buying and becoming loyal to the brands (Consumer Behavior | Psychology Today, 2024).

Implementing efficient marketing strategies leads to the understanding of consumers behaviour, enhancing thus the loyalty to brand by influencing the consumers in the process of decision making (Hiranandani, 2023).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

There are seven generation that have been studied over time, and they are as it follows:

1. *The great generation* (born between 1901-1927). This generation is known by the fact that they grew during the Great Depression and many of the respondents belonging to this generation are war veterans from the Second

World War. The Great Depression caused a series of problems that lead to the majority of the population being extremely poor (Elder, 2018; Kennedy, 2001).

2. *The silent generation* (born between 1928-1945) known as „the lucky few”, includes the veterans that participated in the wars that took place in Korea and Vietnam. Their income was lower compared to the one the previous generation earned. Because of the abject poverty, the objects that other generation consider as necessities or accessible distraction, for them it represented a luxury.

These generations grew in families where the father was the only source of income. Most of the women had no education past primary school, and most of them were taking care of the household (Howe & Strauss, 2009).

Considering the poverty that characterised these generations, most of them were modest people, that bought only what was necessary and small joys. They prefer a practical attitude regarding commercial and they are responding better to commercials that refer to traditional values. The ones that are closer to the way they grew, will obtain a better answer from these generations.

Also, both the Great Generation as well as the Silent Generation will rather choose known, classic brands, than products that belong to newer companies. Thanks to the many decades of radio and television, this behaviour was attributed to the repetitive nature of older commercials that formed the preferences of these respondents (Penington-Gray, 2001).

These generations tend to have less digital experience and they did not adopt the new technologies with ease. The younger ones might have computers and tablets, but there are very few smartphones used by the ones belonging to these generations. It remains the responsibility of younger generations to teach the older ones how to use modern technology (Prensky, 2001; Tapscott, 2009).

3. *Baby boomers* (born between 1946-1964). Many of the members of this period grew up with their mothers leading the household. With this generation, came the change, women gaining access to the world of educated professionals. This was a turning moment in woman's education, leading to women becoming more than 50% from the people with a superior education from United States.

Since now there were two incomes per household, this generation became the

wealthiest. They prefer to buy in large bulks, renowned products that represent quality. Being the generation that grew with a TV in the house, their preferences were determined by the commercials that were aired. This generation is loyal to known brands but is also open to suggestions and recommendations from their children that belong to X, Y and even Z generation.

This generation has an entrepreneurial spirit that is continuously developing. They paid attention to this new trend that avoids typical workplaces with a 9-17 schedule and developed companies that incorporate these values. They believe in niche products that satisfy and responds to an actual need and so they invest in these products and services. They ask for recommendations from trained employees and only then decide if they will buy a product about which they did not have enough information previously.

When targeting the Baby boomers, the message must be conservative and traditional to lure them. A commercial that contains licentious language or inappropriate images will only estrange them. The commercials are to be distributed on TV channels, in newspapers and on the local market (Madichie, 2009; Williams & Page, 2011).

4. *Generation X* (born between 1965-1980), known as the generation with the key around their neck or the MTV generation, these are the kids whose parents have jobs, the ones that caught the highest divorce rate between their parents. This generation was seen as cynical and broken, many times questioning authority, which led to a logic regarding acquisitions, the respondents being immune to emotional messages.

The entrepreneurial spirit of this generations is well developed, working many extra hours beside the 9-17 work schedule to rise their own empire. This generation is much humbler compared with the other generations that surrounds them, preferring to let their work to speak for them instead of bragging about their success.

They easily adopted the utilisation of internet for work, research, online shopping, etc. They are connected with the environment through intense smartphone utilisation. They are well informed staying in tune with news that are read from apps. Also, they are avid volunteers, being important to spend time with the community, for they development and good mood.

This generation prefers products that are accessible and practical. They have steady jobs, leading to the possibility of buying a house, appliances, and furniture. They read reviews with attention before buying a new product and they rely on recommendation for major acquisitions. Also, they prefer streaming platforms instead of cable TV.

When targeting Generation X, the message must be rather clear and concise than emotional, to lure them. It is recommended to distribute the commercials on platforms like Hulu, Netflix, HBO Max, news sites and on the local market (Williams & Page, 2011). They stay loyal to their favourite products and refuse to test different brands. Also, they are attracted by good offers like coupons, promotional codes, loyalty programmes and many others. (Hiranandani, 2023).

5. *Generation Y* (born between 1980-1995), also known as Millennials or Generation Me, is the generation with the highest higher education rate, at least 61% of them attending college. The respondents of this generation work beside their fulltime job, part-time jobs. Due to their education, there is a serious competition when it comes to jobs.

Some millennials saw business opportunities on markets that have never been accessed before and so small businesses and start-ups appeared. Others chose a digital Nomad lifestyle, working remote while travelling the world.

This generation uses smartphones and tablets to make fast acquisitions, to manage their bank accounts and to stay informed (Bolton et al., 2013).

They prefer accessible products, environmentally friendly, the ones not being tested on animals being the most treasured ones. Emotional connections offer them a positive perception that determines them to buy from a certain company. Reviews on products and brands are searched before deciding to buy a product. Also, they are willing to share their own opinions about products and brand, online and offline.

These respondents do not cherish traditions as much as the value of the brand and its actions. They are willing to pay more for popular and unique products (Hiranandani, 2023).

Growing in a revolutionary period for the digital era, they are used to consume daily, media content, online games, videos, and movies on streaming platforms. When targeting

Millennials, there are many ways to get to them. Media content can be consumed during the day through social media, apps, YouTube and streaming, being difficult to choose a way to approach them (Fromm & Garton, 2013).

6. *Generation Z* (born between 1996-2012), also known as Founders Generation, Post-Millennials or iGeneration, favour the digital scene when talking about acquisitions. The respondents of this generation wish to always be amazed by something found on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat or Pinterest, easily accepting new, innovative products. These platforms are used like Google, always searching the next great event, through commercial being possible to actually buy products (Schiopu et al., 2023).

YouTube is also appreciated by this generation because they would rather see how a product works, not only pictures with it. This way they make informed acquisitions, while also learning how to use the product correctly (Williams & Page, 2011). They are very well informed because they do a lot of research and weigh their options before buying products or services. They always look for the best offer and are more prone to buy through social media, compared to other generations. While generation X and Y are centred on the price, this generation is aware of the price, thus is necessary for a company to change their values, quality, and ethic in practice, to sell products to a respondent of this generation. Also implementing marketing strategies through identification of known and appreciated influencers (Hiranandani, 2023).

Generation Z prefers affordable, eco-friendly, animal-free and niche products. They want to express who they are through what they buy, so they can display their status or develop common interests with strangers.

They are heavily influenced by digital celebrities such as beauty vloggers, influencers, or a show about current events, they will absorb their favourite brands from their favourite celebrities. This fact provides the opportunity to make content with paid partnerships based on the celebrity of the influencer (Seemiller & Grace, 2018)

7. *Generation Alpha* (born between 2013-2025), is growing up in an environment full of connections and developing in an era of continuous digitization, being the first generation of the 21st century. It is assumed that it will be the largest and most diverse generation, whose population will exceed 2

billion in 2025. They will shape the development of technology and the direction of research as well as the success of companies, being a crucial focal point for marketers (Ziatdinov & Cilliers, 2022).

Understanding this generation is important because even if the respondents are not old enough to make purchases themselves, they indirectly impact through parental decisions that take into account their preferences, needs and interests, as well as educational resources, entertainment options, food preferences and chosen lifestyles (McCrinkle & Fell, 2020).

More than 54% of respondents of this generation own a tablet, being deeply immersed in the digital world. They are socially conscious and vocal, with 96% of them believing that people should be treated fairly, regardless of what they look like or what their demographics are. Also, more than half (63%) say they want to work where they can have an impact on saving the planet. The vast majority of parents (80%) reported that their Alpha children influenced their actions and purchasing decisions towards a more sustainable future. These children are aware of the importance of mental health, being raised by health-conscious parents. They prefer visual content on platforms like Instagram, YouTube and TikTok (Chan, 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Over the generations, food preferences have varied, being strongly influenced by environmental factors, economic factors, culture, traditions, and consumer preferences. The generational differences are obvious, and the study of their consumption behaviour provides relevant information so that the offer corresponds to the demand of each generation.

The Baby Boomers generation grew up eating most of their meals in restaurants, schools, and corporate cafes as well as cafeterias. More than half of consumers aged 53-72 use catering services on a weekly basis. Compared to the previous generation, they have been exposed to more flavours, ingredients, and styles of cooking. They prefer healthy eating and convenience when it comes to grocery shopping. Information about the food consumed, transparency about the sources of nutrients, how the animals are slaughtered, and other aspects described on the packaging are appreciated. Their definition of healthy includes terms such as: local, fresh, clean, salad consumption increasing by 20% compared to

previous years (Drewnowski & Almiron-Roig, 2010).

Generation X is a group between the ages of 42-52. They are avid fast-food consumers, with 85% of the total demographic visiting a fast-food restaurant monthly. Those born later in this generation choose locations that offer full services, opting for those that also have menus for children or families. The products favoured by this generation are burgers, chicken, tacos or burritos, hot coffee, bottled water, smoothies, and sports drinks. They also have a more adventurous taste palette compared to the previous generation, with over 62% of respondents willing to test new flavours from time to time. Among the flavours tested are those belonging to Japanese cuisine (sushi) or Caribbean food. Only 27% of respondents of the generation prefer to limit themselves to their favourite tastes, rarely being willing to try new tastes, preferring restaurants with limited service that offer the traditional menu (Galanakis, 2024).

Millennials are a generation on the go, with 39% of respondents saying they eat takeout. Despite all the rush, however, they don't rely heavily on processed foods to save time. Half of them say they prefer fresh food and 42% say they prefer to cook their food from scratch with natural ingredients. When it comes to food choices, they strike an exploratory note with 64% saying they enjoy trying new flavours, while 44% would like more ethnic options in restaurants. Older respondents prefer options that please everyone and can be shared like Italian and Mexican cuisines, most likely influenced by family. This generation appreciates technology, with 58% of respondents using their phone to order food, and a study in Austin, Texas found that millennials prefer adding self-checkout boxes to restaurants, improving service and customer satisfaction (Suárez-Gómez & Costa, 2021).

Generation Z is the generation with the most respondents who take takeaway food, exceeding 40%, thus one of the goals of catering companies was to find packaging solutions, so that the food is as easy as possible to consume. They turned steaks into sandwiches, put meat into burger buns, put soups in a glass, etc. Today's students no longer have the necessary time to sit at the table, being often on the run with one hand occupied by a smart device, so solutions to offer them food in the most practical way are very well received (Suryaningrum et al., 2023). Also, 45% of

students consider it important to use fresh products, being interested in the traceability part (from the production of the ingredients to the serving of the food)(Cobe, 2018). They value the use of local products in favour of imported ones, easily accepting seasonal menus based on local production. They have physical and mental health concerns and are more likely to choose vegetarian/vegan options. They are a generation aware of the importance of sustainability, willing to evolve and change their eating behaviour to reduce the carbon footprint and the level of pollution, thus practices such as the introduction of insects into the diet as a source of protein, will find a greater openness to this generation compared with the previous ones.

Purchasing and consuming organic food products is one of the ways to make the transition to sustainable food consumption. A study carried out in Greece, a country strongly affected by the economic crisis for 11 consecutive years, explores the behaviour in

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights differences in food preferences and consumption attitudes between generations. Growing up in different living environments and periods, their lifestyle and behaviour was shaped differently, thus leading to varied consumption attitudes and food preferences.

The silent generation, due to the poverty that characterized the period of this generation, is modest and buys strictly what is necessary, avoiding waste. They have strong traditional values and respond better to practical advertisements, which are broadcast on radio-tv stations or through newspapers.

The Baby-boomers generation caught the emancipation of women, which brought 2 incomes to the family, thus raising the standard of living. They prefer healthy eating and convenience, using weekly catering services. They are impressed by conservative and traditional messages distributed on TV channels, in newspapers and in the local market.

Generation X caught the highest divorce rate among parents. They work overtime to achieve their goals. They prefer to eat fast food or eat in family-friendly restaurants, being open to trying a wide range of tastes. They use the phone extensively, prefer ads with clear and concise messages, which are recommended to

terms of purchases, attitudes, and the effect of the economic crisis on the purchase of organic products, exercised by 5 generations: the Silent Generation, the Baby Boomers, Generation X, Generation Y and Generation Z. One of the ways to consume sustainable food is to purchase and consume organic food products. For this work, 1562 respondents were analysed over 9 months (Theodoridou et al., 2019). The results showed that all generational cohorts demonstrated a favourable attitude towards organic food and identified that one of the factors that decreased the purchase of organic products is the economic crisis. Furthermore, the results show that in all cases, there are differences between generations. The adaptation of government policies can be done through marketing communications that will highlight the advantage of consuming organic products, the benefits of their consumption and thus strengthen the favourable attitude of the consumer towards these products, in conditions of economic crisis (Kamenidou et al., 2020).

be distributed on streaming platforms such as Netflix, HBO max or Hulu.

Generation Y is the generation with the highest rate of higher education. They are open to testing new flavours and appreciate technology, appreciating self-checkouts in cafeterias or using phones to order food. They use technology to make purchases, respond to emotional connections, and look for reviews on social media, Facebook, or Twitter before purchasing a product.

Generation Z is the generation most aware of the impact on the environment, being more attentive in their purchases to the attitude and values of the company than to the price. They are always on the run, so they prefer takeaway food (steak in a sandwich, soup in a glass, etc.), they are interested in the traceability part of food products, and they are open to accepting new food sources such as crickets as a source of protein. They are strongly influenced by social media, influencers and vloggers, their goal being to make a change through an environmentally friendly attitude.

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PHYSIO-CHEMICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISATION OF GREEN TEA (*CAMELLIA SINENSIS*) OBTAINED THROUGH TWO DIFFERENT EXTRACTION METHODS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE (REVIEW ARTICLE)

Abstract

*The objective of the study was to observe the physio-chemical differences between two different extractions of green tea (*Camellia sinensis*).*

To conduct the study, two green tea extractions were obtained: through classical infusion at 85 °C for two minutes and through cold extraction at 45 °C, under void for 45 minutes. Based on the green tea extractions, total antioxidant capacity, polyphenols, flavonoid, and vitamin C concentrations were determined, as well as pH, conductivity, and dry soluble matter values, after which the results were compared to observe the differences.

The obtained results showed that even though the results were similar between the two infusions, a better extraction of the bioactive compounds was determined from the classical infusion.

Keywords: green tea, physio-chemical analysis, cold extraction, infusion

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INTRODUCTION

Green tea is obtained through minimal processing of the *Camellia sinensis* plant. The main purpose of this process is to keep the fresh flavour and to preserve the highest number of bioactive compounds found in the fresh leaves. After harvesting the leaves, the next step is to neutralise the enzymes to avoid tea degradation. The leaves are rolled, and the cells walls are broken, leading to the expression of the juice from the leaves, thus reducing the humidity as much as possible during the drying phase [1].

According to specialty literature, it is demonstrated that the temperature and the infusion time influence the bioactive composition of the tea, as well as the antioxidant capacity [2]. Traditionally, green tea is infused 2-3 minutes at 80-90°C. Researchers observed that the longer the infusion time is, the more the antioxidant capacity grows, reaching a maximum at 5 minutes [3]. Also, the temperature of the infusion, influences the antioxidant capacity and increases the solubility of the catechins [4]. Another research discovered that infusing tea at room temperature, up to two hours, presented an antioxidant activity with 65% higher than infusions at 70°C for 360 seconds [5]. A study from 2011, states that green tea brewed with hot water has a

more astringent taste compared with the green tea brewed with cold water. This happens because hot water extracts epigallocatechin gallate and caffeine, compounds that elicit bitterness and a strong astringent taste. These compounds are hard to extract in cold water, enhancing only the extraction of epigallocatechin and the theanine that are easily extracted in cold water and flavour the green tea infused this way [6].

The main **objective** of this study was to observe the differences in green tea extractions obtained through two methods: classical extraction at 85°C for 2 minutes and through cold extraction at 45°C for 45 minutes under void, and to analyse if there are significant differences between the two extractions through physio-chemical and biochemical determinations.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

1. Material

To elaborate this study, green tea packaged in tea bags was bought in April 2024.

The devices used were ceramic mugs, a water heater, a thermometer, a Heidolph Laborota 4010 digital rotavapor, analytical balance, mini-Shimadzu spectrophotometer, WTW pH-meter and KRUSS digital refractometer.

2. Characterisation of the green tea

Green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) is one of the most consumed beverages around the world. It contains more antioxidants than any other form of tea. The composition in bioactive compounds varies and is directly dependant on the fermentation processes employed in production [7].

The chemical composition of green tea is complex. Some of the elements present in it are vitamins B, C, E, caffeine and theophylline, pigments: chlorophyll and carotenoids, minerals such as Ca, Mg, Mn, Fe, Zn, Mo, Se, Na, P, K, etc., and volatile compounds: esters, alcohols, aldehydes and lactones [8].

Green tea also has many health benefits as seen below:

- enhanced antioxidant activity and protection against oxidative damages through responsible consumption while following a healthy diet [9];
- hypotensive effect and lowered risk of cardiovascular diseases when minimum 10 cups of tea are consumed daily [10];
- anti-mutagenic potential against cancer demonstrated through studies upon cell cultures [11];
- enhanced oral health through lowering the number of cavities after frequent consumption of green tea [12];
- controlled body weight through thermogenesis from the synergic interaction between caffeine, polyphenols and prolonged stimulation of the sympathetic nervous system [13];
- UV protection through oral consumption or topical application of polyphenols from green tea [14];
- increased glucose tolerance [15].

3. Method

The experiment was carried out in 7 steps with 5 repetitions each and the average of the obtained results was written in the paper.

Step 1 was the extraction of the infusion with:

- the classical method at 85°C for 2 minutes,
- the cold extraction under void at 45°C for 45 minutes in the Heidolph Laborota 4010 digital rotavapor.

Step 2 was the determination of the total antioxidant capacity with the FRAP method as it was elaborated by Benzie and Strain in 1996. After mixing the green tea extracts with the FRAP reactive and the other components, the obtained solution was stirred and heated at 37°C. After cooling the samples, the absorbance was read at 593nm. The results were expressed as a correspondent of the antioxidant activity in Trolox equivalents [16].

Step 3 Total phenolic compounds were determined through the Folin-Ciocalteu method, and the samples were read at 760nm. The results were expressed in Gallic acid equivalents/100ml analysed material [17].

Step 4 Ascorbic acid content was determined through the volumetric method – iodometry. The determination is based on the reducing property of the ascorbic acid by transformation through oxidation in dehydroascorbic acid [16].

Step 5 Total flavonoid compounds were determined using the spectrophotometric method with AlCl₃ and the absorbance was measured at 510nm. The used standard was catechin, represented by quercetin [18].

Step 6 Determination of pH and conductivity was done with the use of the WTW pH-meter.

Step 7 Determination of dry soluble matter was done using the digital refractometer KRUSS at 20,6°C, and the correction at 20°C was made using the online programme winemaker.plus [19]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following the research, below are presented the obtained results and the correlations between the parameters.

Table 1 - The results of physio-chemical and biochemical determinations

Determinations	Sample 1 – classic extraction	Sample 2 – cold extraction
Total antioxidant capacity mM TE	10,117	9,287
Total phenol compounds mg GAE/100ml	92,428	89,034
Ascorbic acid content mg/100ml	50,62	46,17
Total flavonoid compounds AlCl ₃ mg/100ml	103,645	98,437
pH	6,25	6,3
Conductivity	76,3	76,2
Dry soluble matter - ° Brix	0,45	0,45

Following the physio-chemical and biochemical determinations as seen in Table 1, it can be seen that the classical extraction method, has a higher number of

bioactive compounds, a slightly higher conductivity but a lower pH compared to the cold extraction method.

Figure 1 - Comparison between the biochemical values of the two extracts

The results that were obtained from the biochemical determination show that there are very small differences between the extraction methods, with the classical method being slightly richer in bioactive compounds.

According to newer studies, epigallocatechin has a beneficial effect on

the immune system, enhancing it and theanine reduces the psychosocial stress, but these compounds are inhibited by epigallocatechin gallate and caffeine, thus in order to obtain the aforementioned effects, cold brewing should be applied to green tea[6].

Figure 2 - Comparison between the physio-chemical values of the two extracts

Both tea infusions had very similar results when the pH, the conductivity and the dry soluble matter was determined.

Other studies showed as well that there are very small differences between

the physio-chemical results, when talking about the method of infusion cold or classical, the differences appearing when the samples change concentrations of plant used for extraction[20].

CONCLUSIONS

1. Cold extraction of tea infusion showed similar results to the classical extraction.

2. The results found in this paper were consistent with previous reports regarding the biochemical and physio-chemical composition of teas brewed in cold and hot water.

3. Considering that epigallocatechin gallate and caffeine extracted in hot water inhibit the presence of epigallocatechin and theanine that are soluble in cold water, cold extraction is recommended when the latter compounds are desired.

4. Classical hot infusion is bitter, and astringent compared to the cold infusion that has a softer flavour thus making the cold extraction to be an option that is better tolerated by consumers and is also a rich source of bio-compounds.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was co-funded from the project CNFIS FDI-2024-F-0334 – “Interdisciplinary research and innovation using sustainable technologie – CIIUTS” funded by UEFISCDI.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF HONEY FROM LYCHEE (*LITCHI CHINENSIS*) AND INDIAN MUSTARD (*BRASSICA JUNCEA*) FLOWERS FROM WEST BENGAL STATE IN INDIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Honey is a natural product of animal origin very important in human diet from many points of view, defined as "the sweet substance produced by honeybees from the nectar of blossoms or from secretions on living plants, which the bees collect, transform and store in honeycombs". It plays an important part in our nutrition, and it is well-known for its positive effects on health.

Litchi Chinensis (or Lychee) is an evergreen tree form the South-Eastern regions of Asia, well known throughout history for its sweet fruit. The fruit features a red coloured harder inedible outer shell, followed by the fruit pulp and the seed.

Brassica Juncea (or Brown Mustard, Indian Mustard, Chinese Mustard) is a species of mustard plant widely used in South-Eastern and African Cuisine, where its leaves are cooked, or its oil gets cold pressed and extracted for frying purposes.

Both plants are commonly found in West Bengal State, in North-Eastern India, thus making their honey rather easily obtainable. The aim of the following study was to analyse certain Physico-chemical and Biochemical parameters from these types of honey from the forementioned region.

Keywords: Honey, Lychee Honey, Mustard Honey, Indian Honey Analysis

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INTRODUCTION

Honey is defined as "the sweet substance produced by honeybees from the nectar of blossoms or from secretions on living plants, which the bees collect, transform and store in honeycombs" (Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2002). Naturally, honey has been traditionally recognized as a valuable source of energy. It has also been recognized for its antimicrobial characteristics, possessed excellent antioxidant activity and is such a natural product with several therapeutic properties. It is a concentrated aqueous solution of invert sugar, that contains a mixture of other carbohydrates, amino and organic acids, minerals, aromatic substances, pigments, waxes and pollen grains to make it complex (Al-Quassemi and Robinson, 2003).

Litchi chinensis belongs to the Sapindaceae family and is well-known in the Indian traditional system for its traditional uses. The parts of the plant used are leaves, flowers, fruits, seed, pulp, and pericarp. All parts of the plant are rich sources of phytochemicals--epicatechin; procyanidin A2 and procyanidin B2; leucocyanidin; cyanidin glycoside, malvidin glycoside and saponins; butylated hydroxytoluene; isolaricresinol; kaempferol; rutin; and stigmasterol.

Ayurveda and the naturopathic system of medicine (indigenous to India) clearly state the use of medicinal plants for treating various disorders. India has a rich knowledge of phytotherapy from ayurveda and hundreds of potent drugs are yet to be evaluated scientifically. Keeping this in view, the lychee is one of the potential plants that has edible fruits and the other parts of which also have potent traditional application, but it has not been studied much (Kilari and Putta, 2016). The component of interest for honey production and implicitly for our research is the flower. Lychee flowers are small and inconspicuous, greenish in colour, and are borne in loose terminal clusters sometimes up to 30cm long (Britannica, 2024).

Mustard (*Brassica juncea*) is a cruciferous vegetable used as a food spice and folk medicine worldwide. Mustard contains numerous phytochemicals such as: vitamins, minerals, dietary fiber, chlorophylls, glucosinolates (and their degradation products), polyphenols and volatile components (allyl-isothiocyanate, 3-butyl isothiocyanate, etc.) Tian, and Deng (2020).

Mustard honey, a monofloral honey derived from mustard flower is considered a great source of nutritional and medicinal values. The honey is traditionally used as ethnomedicine in different parts of the world to cure many health problems (Billah et al, 2019).

The aim of the present study was the physical-chemical and biochemical characterization of two types of honey from India: Lychee and Mustard honey. I discovered these assortments during my participation in the Erasmus placement, carried out at the University of Calcutta in 2023.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As mentioned before, in the region of the Sundarbans, in the district of West Bengal, it is common to see Lychee tree orchards as well as Indian mustard plantations. Therefore, in the pollinating season, the honey production from these specific plants increases.

In the study, 2 samples of honey were analysed, one of lychee and one of mustard.

To obtain the most accurate values, we worked with 3 samples from each type of honey.

For both types of honey, an organoleptic examination was carried out, certain physico-chemical and biochemical parameters.

The Physico-chemical and biochemical analysis conducted were the following: colour determination, water, total soluble substances (TSS), ash an HMF content, the total polyphenols (TPC) and antioxidant activity (AA).

For the organoleptic analysis, we looked into the general aspect of the honeys: degree of impurity (d.o.i.), consistency, colour, taste, smell.

Physical-chemical parameters, like: colour, water, pH, acidity, ash, were analysed according to the Romanian Standard Analysis Methods (National Standard, 2009) and Harmonised methods of the IHC (Bogdanov, 2009), or with specific methods.

- Colour determination: ABS 450nm/ and Pfund scale
- Water and Total soluble substances (TSS): Brix index - refractometric determination
- Total acidity - titrimetric method
- HMF determination - WHITE method (spectrophotometric determination)
- Ash content - calcination at 525°C
- Total Polyphenol (TPC) - Folin-Ciocalteu method
- Total Antioxidant (AA) - FRAP method

Colour Analysis

To help us further expand our information in the colour differences, we conducted a colour intensity analysis. The net absorbance ABS 450, was defined as the difference between spectrophotometric absorbance at 450nm and 720nm. Determinations were made with a

Shimadzu UV Mini 1240 spectrophotometer (Beretta, 2005).

The colour of honey was then determined by spectrophotometric measurement of the absorbance of a 50% honey solution (w/v) at 635 nm. The honeys were classified according to the Pfund scale after conversion of the absorbance values using the formula:

$\text{mm Pfund} = -38.70 + 371.39 \times \text{Abs } 635$
where mm Pfund is the intensity of honey colour in the Pfund scale and Abs is the absorption of honey solution (White, 1984).

Ash Content Determination

The ash content was determined using calcination in a calcinating oven, by gradually heating the samples from 90°C all the way to 525°C. The process was stopped when only white ash remained in the porcelain crucible.

After cooling, the crucibles were weighed, and the ash percentage was calculated for both types of honey.

Water and Total Soluble Substances – BRIX

The total sugar content corresponds to the concentration in the water-soluble substance, expressed in BRIX degrees, because in honey sugar is the main water-soluble substance, the rest of the compounds being quantitatively insignificant. The desired results were obtained using a digital refractometer (KRUS, AR 2008 model, Germany).

Total acidity

Total acidity was determined by titration method (Bogdanov, 2009).

Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) Content determination

HMF content was determined by spectrophotometric method (White, 1979). Each of the honey samples was divided into 2 clarified aliquots; water was added to one of the aliquots and absorption was read at $\lambda=284$ and 336 nm. This was compared to a second solution in which this absorption was eliminated by the addition of sodium bisulphate. Results were expressed in milligrams of HMF per kilogram of honey.

$\text{HMF (mg/kg)} = (A_{284} - A_{336}) \times 149.7 \times 5/m$,
where A_{284} = absorbance reading at 284nm,
 A_{336} = absorbance reading at 336nm,
 m = sample mass (g),
5 = nominal mass of the sample and
 $149.7 = (126/16830) \times (1000/10) \times (1000/5)$.

Total polyphenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity (AA)

The total polyphenolic content (TPC) of the samples was determined by using the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method developed by Singleton and Rossi (1965). The method relies on the transfer of electrons in alkaline medium from phenolic compounds to form a blue chromophore constituted by a phosphotungstic complex where the maximum absorption depends on the concentration of phenolic compounds. For the calibration curve, gallic acid solution were used as the standard.

The results of the spectrophotometric reading are expressed in mg GAE 100mg/kg honey.

The total antioxidant activity were determined using FRAP method (Berzie and Stain, 1996). This method is based on the ability of substances to reduce ferric to ferrous ions, which in the presence of TPTZ at an acidic pH, form a blue colored complex. The absorbance was read at a wavelength of 593 nm. For calibration curve, Trolox solution were used.

Results are further expressed as FRAP values for a 10% honey solution, equal with the μmol Trolox equivalent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Organoleptic analysis

The results of the organoleptic analysis conducted on the two types of honey are presented in the table 1.

Table 1
Organoleptic results of Lychee and Indian Mustard Honey

Analyzed parameters	Lychee honey	Indian mustard honey
General Aspect	homogenous without foam or bubbles	homogenous small air bubbles on the surface
Colour	light colour, golden hue	darker colour, brownish-yellow
Taste and smell	sweet taste, subtle floral smell	sweet taste, specific sharp smell
Consistency	fluid, homogenous, without signs of sugar crystals	fluid, homogenous, without signs of crystals
d.o.i.	without any impurities	without any impurities

Therefore, based on the results of the organoleptic tests carried on the two honey

samples, we can see the differences to be mainly in the colour field, as well as the smell, which goes from a floral one in lychee honey to a sharper, almost pungent scent in the mustard honey.

Colour

After performing the calculations, it was determined that the colours of the two honey samples on the Pfund scale were defined as "White" for the Lychee honey and "Light Amber" for the Indian Mustard honey.

Fig 1. Pfund colour scale – graphic representation

Table 2
Colour intensity (ABS450n) and Pfund Colour intensity results

	Lychee Honey	Mustard Honey
Abs 450nm	0.223	0.41
Abs 720nm	0.002	0.01
Abs 450n	0.221	0.4
Colour	white	Extra light amber
Abs 635nm	0.11	0.201
Pfund	2.15	35.95
Colour Pfund	white	Extra light amber

Ash Content

The values obtained for the ash content were within the limits provided by the FSSAI (Food Safety and Standards Authority of India) specifications, but also fall within the values allowed for ash according to European regulations (0.6%) (Bogdanov, 2009, Council Directive 2001/110/EC of 20 December 2001).

Table 3
Honey ash percentage together with FSSAI maximum permitted value

	Lychee honey	Mustard honey	FSSAI max. value
Ash %	0.040	0.047	0.050

Water and Total Soluble Substances – BRIX

As per the values, the obtained water percentages were both above the EU regulatory standards which allow a water percentage of up to 20% in regular honeys (European

Commission, 2014). However, according to the Indian regulatory standards, which include a calculation correction according to the collecting temperature of the honey as well as the temperature of the lab environment when analyzing the honey samples, the two values which can be observed in the table below are safe for consumers and, therefore, keep the product on the market (FSSAI, 04B.003:2023).

For the Total Soluble Substance percentage, the same refractometer was used, and the value ranged from 73.8% to 77.0%.

Total acidity values respect the limits established for honey in International Regulatory Standards and in FSSAI.

Values for water, TSS and total acidity can be found in table 4.

Table 4
Honey water and TSS and total acidity percentage together with RO/FSSAI maximum permitted value

	Water %	TSS Brix %	Total acidity °T/kg
Lychee	24.8	73.7	27.6
Indian mustard	21.6	77.0	14.7
RO/ FSSAI	20 (25.2*)	-	50

Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) Content

The determined values represented the content of HMF expressed in mg/kg and are presented in the table 5.

Table 5
HMF content together with FSSAI maximum permitted value

	Lychee honey	Mustard honey	FSSAI standard
HMF (mg/kg)	77.67	11.76	80.0

The FSSAI standard allows for a HMF content in honeys from warm and humid areas up to double the European Commission's value (40 mgHMF/kg honey), therefore making these honeys fit within the regulatory standards of the Indian market.

Total polyphenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity (AA)

The results of the spectrophotometric determination of TPC, was expressed in mg GAE/kg honey.

The calibration curve for TPC was represented in Fig.1 and for AA, in Fig.2

Fig.1. Total Polyphenolic content calibration curve

Fig.2. Total antioxidant activity FRAP -calibration curve

Both the Antioxidant Activity results and the TPC results were included in the table 6.

TPC of Mustard honey was almost 4 times higher than TPC for Lychee honey.

Total AA was 2 time higher in mustard honey in comparison with Lychee honey.

Table 6
Results regarding TPC and AA values

Sample	TPC (mg GAE/kg)	AA (µmol Trolox equivalent)
Lychee honey	2.26	70.32
Mustard honey	8.57	155.422

CONCLUSIONS

The two samples of honey we analysed are honeys with a specific aroma, strong flavours and a higher fluidity, the latter one thanks to the higher average temperature in the areas of cultivation in India.

The values obtained for the physical-chemical parameters fit within the European regulatory standards except HMF and water content, which have a different limit in the Indian market.

Comparing the 2 types of honey, comparing the 2 types of honey, it can be observed that the Mustard Honey has a lower water content, with a higher TPC and AA. The composition of the honeys varies depending on the floral source, seasonal and environmental factors.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was co-funded from the project CNFIS FDI-2024-F-0334 – “Interdisciplinary research and innovation using sustainable technologies – CIIUTS” funded by UEFISCDI.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF APPLE FRUITS AND THE EFFECT OF APPLE JUICE PASTEURIZATION ON VITAMIC C CONTENT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The objective of this study was to characterize three apple varieties (Idared, Red Delicious and Golden Delicious) grown in Romania, with an emphasis on the physico-chemical characteristics. The influence of pasteurization at 70 °C for 30 minutes on ascorbic acid content was also an important objective. Among the physico-chemical characteristics, the content of Dry matter, Humidity, Total mineral content (ash), Total soluble solids (TSS), Total titratable acidity (TTA) and the pH was determined. Among the 3 apple varieties, Golden Delicious (GD) presented a remarkably higher content of total minerals (0.179 %), TTA (3.66 % malic acid in pasteurized juice and 3.52 % malic acid in unpasteurized juice, respectively) and TSS (14.25 °Brix in unpasteurized juice), compared to the varieties Idared (IR) and Red Delicious (RD). After pasteurization, the content of ascorbic acid decreased significantly, compared to unpasteurized juices, and the highest content was reported by unpasteurized IR juice (4.39 %). However, in the case of the GD variety, the content of TTA increases after pasteurization, compared to unpasteurized juice. The investigated apple varieties are fruits rich in bioactive compounds, and the pasteurization treatment does not lead to drastic decreases in the studied physico-chemical parameters.

Keywords: Apple fruits, Apple juice, Physico-chemical parameters, Vitamin C, pasteurized juice.

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INTRODUCTION

Apples are a class of fruit varieties that ripen from late summer to winter and are mostly consumed fresh. The most common domesticated apples are known as *Malus x domestica* (*M. domestica*). Apples can be stored and consumed in all seasons and attract consumers with their color, shape, size and taste. Quality markers of apples are represented by size, shape, color, taste, smell, strength and firmness (Babojelić et al., 2007; Bordean et al., 2013).

If the fruit is harvested too early, and it does not reach the normal point of maturity, the bioactive compounds present in the fruit do not develop completely, and the organoleptic characteristics will suffer. At the same time, if the apple harvest is delayed, it overripes, which leads to storage risks, making it susceptible to handling and storage diseases (Bogdanescu et al., 2018; Bordean et al., 2013; Cvetković et al., 2012).

Apples are harvested manually, by slightly twisting the fruit, thus preventing the occurrence of physical risks. From the moment of harvest until the moment the fruits reach the storage area, it should not exceed more than 2-3

days, so as not to negatively influence the storage capacity (Bogdanescu et al., 2018; Bordean et al., 2013; Cvetković et al., 2012)..

For long-term storage, fruits belonging to varieties with high economic value should be selected, such as Jonathan, Golden Delicious, Florina, Starking Delicious, Idared, etc (Bassi et al., 2017; Bogdanescu et al., 2018).

The optimal storage temperature may vary depending on the variety, depending on their tolerance to low temperatures, which can lead to physiological disorders of the fruits. Among the cold-resistant varieties with sweet flesh and slightly acidic are the 'Golden Delicious' and 'Red Delicious' varieties, which are stored at temperatures between 0° C and 1° C. In the category of acidic varieties and more sensitive to cold, there is also the 'Idared' variety, which has an optimal storage temperature of about 3-4° C (Bogdanescu et al., 2018).

The 'Red Delicious' variety originated in Peru, Iowa, USA, in about 1972 and was introduced commercially in 1895. It has become the most important and best studied variety in the world, with a distinctive color and appearance. It is an important variety in the European Union, the USA and many other countries. The fruit is crisp and juicy when

harvested in September and October (Bassi et al., 2017; Doryanizadeh et al., 2016; Ferree David C. & Warrington I., n.d.).

'Golden Delicious' is the second most popular variety grown after 'Red Delicious' and was discovered in West Virginia in 1914. The variety is a medium to large pale yellow apple, which is mild and sweet. It is crisp when harvested in September and October (Bassi et al., 2017; Bogdanescu et al., 2018; Ornelas-Paz et al., 2018; Thakur et al., 2024).

'Idared' is an apple that was scientifically developed in 1942 at the University of Idaho Agricultural Experiment Station and is a cross between the Jonathan and Wegener varieties. Since then, demand for production has increased significantly. 'Idared' is a medium to large apple with a creamy white flesh that is firm, crisp, and juicy (Bogdanescu et al., 2018; Paunovic et al., 2010; Schechter et al., 1993).

Apples, as well as other fruits such as oranges, grapefruits, and strawberries, are known to possess another layer called the extracellular cuticle. This cuticle protects the apple from physical, chemical, and biological stresses such as wind, temperature, chemicals, and drought when the fruit is in the growing stage, as well as when it is harvested. The literature has shown that the outer layer contributes to these barrier properties. Consequently, apples are exposed to mold infections, physical damage and moisture loss (Arrieta-Baez et al., 2020; Bandici et al., 2022).

The aim of this research was to investigate the influence of juice pasteurization on the vitamin C content, as well as the physicochemical characteristics of three Romanian apple varieties: Idared (IR), Red Delicious (RD) and Golden Delicious (GD).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Plant Materials

Fresh fruits from three different varieties of apples grown in Romania, namely Idared (IR), Red Delicious (RD) and Golden Delicious (GD), were purchased from the local market and transported to the laboratory of the Faculty of Environmental Protection, University of Oradea, Romania, being then analyzed. Before starting the experiment, the fruits were very well washed and dried, and then used to determine the Sensory analysis, Dry matter, Humidity, Total mineral content (ash), Total soluble solids

(TSS), Total titratable acidity (TTA), the pH and the content of Acis ascorbic (Vitamin C).

For the determination of sensory analysis, dry matter, humidity and total mineral content (ash), the fruits as such were used.

For TSS, TTA, pH and vitamin C content determinations, fresh fruits were well homogenized in a blender (WARING), the extract obtained was then filtered, and finally, a clear juice without impurities was obtained. Part of the obtained juice was subjected to the pasteurization process at a temperature of 70° C for 30 min, and part of the juice was kept unpasteurized. The operation was repeated for all three varieties of apple under study, and further the previously mentioned determinations were made, both for unpasteurized apple juice and for pasteurized juice, according to the experimental plan presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The experimental design for the determination of the physico-chemical parameters of apple fruits and respectively, of apple juices obtained from the varieties IR., RD. and GD.

Sensorial analyze

Ten sensory characteristics (appearance, aroma, taste, texture and aspects related to overall desirability) were evaluated by a team of four men and ten women aged between 19 and 46, students and members of the Department of Food Engineering from the University of Oradea, Romania. Each characteristic was scored between 1 (unacceptable) and 10 (excellent). During the assessment, panel members were given 5 minutes of rest between tests to minimize fatigue and carryover effects. For data collection, sensory evaluation sheets were used and the results define food products quality (Memete et al., 2022).

Determination of dry matter and humidity

Dry matter determination from the conducted analysis was determined through water elimination in the drying oven at 105°C up to a constant weight value.

The percentual vanished weight is represented by the water content, also referred as humidity (Miteluț et al., 2021; Purcărea, 2015).

Determination of mineral substances

For the determination of mineral substances, the apples were finely chopped, weighed and transferred to ceramic crucibles to withstand the calcination furnace at high temperatures. Mineral substances are inorganic substances that appear after exposure to high temperatures of 525±25°C in the calcining furnace for 18 hours until the weight of the sample is constant (Harris & Marshall, 2017; Ismail, 2017; Purcărea, 2015).

Determination of total soluble solids (TSS)

Total soluble solids (TSS) results indicate the concentration of sugar in the sample.

Total soluble solids were refractometrically determined from both unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices. In the first stage, the juice obtained was filtered to obtain a clear juice without impurities. The portable KRÜSS refractometer was turned on, and then brought to 0 with distilled water, after which the Brix readings (in triplicate) of the studied samples were taken at a temperature of 20°C. The results were expressed in °Brix percentage (Memete, Sărac, et al., 2023)..

Determination of total titatable acidity (TTA) and pH

10 ml of clear apple juice, without impurities, was homogenized with 50 ml of distilled water. In an Erlenmeyer glass, over the obtained extract, 2.3 drops of phenolphthalein were added, and then titrated with NaOH 0, 1 N until the color turns pink which must persist for 30 seconds. All determinations were performed in triplicate.

Equation (1) was used to interpret the results

$$A = V \times 10 \quad (1)$$

Where: A - acidity of the extract expressed in degrees of acidity; V - the volume of the 0.1 N NaOH solution used in the titration, in ml.

For graphical representation, the degrees of acidity were transformed into grams of organic acid that is representative of apple fruits (malic acid).

The pH was determined using a pH meter (Denver Instrument 220) previously calibrated with pH 4.0 and pH 7.0 buffer solutions, the electrode of the pH meter was fully immersed in 100 ml of unpasteurized apple juice and pasteurized, for accuracy of results. All determinations were performed in triplicate at 23°C (Memete et al. 2023; Rosnah et al. 2012).

Determination of vitamin C content

In an Erlenmeyer beaker, 10 ml of apple juice and 20 ml of 2% oxalic acid were added, homogenizing together for 5 minutes. After homogenization, 10 ml of sample was transferred into another Erlenmeyer beaker and titrated with 0.01% 2,6 dichlorophenol indophenol solution until the appearance of a pink color that persisted for at least 15 seconds. The operation was repeated with standard ascorbic acid solution and the titration volume with 0.01% 2,6 dichlorophenol indophenol solution was noted (Memete, Miere (Groza), et al., 2023; Parveez Zia & Alibas, 2021).

In order to quantify the results, equation (2) was used:

$$\% \text{ Vitamin C} = (\text{Titration volume of samples} / \text{Titration volume of standard acid solution}) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sensory analysis of apple cultivars

The importance of sensory analysis for food products is increasing, especially in terms of smell and taste, because, in addition to the nutritional value and beneficial effects that accumulate in the body through the consumption of certain foods, they attract consumers primarily due to the appearance and their taste. Sensory analysis is also important in the acceptance or rejection of the food product (Khodaei et al., 2021).

The results of the sensory analysis of fresh apples of different varieties (IR, RD and GD) are presented in Figure 2.

The sensory evaluation method of apple fruit considered visual attributes (color), three gustatory attributes (pulp consistency and juiciness of the flesh, taste and ripeness) and harmony of general characteristics. The color of fruits is important in their acceptance or rejection by consumers (Khodaei et al., 2021; Memete et al., 2022).

Figure 2. Sensory analysis of three different varieties of apple fruit (IR, RD, GD). V.U.A = Variety Autenticity and Uniformity; F.= Form; S. = Size ; C. = Color; E.A. = Exterior Aspect; Fn.= Freshness; P.C. = Pulp Consistency and juiciness of the flesh; A = Aroma; T.= Taste; Rn.= Ripeness.

Regarding the sensory analysis of the three apple varieties (Figure 2), IR reported the highest score for sensory characteristics such as Ripeness (Rn), Size (S) and Freshness (Fn). Analyzing the RD variety, the highest score reported was for Exterior Aspect (E.A.) and Aroma (A). The lowest score was reported for External Appearance (E.A.) compared to IR and GD varieties. Regarding the GD variety, the best score recorded was for Taste (T), followed by Pulp Consistency (P.C) and Color (C).

The content of dry matter and humidity in apple cultivars

As physico-chemical growth and development parameters of the three apple varieties, the percentage of dry matter and humidity was determined for each variety by measuring the weight loss of the fruits after their total dehydration in the oven at 105°C until reaching of a constant weight; The results were presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Dry matter and humidity content of IR, ID and GD apple fruits.

Based on the results presented in Figure 3, the percentage of humidity differs according to the variety of fruit studied. The highest humidity percentage was recorded by RD (89.11%), and the lowest by GD (87.48 %). All varieties recorded a high percentage of humidity, with no statistically significant differences reported. Comparing with other studies in the literature, values close to those reported in Figure 3, in terms of dry matter and humidity of the variety IR, were reported in the study of Paunovic et al., 2010 where the dry matter was 15.4 % and the humidity of 84.6 % (Paunovic et al., 2010). Doryanizadeh et al., 2016 reported humidity in the RD variety between 75.76% and 81.5% (Doryanizadeh et al., 2016). Also, Ornelas-Paz et al., 2017 determined the humidity content of GD apples at different ripening stages, and the reported values ranged from 86.0±0.2 % to 86.8±0.1 % (Ornelas-Paz et al., 2018). There are many factors that can influence fruit humidity and dry matter, such as agricultural practices, climatic conditions (high temperatures), fruit maturity level, size, surface-to-volume ratio or external structure. All the listed factors can lead to large differences in humidity, even between the same varieties or varieties of the same species (Bovi et al., 2018; Lufu et al., 2020).

The content of total minerals (ash) in apple cultivars

The content of total minerals was determined for each apple variety, by measuring the weight loss of the fruits after their total dehydration in a calcining oven at 525±25 °C until a light gray ash was obtained; The results were presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The total mineral content (Ash) of IR, ID and GD apple fruits.

The determination of the ash of food refers to the total minerals and inorganic substances remaining after the food sample has been heated to a very high temperature, removing moisture, volatile and organic substances. The most common minerals and inorganic substances in food are calcium, magnesium, sodium and potassium, but others can also be identified, such as manganese, iron, zinc, in smaller quantities (Harris & Marshall, 2017; Ismail, 2017).

From the results obtained following the determination of the total mineral content and shown in Figure 4, the GD apple varieties followed by the RD reported significantly higher values (0.179% and 0.177, respectively), compared to the IR (0.114%).

The ash content may vary, depending on the degree of processing of the food. Natural foods have lower ash content compared to processed foods (Harris & Marshall, 2017; Ismail, 2017).

Denes, 2023 determined the ash (total mineral content) of a mix of dried Romanian apples from the varieties 'Poinic', 'Mustos', 'Dulce', 'Summer', 'Winter', 'Jonathan' and the reported value was 2.04. Also, in the same study, ash was reported only for the 'Mustos' variety in different years (2018, 2021), and the values obtained were 1.4 and 1.74, respectively (Denes, 2023).

Physico-chemical parameters determined in unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices

Physico-chemical determination of apples, such as pH, total titratable acidity (%) and total soluble solids (TSS) expressed in % degree/Brix, were determined from fresh juice, both unpasteurized and pasteurized, obtained for each variety in part.

TTA content in unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices

The results of total titratable acidity (%) of unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Total titratable acidity of unpasteurized and pasteurized juice obtained from IR, RD and GD apple fruits.

Regarding the total titratable acidity of apple juice (Figure 5), no significant differences were reported between unpasteurized and pasteurized juices for the same variety studied. The highest values were reported for juices obtained from GD apple varieties, both in the case of unpasteurized (3.53 ± 0.01 % malic acid) and pasteurized ones (3.66 ± 0.02 % malic acid). Juices obtained from apples of the RD variety reported the lowest TTA values (2.17 ± 0.03 % malic acid in unpasteurized juice and 2.04 ± 0.01 % malic acid in pasteurized juice respectively); The acidity differences between RD and the other two varieties (IR and GD) are statistically significant in both situations.

Comparing with other literature studies, regarding TTA in GD fruits, Thakur et al., 2024 reported lower values (0.35 ± 0.01 % malic acid) compared to GD fruits in our study (Thakur et al., 2024). Rupasinghe et al., 2010 studied total titratable acidity in 14 red-fleshed apple cultivars, 3 commercial apple cultivars and 3 commercially produced apple juices, and reported values ranged from 0.242 % malic acid (commercial apple cultivar) and 1.28% malic acid (red-fleshed apple) (Rupasinghe et al., 2010).

The pH values in the unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices

The results of pH of unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The pH of unpasteurized and pasteurized juice obtained from IR, RD and GD apple fruits.

From Figure 6 it can be seen that the highest pH is reported in the unpasteurized RD juice (4.1), followed by the pasteurized one (4.03), compared to GD and IR. No statistically significant differences were noted between unpasteurized and pasteurized juices of the same apple variety.

Regarding the pH values in the case of the GD variety, similar values were also obtained in the study of Planchon et al., 2004, namely 3.65 (Planchon et al., 2004). Also, a pH of 3.81 ± 0.09 was reported in the study of Thakur et al., 2024 for the variety GD. (Thakur et al., 2024). In the study Bassi et al., 2017, most of the juices obtained from the commercial variety RD had a pH close to 4 (Bassi et al., 2017). In another study, Bogdănescu et al., 2018 determined the pH of eight Romanian apple cultivars, and regarding the ID and GD cultivars the values were similar to those reported in our study (Bogdanescu et al., 2018).

The pH value is closely correlated with the concentration of ascorbic acid in fruit juices. More acidic juices contain higher concentrations of organic acids, especially malic and citric acid, which help protect ascorbic acid from degradation (Bassi et al., 2017; CoSeteng et al., 1989). In addition, the redder the juices, the higher the concentrations of anthocyanins, especially cyanidin-3-O-galactoside which also contributes to the protection of ascorbic acid from oxidation, through its powerful antioxidant capacity (Rupasinghe et al., 2010).

The TSS content in the unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices

The results of the Total Soluble Solids (TSS) of the juices obtained from the 3 unpasteurized and pasteurized apple varieties (IR, RD and GD) are expressed in % °Brix and presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The total soluble solids (TSS) of unpasteurized and pasteurized juice obtained from IR, RD and GD apple fruits.

Soluble sugars and organic acids play an important role in determining fruit taste. In apple, fructose is the most abundant soluble sugar, while the predominant organic acid is malic acid which represents up to about 90% of the total organic acids (Monago-Maraña et al., 2021; Zhang & Han, 2021). Apple sweetness is correlated with TSS content, which includes total soluble substances such as organic acids, amino acids, soluble pectins. Also, TSS is an essential parameter in determining the aroma, degree of ripeness, as well as to establish the optimal harvest time of apples (Guan et al., 2015; Monago-Maraña et al., 2021; Zhang & Han, 2021).

TSS analysis indicates the sugar content of juices obtained from 3 apple varieties, unpasteurized and pasteurized. From Figure 7 it can be seen that there were no significant differences between the 3 unpasteurized juices and the 3 pasteurized juices, the highest values being reported by juices obtained from the GD variety in the case of the unpasteurized ones (14.25 °Brix) and RD in the case of the pasteurized ones (14.13 °Brix), and the lowest values were reported by IR in both situations (13.44 °Brix for unpasteurized juice and 13.23 °Brix for pasteurized juice, respectively).

Comparing our results with other studies in the literature, similar results were also reported by Bogdănescu et al., 2018, where the highest TSS values were reported for the GD variety and the lowest were for the IR variety in the case of the GD variety (Bogdanescu et al., 2018). In the study of Planchon et al., 2004 TSS values in apple juice were 13.8 Brix (Planchon et al., 2004). Thakur et al., 2024 also studied the TSS content in GD apples and reported values of 25.48 ± 0.69 °Brix (Thakur et al., 2024). In another study, Monago-Maraña et al., 2021 reported TSS values, determined at 25 °C,

between 15 and 16 % (Monago-Maraña et al., 2021).

The ascorbic acid content in the unpasteurized and pasteurized apple juices

Ascorbic acid (Vitamin C), a powerful water-soluble antioxidant compound, was quantified from the juices obtained from apple fruits and the influence of pasteurization at 70°C on the juice obtained from the three apple varieties: IR, RD and GD was observed. The results obtained were presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The Ascorbic acid of unpasteurized and pasteurized juice obtained from IR, RD and GD apple fruits.

Apples are among the most consumed fruits in the Western world, either fresh or processed. Therefore, apples are a major source of nutrients and antioxidants. The content of antioxidants, and ascorbic acid in particular, has been extensively studied in other studies, but this content has been shown to be dependent on genotype, geographical position, environmental conditions during the growing and ripening season, agricultural practices, storage conditions as well as processing ones (Farneti et al., 2015; Vegro et al., 2016; Wojdyło et al., 2008). Increased attention to healthy foods has led to a growing interest in identifying varieties with a high ascorbic acid content; However, there are few studies that focus on the factors that influence the content of ascorbic acid in different apple genotypes (Bassi et al., 2017; Kevers et al., 2011; Laslo et al., 2018; Planchon et al., 2004).

Regarding the results of our study, it can be seen in Figure 7 that there is a significant decrease in the content of ascorbic acid in pasteurized apple juice compared to unpasteurized juice. The highest content of ascorbic acid was reported in the juice obtained from apples of the IR variety (4.39 % in unpasteurized juice and 2.80 % in pasteurized

juice, respectively), and the lowest content is given by the juice obtained from the GD variety (2.81 % in unpasteurized juice and 1.25 % in pasteurized juice, respectively).

Ascorbic acid in apples degrades both during fruit processing and storage, a fact also confirmed in the study by Kevers et al., 2011, where they observed that ascorbic acid degraded by 80% during three months of cold storage, thus providing a possible explanation for the lower values obtained (Kevers et al., 2011). Also, in the study by Laslo et al., 2018, they investigated the effect of pasteurization on juices obtained from two different varieties of apples grown in Romania (Florina and Liberty). The results demonstrated that the content of ascorbic acid in juices pasteurized at 80° C for 25 minutes, decreased by 73.53% and 76.35% for Florina and Liberty juices, respectively, compared to unpasteurized apple juices (Laslo et al., 2018).

In another study, Planchon et al., 2004 reported ascorbic acid contents ranging from 2.9 to 25.6 mg/100 g FW for whole fruit from 30 old Belgian apple cultivars. Among the 30 varieties studied, we also list the GD variety, for which the reported ascorbic acid content was 11.4 mg/100 g FM (Planchon et al., 2004). Bassi et al., 2017 studied the ascorbic acid content in the pulp of 64 different apple cultivars and reported values between 0.1 mg/100 g and 13.9 mg/100 g. Among the 64 cultivars studied, RD and GD cultivars were also listed which had an ascorbic acid content of less than 1.5 mg/100 g FW in the pulp (Bassi et al., 2017).

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper it is shown that the varieties IR, RD and GD which are widely cultivated in Romania, are fruits with valuable sensory characteristics for human consumption. The pasteurization process of apple juices at 70 °C for 30 minutes increased the level of total titratable acidity in GD juice and significantly decreased the content of Vitamin C, as well as the other studied parameters. Among the apple varieties, GD recorded the highest total mineral content (0.179%) compared to RD (0.177%) and IR (0.114%) varieties. Also, RD was the most appreciative in terms of the sensory characteristics studied and recorded the highest humidity and pH values. From the point of view of vitamin C content, the IR variety stood out with the highest content, both in terms of unpasteurized (4.39 %) and pasteurized (2.80

%) juice. At the same time, the IR variety reported the lowest values of pH, total minerals and TSS, but was the most appreciated for the flavor and external appearance of the fruit. As future perspectives, it is important to study the effect of pasteurization on the evolution of bioactive compounds from apple juices grown in Romania, as well as to establish the best conditions to obtain juices or other food products from apples that maintain a high level of vitamin C, bioactive compounds as well as high antioxidant capacity.

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THE HIGHLIGHTING OF MIGRATORY-TYPE COLONIES FOR PROTEUS

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REVIEW, RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The most well-known characteristic of *Proteus* colonies is the formation of a "wave" or "swarming" pattern on solid media (such as agar). This is due to a property called "swarming," through which the bacteria move collectively across the surface of the medium, expanding and creating concentric rings. The colonies can rapidly increase in diameter due to this behavior. *Proteus mirabilis* has significantly higher motility than many other bacteria, allowing it to spread in waves on solid media. This movement is supported by a large number of pericellular flagella, which help the bacteria move in large groups. The swarming patterns of the colonies vary based on factors such as the composition of the culture medium, temperature, and humidity. In optimal conditions, *Proteus* colonies tend to appear more structured and organized, with concentric patterns that can be influenced by bacterial density and migration speed. *Proteus* colonies demonstrate high adaptability to various environmental conditions, which contributes to the bacterium's resistance in hostile environments and its survival in competitive conditions with other microorganisms. *Proteus* colonies are an important indicator in diagnosing urinary tract infections and other opportunistic infections, as the unique swarming patterns aid in quick identification in the laboratory. In the lab, these colony characteristics are particularly useful for identifying *Proteus mirabilis* and other species within the same genus, as each distinct form and characteristic movement is unique to this bacterial genus.

Keywords: swarming colonies, environmental conditions, microorganisms

INTRODUCTION

Proteus is a genus of Gram-negative bacteria in the family *Enterobacteriaceae*, best known for the species *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris*. These bacteria are found in various environments, including soil, water, and the intestines of some animals and humans. Typically, *Proteus* bacteria are harmless, but certain species are pathogenic and can cause infections in humans, particularly urinary tract infections and wound-associated infections.

Proteus bacteria are rod-shaped bacilli equipped with flagella that give them impressive mobility, known as "swarming" motility. This motility facilitates their rapid movement and the formation of characteristic colonies on solid media, appearing as concentric rings. Swarming motility is a distinctive trait of *Proteus* bacteria. On solid culture media, such as agar, the bacteria form "wave-like" patterns due to their rapid and coordinated movement. This phenomenon occurs in stages, alternating between periods of intense swarming and rest phases.

Proteus produces the enzyme urease, which breaks down urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide. This ability plays an important role in diagnosing infections, as urease production contributes to the alkalization of the environment, serving as a specific indicator in

the laboratory for identifying these bacteria. Certain strains of *Proteus*, particularly *Proteus vulgaris*, have acquired resistance to multiple classes of antibiotics, including beta-lactams. This makes treating infections caused by *Proteus* challenging, especially in patients with compromised immune systems.

Species of the *Proteus* genus, particularly *Proteus mirabilis*, are often associated with urinary tract infections, especially in patients with long-term urinary catheter use. They can cause severe infections, such as pyelonephritis (a kidney infection), and may lead to the formation of urinary stones through ammonia production, which alkalizes the urine. *Proteus* infections are common in the urinary tract, but these bacteria can also cause wound infections, otitis, and, in rare cases, septicemia. Diagnosis of these infections often relies on clinical symptoms and laboratory tests that identify the bacteria through specific properties, such as urease production and distinctive swarming patterns.

Proteus mirabilis is a Gram-negative bacterium from the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, known for its high motility and ability to colonize the urinary tract. It is one of the most common causes of urinary tract infections, especially in cases of complicated infections associated with urinary catheters. Typically, *Proteus mirabilis* lives in soil, water, and the intestines of some

animals and humans but can become pathogenic under certain circumstances. *Proteus mirabilis* is a rod-shaped bacillus with pericellular flagella that provide it with high motility. Due to the large number of flagella, *P. mirabilis* can move rapidly on moist surfaces, especially solid media, spreading in waves or concentric rings.

Proteus mirabilis exhibits a unique "swarming" behavior on solid media, where it forms wave-like patterns. This is a distinctive characteristic that facilitates its identification in the laboratory. Swarming occurs in cyclic stages: periods of rapid growth and migration are followed by resting phases. An important feature of this bacterium is the production of urease, an enzyme that breaks down urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide. This process leads to the alkalization of the environment, creating conditions favorable for urinary stone formation. Alkalinization of the urine is a hallmark of *Proteus mirabilis* infections and aids in diagnosis. Ammonia-induced alkalization promotes the precipitation of phosphate, calcium carbonate, and magnesium salts, which lead to the formation of urinary stones. These stones can cause blockages and severe inflammation, complicating urinary tract infections.

Although *Proteus mirabilis* is generally susceptible to many antibiotics, some strains have developed resistance to certain classes of drugs, including penicillins and cephalosporins. This can complicate treatment, especially in chronic or complicated infections.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I conducted a prospective study based on microbiological diagnoses recorded in the bacteriological registry of the medical analysis laboratory, S.C. Diaser, Oradea. To conduct the study, I also accessed the archive, recorded in the laboratory's computer program in S.C. Diaser, Oradea, as well as the computerized database of the unit.

In the laboratory, the identification of bacteria from the *Proteus* genus requires a specific set of materials and a methodology to confirm the presence of these bacteria and determine the species, particularly *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris*, known for their implications in urinary tract infections and other infections. Here are details about the necessary materials and the identification method commonly used in the laboratory.

Necessary materials

Culture media:

- **MacConkey Agar:** This is a selective and differential medium used to isolate Gram-negative bacteria. *Proteus* grows on this medium without fermenting lactose, resulting in colorless colonies.
- **Blood Agar:** This medium is used to observe growth patterns and swarming motility, a characteristic of *Proteus mirabilis*.
- **TSI Agar (Triple Sugar Iron):** This medium allows for the observation of hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) production, gas formation, and sugar fermentation (glucose).
- **Urea Medium:** This is essential for detecting the production of the urease enzyme, which is a specific marker for *Proteus*.

☒ Biochemical reagents:

- **Reagents for the urease test:** Indicate the presence of the urease enzyme by changing the color of the medium (usually to pink) due to the alkalization caused by the breakdown of urea.
- **Reagents for the indole test:** Used to differentiate *Proteus mirabilis* (indole-negative) from *Proteus vulgaris* (indole-positive).

☒ Automated systems:

- **VITEK system:** An automated bacterial identification and antibiogram system used in laboratories to confirm identifications.
- **MALDI-TOF (Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry):** A modern technology for the rapid identification of bacteria based on the specific protein spectral pattern of each bacterial species.

☒ General equipment:

- Test tubes and a bacterial loop for inoculation.
- An incubator set to 35-37°C.
- Microscopic examination lamps.

Identification Method

1. **Sample Collection and Inoculation:**
 - The clinical sample, in this case, urine, is collected using aseptic techniques and inoculated onto selective culture media, such as MacConkey agar and blood agar, using a bacterial loop to evenly

distribute the sample across the surface of the medium.

- The plates are incubated at 35-37°C for 18-24 hours.

2. Observation of Colonies:

- After incubation, the plates are checked for the presence of characteristic *Proteus* colonies. These colonies display a distinct “swarming” appearance on blood agar and appear colorless on MacConkey agar (as they do not ferment lactose).
- Colonies with a swarming pattern and a pungent odor (characteristic of *Proteus mirabilis*) are suspected to belong to the *Proteus* genus.

☒ Biochemical Tests:

- **Urease Test:** A sample from the colony is inoculated into a urea medium and incubated for 4-6 hours. *Proteus* will produce a positive reaction (typically a color change of the medium to pink) due to urease production.
- **TSI Test:** The colony is inoculated into a test tube with TSI medium and incubated for 18-24 hours. The appearance of H₂S (which darkens the medium), gas formation, and glucose fermentation indicate the presence of *Proteus*.
- **Indole Test:** This test differentiates *Proteus mirabilis* (indole-negative) from *Proteus vulgaris* (indole-positive). The reagent is added after incubation, and a color change indicates a positive result.

☒ Antibiotic Sensitivity Test:

- After identification, an antibiogram is performed to determine the sensitivity of *Proteus* to various antibiotics. This step is essential for guiding appropriate treatment of the infection, as certain strains may exhibit antibiotic resistance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Proteus mirabilis and *Proteus vulgaris* are two important species within the genus *Proteus*, recognized as pathogenic agents in urinary tract infections. These bacteria have distinctive morphological, cultural, and biochemical characteristics that facilitate their identification in the laboratory.

In our study, both species, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris*, were found to be gram-negative, rod-shaped bacteria, measuring approximately 1-3 μm in length and 0.5-0.8 μm in width. The bacteria are highly motile due to the presence of numerous peritrichous flagella that are evenly distributed over the entire surface of the cell.

Both species are gram-negative and stain pink during Gram staining due to their thin peptidoglycan cell wall. Microscopic examination reveals them as pink-stained bacilli, either appearing individually or in irregular clusters.

It was noted that *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris* grow well on standard bacterial culture media, such as nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, and blood agar. On solid media, such as blood agar and nutrient agar, both species exhibit swarming phenomena (collective movement), characterized by the formation of concentric rings resulting from the migration of bacterial cells.

On MacConkey agar, the colonies are non-lactose fermenters, appearing colorless or pale yellow. On blood agar, *Proteus* colonies may produce partial hemolysis, sometimes giving a transparent appearance around the colonies.

Regarding CLED medium, this medium is frequently used for the culture of bacteria from urine. In the case of *Proteus*, CLED prevents swarming, allowing the formation of isolated, round, and opaque colonies.

Fig.1. A) *Proteus mirabilis* culture in chromogenic medium giving rise to cream-colored colonies under a brown halo without swarming. (B) Growth translucent blue colonies in CLED medium. (C) Swarming phenomenon on blood agar. Yellow arrows indicate line of dienes. (D) Rapid urease reaction after 2 h causing a color change by the phenol indicator from yellow (pH: 6.6) to red (pH:8).

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364423898/The_Brief_Case_Proteus_mirabilis_Causing_Coralliform_Lithiasis_and_Bacteremia_in_an_Elderly_Catheterized_Patient/figures?lo=1

Proteus mirabilis and *Proteus vulgaris* have similar biochemical profiles but also some important differences that help differentiate the two species.

Common biochemical tests that we conducted for both species include the urease test, where it was found that both species are urease-positive, producing the enzyme urease that breaks down urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide, leading to an increase in the pH of the medium.

The TSI (Triple Sugar Iron Agar) test revealed that both species ferment glucose, producing acid and gas. They also produce hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), which is visible by the black color of the medium due to the formation of ferrous sulfide precipitate.

We deduced that in the catalase test, both species are catalase-positive, releasing oxygen

upon the addition of hydrogen peroxide. Regarding oxidase, it was found that both are oxidase-negative, a test useful for differentiating them from other gram-negative bacteria.

Other specific biochemical tests used in the study for differentiation are indole and carbohydrate fermentation. *Proteus vulgaris* is indole-positive, producing indole from tryptophan, which results in a positive reaction in the presence of indole reagents, such as Kovac's or Ehrlich's, turning pink-red. *Proteus mirabilis* is indole-negative and does not produce indole.

In terms of carbohydrate fermentation, both species ferment glucose but do not ferment lactose or sucrose, which is evident on selective media like MacConkey.

Table No. 1: Summary of the Differences Between *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris*

Characteristic	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>
Indole Production	Indole- negative	Indole-positive
Urease Activity	Urease-positive	Urease-positive
Glucose Fermentation	Yes	Yes
Lactose Fermentation	No	No
Sucrose Fermentation	No	No
Catalase Test	Catalase-positive	Catalase-positive
Oxidase Test	Oxidase-negative	Oxidase-negative

In the medical journal of Microbiology, P. G. H. Peerbooms, A. M. J. J. Verweij, and D. M. MacLaren, in their work "Uropathogenic Properties of *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris*," highlighted that Krikler (1953) reported prevalences of 17% for *P. mirabilis* and 5% for *P. vulgaris* in the feces of healthy individuals. It is believed that urinary pathogens primarily originate from the intestine, and interestingly, *P. mirabilis* is disproportionately isolated more frequently from patients with urinary tract infections compared to *P. vulgaris*. For instance, Senior (1979) isolated 258 strains of *P. mirabilis* from infected urine, while only four strains of *P. vulgaris* were isolated, two of which were found alongside *P. mirabilis*. This epidemiological data suggests that *P. mirabilis* is

CONCLUSIONS

Regarding the results reported for *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris*, it was found that they are gram-negative, rod-shaped bacteria. *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris* grow well on common bacterial culture media, such as nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, and blood agar.

On solid media, such as blood agar and nutrient agar, both species exhibit the phenomenon of swarming, characterized by concentric rings that appear from the migration of bacterial cells. The TSI test highlighted that both species ferment glucose, producing acid and gas.

more likely to cause urinary tract infections than *P. vulgaris*.

Since both species are genetically and biochemically very similar (Brenner et al., 1978), a comparative study of isolates from both species could provide valuable insights into the bacterial properties important in the pathogenesis of urinary tract infections. Therefore, they compared isolates from fecal samples of both species, taken from the same population, concerning several properties: experimental virulence in a mouse model, growth rates in urine and liquid media, production of hemolysins, hydrophobicity, sensitivity

It was deduced that, in the catalase test, both species are catalase-positive, releasing oxygen upon the addition of hydrogen peroxide. In terms of oxidase, both were found to be oxidase-negative, a useful test to differentiate them from other gram-negative bacteria.

Proteus vulgaris is indole-positive, producing indole from tryptophan, which results in a positive reaction in the presence of indole reagents, such as Kovac's or Ehrlich's, turning pink-red. *Proteus mirabilis* is indole-negative and does not produce indole.

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THE HIGHLIGHTING OF M-TYPE COLONIES FOR KLEBSIELLA

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REVIEW, RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Klebsiella is a genus of gram-negative bacteria that belongs to the Enterobacteriaceae family. These bacteria are known for their ability to form colonies, which refers to the grouping of bacteria that grow together on a culture medium. *Klebsiella* colonies are often large, swollen, and have smooth edges. They may have a mucoid texture due to the production of a polysaccharide capsule, giving them a gelatinous appearance. The color of the colonies can vary, but they are often colorless or whitish in hue. *Klebsiella* grows well on standard culture media, such as MacConkey agar, where it can form pink colonies due to lactose fermentation. This characteristic is an important indicator for identifying bacteria from this genus. There are several species of *Klebsiella*, with the most common being *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Klebsiella oxytoca*. Each species may exhibit variations in colony characteristics. *Klebsiella* can also be isolated on selective media that contain antibiotics to help identify resistant strains. These media allow for the observation of colonies capable of surviving under stress conditions.

Keywords: gram-negative bacteria, culture medium, polysaccharide capsule

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Klebsiella* comprises short, immobile, gram-negative bacilli with rounded ends, often arranged in pairs in the lengthwise direction. Out of the 10 species in this genus, 4 are significant in human pathology: *K. pneumoniae*, *K. oxytoca*, *K. ozenae*, and *K. rhinoscleromatis*. These bacteria are opportunistic pathogens and components of the intestinal flora in humans and animals, and they can also be found in small numbers on the mucous membranes of the respiratory tract. They can be isolated from water, soil, and plants.

K. pneumoniae is the most frequently isolated species within the genus. In cases of decreased immune resistance (in premature infants and the elderly), *Klebsiella* can cause severe infections, including pneumonia, septicemia, and meningitis. It is an important etiological agent of nosocomial infections (such as surgical wound infections, urinary tract infections, and septicemia). Nosocomial outbreaks with antibiotic-resistant strains have been reported, especially in neonatal units. Its etiological role in diarrheal diseases is debated. *K. oxytoca* produces similar infections.

The species *K. rhinoscleromatis* and *K. ozenae* are pathogenic only to humans, causing chronic rhinitis, more common in tropical regions. *K. rhinoscleromatis* is associated with rhinoscleroma—a hypertrophic chronic rhinitis with granulomatous lesions. *K. ozenae* causes ozena—a chronic inflammatory condition

characterized by mucosal suppuration and a foul odor, accompanied by atrophy of the nasal mucosa, which can lead to a loss of the sense of smell.

Other, less frequently isolated species include *K. ornithinolytica* and *K. planticola*, which have been found in urine, respiratory secretions, and blood in humans.

Klebsiella is an opportunistic pathogen that can cause severe infections, particularly in patients with compromised immune systems. *Klebsiella* colonies can be found in various types of infections, including urinary tract infections, where they can be identified in urine samples.

Studying *Klebsiella* colonies is essential for diagnosing bacterial infections and understanding the pathogenicity of these bacteria. Identifying and characterizing these colonies aids in developing more effective treatment strategies, especially in the context of increasing antibiotic resistance.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I conducted a prospective study based on microbiological diagnoses recorded in the bacteriological registry of the medical analysis laboratory, S.C. Diaser, Oradea. To conduct the study, I also accessed the archive, recorded in the laboratory's computer program in S.C. Diaser, Oradea, as well as the computerized database of the unit.

The identification of bacteria from the genus *Klebsiella* is performed through a series of laboratory methods that include culture

techniques, biochemical testing, and, in some cases, molecular methods. Here is a detailed guide to the materials and methods used in the identification of *Klebsiella*:

Necessary Materials

1. **Culture Media:**
 - **MacConkey Agar:** A selective medium for gram-negative bacteria that contains lactose, allowing for the identification of lactose-fermenting strains (colonies will appear pink).
 - **Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) Agar:** Differentiates fermenting bacteria, with *Klebsiella* colonies displaying a metallic sheen.
 - **Bile Esculin Agar:** Used to identify strains resistant to bile salts.
2. **Reagents for Biochemical Tests:**
 - Reagents for fermentation tests (e.g., sugar fermentation media – glucose, lactose).
 - Reagents for oxidase tests: To check the bacteria's ability to produce the enzyme oxidase.
 - Reagents for catalase tests: Used to determine catalase production (bubbles of oxygen in the presence of hydrogen peroxide).
 - Reagents for the IMViC test (Indole, Methyl Red, Voges-Proskauer, Citrate).
3. **Laboratory Equipment:**
 - **Incubator:** To maintain the optimal growth temperature (37 °C).
 - **Sterile Workbench:** To prevent contamination of samples.
 - **Pipettes and Test Tubes:** For handling samples and reagents.
 - **Microscope:** For examining the morphology of bacteria.
4. **Control Cultures:** Standard *Klebsiella* strains (e.g., *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC) for comparing results.

Identification Methods

1. **Bacterial Culture:**
 - **Sample Collection:** Samples can include urine, sputum, exudates, or other types of clinical specimens.
 - **Culture Maintenance:** The samples are inoculated onto

appropriate culture media (e.g., MacConkey agar) and incubated for 24-48 hours at 37 °C.

2. **Colony Observation:**
 - After incubation, colonies are observed. *Klebsiella* colonies are typically large, mucoid, and pink on MacConkey agar.
3. **Biochemical Tests:**
 - **Oxidase Test:** *Klebsiella* is oxidase negative.
 - **Catalase Test:** Hydrogen peroxide is added to a colony; bubble formation indicates the presence of the enzyme.
 - **Sugar Fermentation Tests:** Media containing various sugars (glucose, lactose) are inoculated to observe fermentation and acid production (indicated by a color change).
 - **IMViC Test:** Determination of indole, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, and citrate utilization, which helps differentiate species within the *Enterobacteriaceae* family.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The identification and characterization of bacteria from the genus *Klebsiella* are essential in the context of infectious pathology, as these bacteria are known to be opportunistic pathogens. In this section, we will discuss the typical results obtained from laboratory tests, as well as the implications of these results.

From normally sterile or minimally contaminated products, such as sputum, the Gram-stained smear can guide the diagnosis. The presence of polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMNs) and short, gram-negative bacilli, stained bipolar, encapsulated, arranged in diplococci in the lengthwise direction or in short chains, indicates with high probability an infection with *Klebsiella*.

In the study, as the bacteria multiplied, the broth became turbid due to bacterial growth. This turbidity is an indicator of bacterial activity in the medium. After allowing the broth to sit, sediment appeared at the bottom of the container, representing dead bacteria or aggregates of bacterial cells.

In some cases, a pellicle may form on the surface of the broth. This can be the result of biofilm formation by the bacteria colonizing the surface of the liquid. A characteristic odor

associated with some strains of *Klebsiella* was also noted, typically described as having a sweet

or fermented smell due to the metabolism of organic substances.

Fig. 1. *Klebsiella* spp., M-type colonies on blood agar culture medium.

<https://microbiologie.umfst.ro/atlas/bacteriologie/bactsp/klebsiella.php>

Fig. 2. *Klebsiella* spp., M-type colonies on lactose agar culture medium, lactose positive.

<https://microbiologie.umfst.ro/atlas/bacteriologie/bactsp/klebsiella.php>

On MacConkey agar, *Klebsiella* colonies typically appear large, mucoid, and pink, indicating lactose fermentation. This suggests that the isolated bacteria are likely lactose-fermenting species, such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The oxidase test result is negative, confirming that the isolates belong to the Enterobacteriaceae family, including the *Klebsiella* genus. Conversely, the catalase test is positive,

indicating the bacteria's ability to break down hydrogen peroxide. Most strains fermented lactose and glucose, producing acid, while *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains were indole-negative. The results of biochemical tests affirmed that most isolates are *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, commonly associated with nosocomial infections.

Fig.3. *Klebsiella spp.*, TSI: G+, L+, Z+
SIM: H₂S-, I variabil, M-, Uree: +, Simmons: +

Fig.4. *Klebsiella spp.*, TSI: G+, L+, Z+,
SIM: H₂S-, I variabil, M-, Uree: + Simmons: +

<https://microbiologie.umfst.ro/atlas/bacteriologie/bactsp/klebsiella.php>

Klebsiella pneumoniae is recognized as a major pathogen in urinary tract infections, pneumonia, and intra-abdominal infections. Antibiotic resistance is a significant concern, with many strains resistant to beta-lactams, complicating treatment. Continuous monitoring of resistance profiles is essential for guiding clinical treatments and preventing the spread of resistant strains. The study highlights the

importance of accurately identifying *Klebsiella* species due to their public health impact. Additionally, several virulence factors have been identified, including a prominent polysaccharide capsule and fimbrial adhesins that aid in host cell adherence.

CONCLUSIONS

In broth culture, turbidity indicated bacterial growth. On MacConkey agar, *Klebsiella* colonies typically appeared large, mucoid, and pink, suggesting lactose fermentation, likely indicating the presence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The oxidase test was negative, confirming the isolates belong to the Enterobacteriaceae family. The catalase test was positive, indicating the bacteria's ability to break down hydrogen peroxide. Citrate was negative, as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* does not utilize citrate as its sole carbon source.

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THE EFFECTS OF YEAST AND LACTIC BACILLI IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENZYMES AND THEIR RESULTS FOR THE GENERATION OF AMINO ACIDS IN DOUGH, A FACTOR THAT INFLUENCES THE AROMA OF BREAD

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REVIEW, RESEARCH ARTICLE (REVIEW ARTICLE)

Abstract

It was determined the release of amino acids in the dough obtained from wheat flour, water, salt, yeast and dough prepared from the same ingredients, but which were inoculated with lactic acidophilic bacteria. Following the proteolytic activity, the released amino acids were constant in both situations, although the yeasts presented a high demand for amino acids, and their concentration was not significantly affected by the activity of lactic bacilli. The content of amino acids was influenced by the pH during the period of fermentation and microbial metabolism. Proline formation was favored by values higher than pH 5.5, while the release of phenylalanine, leucine and cysteine occurred mainly at lower pH. In order to determine the effects of the amino acid concentration on the bread aroma, the fermented doughs were subjected to the baking test. Following the assessment, it was observed that the most pronounced aromas were obtained when baking the dough inoculated with lactic acid bacteria. These results support the hypothesis that the aroma of the bread is improved by increasing the concentration of free amino acids as a result of the activity of lactic bacilli in the dough.

Keywords: fermentation, lactic bacilli, aroma.

INTRODUCTION

The bread is prepared from practically tasteless ingredients, flour, water, salt and yeast. Almost all the aromatic active components are formed during the fermentation of the dough and baking. Increased amounts of free amino acids in the dough can improve the flavor of the bread. By stimulating proteolysis by adding lactic bacteria, during the fermentation period the sensory properties characteristic of bread are considerably improved compared to doughs obtained only with the addition of yeast and chemically acidulated. The aim of this work was to determine the contribution of flour obtained from wheat and microbial enzymes to the proteolytic release of amino acids during dough fermentation, as well as the relevance for the sensory attributes of bread. The effect of acidification and reduction was compared with proteolysis agents in doughs that were not inoculated and doughs fermented with different initial lactic cultures. The relevance of the levels of amino acids in the dough for the aroma of the bread was determined by the sensory analysis of the bread.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The wheat flour used was from a local mill, having a moisture content of 13.9%, wet gluten of 32% and an ash content of 0.55%.

The initial cultures were obtained by thermostating them for 12 hours at a temperature of 35 degrees Celsius. Cultures and flour were prepared with an addition of 400% water, after which they were placed in 50ml glasses and left to incubate at a temperature of 30 degrees Celsius. Samples were taken at appropriate intervals to determine the number of viable cells, the pH level, the concentration of organic acids in the suspension, ethanol and amino acids. The absence of contaminants in the suspension fermentation was verified by determining the colony, morphology and microscopy of the colonies selected to determine the cell morphology. Fiecare fermentatie a fost efectuata in dublu exemplar. The baking test was made by obtaining a dough from 720g of flour, 120ml of suspension, 300ml of water, 40g of coarse non-iodized salt. The control sample was obtained by replacing the suspension with 120 gr of Pakmaya compressed yeast. The dough was kneaded with a Heiner planetary mixer at low speed for 2 minutes and at high speed for 4 minutes. After obtaining the dough, they were placed in molds and were thermostated for 35 minutes at a relative humidity of 80%. After fermentation, the samples were baked at a

temperature of 235 degrees for 20 minutes. After baking, the samples were taken out of the molds, left to cool for an hour, after which they were subjected to a sensory analysis made up of a team of 5 analysts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The release of total amino nitrogen is related to the growth and metabolism of microorganisms. In all yeast-fermented doughs, the lowest amounts of amino acids were detected in the multiplication and growth phase, and the highest in the stagnation period due to the oversaturation and increase in the acidity of the dough. A comparison of doughs fermented by inoculation with cultures of lactic bacilli with those obtained by fermentation with the help of yeast allows us to estimate the contribution of microbial proteases to proteolysis in the dough. Fermentation of the dough with yeast led to the decrease of free amino acids due to the microbial metabolism, and following the conversion of these metabolic products in the dough (leucine and phenylalanine) aromatic volatile products are obtained. Enhanced proteolysis during dough fermentation is in agreement with previous reports on amino acid evolution. Lactic bacteria require amino acids or peptides for growth, and after metabolism, volatile substances are obtained that contribute to the impregnation of the bread with an aroma.

CONCLUSIONS

The most important flavor elements are obtained during baking during the formation of the crust or crust of the bread. These, by combining with the volatile substances that are formed during fermentation, can intensify the organoleptic qualities of the bread. In the case of doughs fermented with the help of lactic bacteria, the volatile substances that remain in the bread are in larger quantities compared to those obtained by fermentation with yeast, where the concentration of ethyl alcohol is higher, but during baking it is almost completely eliminated. However, tasters preferred the bread obtained with yeast due to the texture of the core and the taste. The difference in taste can be attributed to the fact that the acidity of the dough in the bread made with the help of fermentation with lactic

bacteria is significantly higher, which after baking can contribute to the differences in the taste of the bread core. In addition, the porosity of the bread core and the volume were much lower in the bread obtained with lactic acid bacteria because the amount of carbon dioxide resulting from fermentation is much lower in this case.

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THE EFFECT OF FERTILIZERS WITH NPK ON COPPER CONCENTRATION IN THE PRELUVOSOIL FROM ORADEA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The research was carried out over a period of three years (2020 - 2022) in a long-term experience with chemical fertilizers, located on a preluvosoil type soil in the North-West part of Romania. Following the application over a long period of different doses of chemical fertilizers with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, it was observed that the concentration of copper in the soil did not have high values compared to the alert point (100 mg/kg). The concentration of copper in the soil increased with the increase in the doses of fertilizers, the differences being in some cases statistically significant. The values obtained were between 21.9% and 28.9% compared to it.

Keywords: copper, concentration, preluvosoil, chemical fertilizers

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INTRODUCTION

Naturally, the concentration of copper in soils around the globe is between 1 and 300 mg/kg, with an average concentration of 22.4 mg/kg. The soils in the Warsaw area had a copper concentration between 1-560 mg/kg (Lis J., 1992), and McGrath S.P. and Loveland P.J., (1992) determined in Great Britain concentrations between 1.2 and 1.508 mg Cu/kg. The average concentration of copper in European soils was 13 mg/kg (Salminen R. et al., 2005).

In the contaminated and polluted areas in Romania, especially in the soils adjacent to the non-ferrous ore processing units, the determined copper concentration was 2.000 - 3.000 mg/kg (Lăcățusu R., 2008).

The maximum allowed limit, in our country, for the concentration of copper in the soil is 20 mg/kg, the alert threshold 100 mg/kg, in the case of sensitive soils and 250 mg/kg in the case of the least sensitive ones, respectively the intervention threshold of was set at 200 mg/kg for sensitive soils and 500 mg/kg for less sensitive soils (Order no. 756/1997 of the Ministry of Water, of Forests and Environmental Protection).

The ability of different types of soil to retain and neutralize heavy metals, as well as their vulnerability to different types of polluting

elements, is an important premise in their effective management.

Metals, and especially heavy metals, can be carried through precipitation into the lower layers of the soil, from where they reach plants - animals - humans through bioaccumulation. For these reasons, it was necessary to establish some critical loads of metals whose concentrations should not be exceeded, so that there is no risk of soil transformation into a potential supplier of environmental pollutants.

In Romania, five classes of vulnerability were established (very low, low, moderate, high, very high) and depending on the reaction state of the soil solution, in three subclasses: moderately and strongly acid, weakly acid and neutral, alkaline (Florea N. and Ianoș Gh., 2002).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Wet mineralization was performed with concentrated strong acids and hydrogen peroxide (HNO₃, HCl and H₂O₂) using the MILESTONE digester.

The dry sample is extracted with a mixture of hydrochloric acid/nitric acid and perhydrol by keeping it for 2 h in a microwave oven at a previously established mineralization program. The extract is then filtered and brought to volume with distilled water.

1.00±0.1 g of soil was weighed into MILESTONE microwave mineralization vials over which an oxidizing mixture was added: 6 ml of concentrated nitric acid, 3 ml of hydrochloric acid and 0.25 ml of perhydrol. The vials were sealed and the mineralization program was started (the digestion program also includes a ventilation of the samples to cool them down for 30 minutes). After completion of the program, the samples were kept overnight in the digestion vessels covered with a filter paper to avoid contamination. Then, the samples were filtered in 50 ml volumetric flasks and brought to the mark with water.

At each series of analyses, extractions were performed for the control, using the same procedure, but without the soil sample.

To determine the heavy metals under study, the soil samples, plant biological material, respectively animal biological material prepared according to the work methods presented previously were subjected to analysis by means of the SHIMADZU AA-6300 atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

The schema of the long term trial with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium

1	1	1	9	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	4	6	7	5	8	R
1	0	2		3	5	6	4									4
1	1	1	1	3	2	1	4	8	7	5	6	1	1	9	1	R
4	6	3	5									2	1	0	3	
6	5	7	8	1	1	1	9	1	1	1	1	3	4	2	1	R
				0	1	2		6	3	5	4					2
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	R
									0	1	2	3	4	5	6	1

1. N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	5. N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₀	9. N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₀	13. N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₀
2. N ₀ P ₀ K ₄₀	6. N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀	10. N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₄₀	14. N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₄₀
3. N ₀ P ₀ K ₈₀	7. N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₈₀	11. N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀	15. N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀
4. N ₀ P ₀ K ₁₂₀	8. N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₁₂₀	12. N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₁₂₀	16. N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₁₂₀

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the three years studied (2020-2022), the lowest copper concentration was recorded in the control version (N₀P₀K₀), 21.938 mg/kg in 2020, 22.262 mg/kg in 2021, respectively 22.792 mg/kg in 2022. The concentration of copper increased by 3.3% in 2020, 3.4% in 2021, respectively by 3.7% in 2022, the differences not being statistically ensured, within the N₈₀P₄₀K₄₀ variant. In the N₈₀P₈₀K₈₀ variant, the differences recorded were greater than those in the control variant by 9.4% (23.998 mg/kg) in 2020, 10.9% (24.679 mg/kg) in 2021 and 11.2% (25.339 mg/kg) in 2022. The difference recorded in 2020 was statistically insignificant, and the differences

from the years 2021 and 2022 were statistically significant. In the version fertilized with N₁₆₀P₈₀K₁₂₀, the biggest differences were recorded compared to the unfertilized version, these registering values of 27.474 mg/kg in 2020, 27.943 mg/kg, respectively 28.882 mg/kg, higher by 25.2%, 25.5%, respectively 26.7%, being distinctly significant. (Table 1.)

In the experiment with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilizers, the concentration of copper in the soil did not exceed the alert threshold (100 mg/kg), established by the Order of the Ministry of Water, Forests and Environmental Protection no. 756/1997. The concentration of copper in the N₀P₀K₀ variant (control) represents 21.9% in 2020, 22.3% in 2021, respectively 28.9% in 2022, of the alert threshold value. In the version fertilized with N₈₀P₄₀K₄₀, copper recorded concentrations of 22.6% in 2020, 23% in 2021 and 23.6% in 2022 relative to the alert threshold value. In the N₈₀P₈₀K₈₀ variant, the copper concentration recorded 24% in 2020, 24.7% in 2021, respectively 25.3% in 2022 of the alert threshold value. In the N₁₆₀P₈₀K₁₂₀ variant, compared to the alert threshold, the copper concentration had values of 27.5% in 2020, 27.9% in 2021, respectively 28.9% in 2022. (Figure 1.)

On average over the three years studied, in the N₀P₀K₀ variant the concentration of copper in the preluvosol from Oradea was 22.330 mg/kg. and in the other variants the concentrations were higher by 3.5% in the N₈₀P₄₀K₄₀ variant. 10.5% in variant N₈₀P₈₀K₈₀, respectively 25.8 mg/kg in the variant N₁₆₀P₈₀K₁₂₀. Reaching values of 23.105 mg/kg. 24.672 mg/kg. respectively 28.099 mg/kg. In the N₈₀P₄₀K₄₀ variant. the recorded difference was not statistically ensured. In the N₈₀P₄₀K₄₀ variant it was statistically significant, respectively in the N₁₆₀P₈₀K₁₂₀ variant it was distinctly significant. (Table 2.)

Among the 5 types of functions tested (exponential, linear, logarithmic, polynomial, power), the polynomial function best quantifies the relationship between the doses of chemical fertilizers and the concentration of copper in the soil, R² = 0.9612. (Figure 2.)

Table 1

The influence of doses and combinations of NPK fertilizers on copper concentration in preluvosoil from long term trial

Variant	Cu concentration		Difference		Statistical significance
	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	
2020					
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	21.938	100	-	-	Control
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀	22.659	103.3	0.721	3.3	-
N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀	23.998	109.4	2.071	9.4	-
N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₁₂₀	27.474	125.2	5.536	25.2	**
	LSD 5%		2.202		
	LSD 1%		3.900		
	LSD 0.1%		6.410		
2021					
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	22.262	100	-	-	Control
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀	23.021	103.4	0.759	3.4	-
N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀	24.679	110.9	2.417	10.9	*
N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₁₂₀	27.943	125.5	5.681	25.5	**
	LSD 5%		2.310		
	LSD 1%		4.122		
	LSD 0.1%		7.233		
2022					
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	22.792	100	-	-	Control
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀	23.635	103.7	0.843	3.7	-
N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀	25.339	111.2	2.547	11.2	*
N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₁₂₀	28.882	126.7	6.090	26.7	**
	LSD 5%		1.970		
	LSD 1%		3.122		
	LSD 0.1%		6.321		

Figure 1 Graphical representation of copper values in soil based on doses and combinations of NPK fertilizer compared to the alert point

Table 2

The influence of doses and combinations of NPK fertilizers on copper concentration in preluvosoil from long term trial, average data, (2020-2022)

Variant	Cu concentration		Difference		Statistical significance
	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	22.330	100	-	-	Control
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀	23.105	103.5	0.775	3.5	-
N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₈₀	24.672	110.5	2.342	10.5	*
N ₁₆₀ P ₈₀ K ₁₂₀	28.099	125.8	5.769	25.8	**
	LSD 5%		2.161		
	LSD 1%		3.714		
	LSD 0.1%		6.655		

Figure 2 Correlation between doses of NPK fertilizers and copper concentration in soil

CONCLUSIONS

On average over the three years studied, compared to the non-fertilized control, the copper concentration of the soil in the studied variants is increased. In the control variants, the copper concentration had an average value of 22.330 mg/kg. The highest increase in the average concentration of copper in the soil, 5,769 mg/kg, was determined following fertilization with 160 kg of nitrogen, 80 kg of phosphorus and 120 kg of potassium. In the case of the other variants analyzed, the increases were not significant.

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THE ROLE OF VETERINARIANS IN ONE HEALTH PREPAREDNESS: STRENGTHENING SURVEILLANCE AND RESPONSE FOR EMERGING INFECTIOUS DISEASES

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REVIEW

Abstract

The concept of global health security has gained popularity in recent years, especially in light of rising infectious illnesses and the COVID-19 pandemic. This study investigates the multiple character of global health security, emphasising the need for a holistic approach that brings together many areas such as public health, veterinary medicine, and environmental research. The One Health framework emerges as a fundamental paradigm, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration to effectively manage zoonotic illnesses and improve preparedness and response strategies. Institutional barriers, communication gaps, and resource constraints are major challenges in implementing this integrated strategy, preventing veterinarians and other health professionals from participating fully. The paper also explores the importance of global health diplomacy in adjusting interventions to local settings, hence increasing the acceptance and effectiveness of health programs. Finally, the findings highlight the importance of a coordinated global response to health risks, recognising that health-care system security is inextricably related to the well-being of communities around the world.

Keywords: One Health, Emerging Infectious Diseases, Veterinary Surveillance

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INTRODUCTION

The One Health concept embodies a comprehensive approach to health that acknowledges the interrelation of human, animal, and environmental health. This paradigm has garnered considerable attention in recent years, especially due to the rising incidence of zoonotic emerging infectious diseases (EIDs) and the pressing necessity for unified global health security initiatives. A collaborative, interdisciplinary approach that integrates knowledge and practices from various sectors, including public health, veterinary medicine, and environmental science, is necessary to effectively address health issues, as the One Health framework emphasises (Destoumieux-Garzón et al., 2018; Kariotis et al., 2022; Couto & Brandespim, 2020). The increase in zoonotic emerging infectious diseases, like COVID-19, Ebola, and Zika virus, has highlighted the essential significance of the One Health strategy. Approximately 60% of infectious diseases in humans are of zoonotic origin, and around

75% of new infectious diseases are likewise zoonotic (Horefti, 2023; Shaheen, 2022). This concerning trend requires a transformation in health system operations, transitioning from isolated practices to a more cohesive model that recognises the intricate interconnections among human, animal, and environmental health (Sleeman et al., 2017; Ryu et al., 2017).

The One Health strategy attempts to prevent and control zoonotic diseases while addressing broader health determinants, including socio-economic variables and environmental changes (Înci et al., 2018; Couto & Brandespim, 2020; Stenvinkel, 2020). The necessity for synchronised vigilance against zoonotic emerging infectious diseases is heightened by globalisation, climate change, and augmented human-animal interactions. The aforementioned elements facilitate the establishment and dissemination of infectious diseases, necessitating health systems to embrace a One Health approach (Sleeman et al., 2017; Couto & Brandespim, 2020; Cleaveland et al., 2017).

Environmental degradation and climate change might modify wildlife habitats, resulting in heightened interactions between

humans and potential zoonotic reservoirs (İnci et al., 2018; Couto & Brandespim, 2020; Gheorghe-Irimia, 2023, Şonea, 2023a, Şonea, 2023b, Tudor, 2023). This dynamic highlights the imperative of incorporating environmental health factors into public health policies to reduce the risks linked to zoonotic infections (Horefti, 2023; Stenvinkel, 2020). Furthermore, the One Health structure promotes interdisciplinary collaboration, which is crucial for efficient disease surveillance and response. One Health initiatives can improve the ability to detect and respond to zoonotic disease outbreaks by cultivating partnerships among diverse stakeholders, including governments, non-governmental organisations, and local communities (Vesterinen et al., 2019; Couto & Brandespim, 2020; Tidman et al., 2022). The partnership among the World Health Organisation (WHO), the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), and the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) has been crucial in advancing the One Health strategy worldwide (Kariotis et al., 2022; Pitt, 2024). This tripartite collaboration demonstrates that integrated efforts can yield more effective health interventions and enhance results for both human and animal populations (Kariotis et al., 2022; Couto & Brandespim, 2020).

Education and training are essential elements of the One Health framework. As the concept develops, there is an increasing acknowledgement of the necessity to integrate One Health principles into the educational curricula for health professionals (Xie et al., 2017; Rabinowitz et al., 2017). By imparting knowledge and skills regarding the interrelations among human, animal, and environmental health to future healthcare providers, we can cultivate a new generation of practitioners adept at tackling the intricate health challenges of the 21st century (Xie et al., 2017; Rabinowitz et al., 2017). This educational transition is essential for fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and improving the overall efficacy of health interventions (Barrett et al., 2010; Ryu et al., 2017). The One Health strategy, with education, underscores the significance of community involvement in tackling zoonotic illnesses. Local communities frequently serve a vital function in illness prevention and management, as they contain significant knowledge regarding their ecosystems and health behaviours (Hassan et al., 2017; Cleaveland et al., 2017). Involving

communities in One Health initiatives can enhance trust and promote collaboration between health authorities and the populations they serve, ultimately resulting in more effective health interventions (Cleaveland et al., 2017; Horefti, 2023). This participative method is especially crucial in low- and middle-income countries, where resources may be constrained, and community engagement is vital for achieving favourable health outcomes (Cleaveland et al., 2017; Horefti, 2023, Couto & Brandespim, 2020; Tidman et al., 2022).

Considering the aforementioned, this paper aims to examine the crucial role of veterinarians in One Health readiness, specifically regarding the surveillance and response to emerging infectious diseases (EIDs).

THE ROLE OF VETERINARIANS IN THE ONE HEALTH PREPAREDNESS

Early detection and surveillance

Veterinarians have an important role in the early detection and surveillance of zoonotic infections, which is critical for avoiding human spillover incidents. Identifying zoonotic infections in animals before they infect people is critical for minimising epidemics. According to Rodríguez-Prieto et al. (2014), veterinarians play an important role in monitoring animal populations for new infectious illnesses. Using both passive and active surveillance methods, veterinarians can detect pathogens early, as demonstrated by the successful detection of SARS-CoV-2 in mink populations in the Netherlands, where active surveillance identified infected farms before clinical signs appeared (Santman-Berends, 2024). This proactive strategy protects animal health while also lowering the potential of zoonotic transmission to humans. The incorporation of veterinarian data into One Health surveillance systems improves the overall effectiveness of disease monitoring. Veterinarians collaborate with public health officials and ecologists to better understand zoonotic disease epidemiology (Rodríguez-Prieto et al., 2014).

Establishing One Health networks with veterinarians, epidemiologists, and wildlife experts is crucial for enhancing early warning systems and coordinating response to future outbreaks (Rodríguez-Prieto et al., 2014). A thorough assessment of monitoring systems emphasises the necessity for interdisciplinary

collaboration to detect exotic and re-emerging illnesses in animal populations, preserving public health (Rodríguez-Prieto et al., 2014). Veterinary engagement in early warning systems has been successful in a number of global efforts. The Vietnam Initiative on Zoonotic Infections (VIZIONS) emphasises the necessity of early detection of zoonotic infections, especially those with the potential to infect humans (Rabaa et al., 2015). This initiative demonstrates how veterinarians may lead initiatives to monitor animal health and discover infections that pose a risk to human populations. Furthermore, improved diagnostic techniques, such as multiplex PCR assays, enable the simultaneous detection of numerous zoonotic infections in livestock, increasing the ability for early detection (Modise et al., 2023).

Disease Control and Risk Reduction

Implementing biosecurity controls in livestock and wildlife is another crucial area where veterinarians may help with One Health planning. Veterinarians contribute to public health by developing strategies to reduce the danger of pathogen transmission between animals and humans. For example, biosecurity measures on swine farms have been demonstrated to lower the probability of influenza virus transmission between farm personnel and pigs (Moraes et al., 2023). Veterinarians advise for preventing zoonotic illnesses through appropriate cleanliness, regulated access to animal housing, and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) (Jones et al., 2023; Verkola et al., 2021). Vaccination programs and antimicrobial management in animal populations are both critical components of disease prevention. Veterinarians are in charge of developing vaccination procedures that protect both animal and human health by limiting the spread of zoonotic illnesses (Moraes et al., 2023). For example, vaccinating animals against viruses like *Brucella* and *Leptospira* is critical to reducing zoonotic transmission to people (Modise et al., 2023). Furthermore, veterinarians play an important role in promoting responsible antibiotic use in veterinary medicine, which is required to battle the growing threat of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) ("Zoonoses and AMR: Silent Spreader of Superbug Pandemic", 2023). Veterinarians work to prevent the emergence

of resistant diseases that can harm both animals and humans by educating farmers and pet owners about the dangers of antibiotic misuse.

Veterinarians use community engagement and education to mitigate zoonotic hazards. By promoting understanding about zoonotic illnesses and their transmission pathways, they empower communities to take preventive actions (Moraes et al., 2023). For example, educational campaigns aimed at pet owners can educate them on the significance of regular veterinary check-ups and preventive care, which can greatly lower the incidence of zoonotic illnesses (Day, 2011). Furthermore, veterinarians frequently work with public health officials to perform outreach programs that teach people the value of cleanliness and biosecurity policies in reducing zoonotic disease transmission (Gado et al., 2023).

Response to Emerging Infectious Disease

In the event of an outbreak, veterinarians play a critical role in the investigation and control of developing infectious illnesses. Their knowledge of animal health enables them to accurately identify the source of epidemics and efficiently conduct control measures. For example, during avian influenza outbreaks, veterinarians played an important role in performing epidemiological studies to track the virus's progress and adopt containment tactics (Zumla et al., 2016; Shaheen, 2022). Their participation in epidemic response protects animal health while also preventing zoonotic transmission to humans. Cross-sector collaboration is critical for an effective response to EIDs, and veterinarians frequently engage with public health and environmental experts to manage outbreaks.

The One Health paradigm exemplifies this collaborative approach by emphasising the connection of human, animal, and environmental health (Zumla et al., 2016). For example, during the Rift Valley fever outbreaks, veterinarians worked with public health officials to monitor livestock populations and implement vaccination efforts that protected both animal and human health (Zumla et al., 2016; Shaheen, 2022). Such interdisciplinary activities are essential for providing a complete response to zoonotic disease outbreaks. Examples of veterinary participation in EID response efforts abound. The reaction to the

Ebola virus outbreak in West Africa highlighted the role of veterinarians in treating zoonotic illnesses that can spread to humans (Zumla et al., 2016). Similarly, continual surveillance of zoonotic pathogens in animals, as evidenced by studies on tick-borne diseases, highlights the need of veterinarians in early detection and response efforts (Egan et al., 2021; Omondi et al., 2017).

CURRENT CHALLENGES

Integrating veterinarians into One Health emergency planning involves a number of challenges and hurdles that must be addressed in order to maximise the effectiveness of this collaborative strategy. These challenges are caused by a variety of variables, including institutional silos, communication gaps, cultural differences, and limited resources. The presence of institutional and disciplinary divisions is a key obstacle to veterinarians' incorporation into One Health programs. Many health professionals, including veterinarians and physicians, frequently function in silos, resulting in a lack of collaboration and communication (Annand et al., 2020; Speare et al., 2015). This isolation may impede the timely sharing of vital data on zoonotic illnesses, which is required for effective disease surveillance and response (Annand et al., 2020). For example, in Australia, despite multiple health agencies' acceptance of One Health, effective interagency cooperation for zoonotic disease investigations is frequently limited unless a laboratory-confirmed diagnosis is available (Annand et al., 2020). This scenario demonstrates how institutional impediments can stymie the collaborative efforts required for successful One Health adoption. Cultural disparities between veterinary and human health workers further complicate integration efforts. Many veterinarians believe that they are expected to take the lead in One Health programs, yet many feel unprepared or unsupported in this role (Steele et al., 2019). The requirement for behavioural and cultural change among veterinarians and physicians is critical for optimal collaboration (Steele et al., 2019). Furthermore, veterinarians may face scepticism from medical colleagues about their expertise in zoonotic diseases, complicating interprofessional partnerships (Nunes et al., 2022). This lack of mutual respect and

understanding can foster a climate in which collaboration is not prioritised, so harming One Health efforts. Communication barriers between veterinarians and other health providers are another major impediment to efficient integration. Studies have indicated that communication between veterinarians and physicians is frequently inadequate, resulting in missed possibilities for collaboration in public health education and zoonotic disease control (Vale et al., 2021). For example, pet owners generally view veterinarians as trustworthy sources of information about zoonoses, but this confidence is not necessarily exploited in joint efforts with medical experts (Powell et al., 2022). Bridging these communication gaps is critical to ensure that veterinarians can effectively contribute to One Health programs while also having their knowledge recognised and utilised. Limited resources also make it difficult to integrate veterinarians into One Health preparedness. Many veterinarians work in environments where they lack access to the tools, training, and support required to participate effectively in One Health activities (Sawford et al., 2012). For example, in some areas, veterinarians may face logistical constraints such as limited transportation infrastructure, limiting their ability to engage in outbreak surveillance and response operations (Sawford et al., 2012). Furthermore, budgetary restrictions may limit veterinary practices' ability to invest in training and resources that foster partnership with public health authorities (Rabinowitz et al., 2013).

Addressing these resource constraints is crucial for allowing veterinarians to take a more active role in One Health programs. Finally, veterinarians' mental health and well-being can influence their ability to participate in One Health preparation.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, while veterinarians play an important role in One Health preparedness, various challenges and barriers must be addressed to allow their integration into this collaborative framework. Overcoming institutional barriers, cultural differences, communication gaps, and resource constraints will be critical to increasing the success of One Health efforts and ensuring that veterinarians can contribute significantly to global health security.

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ONE HEALTH SOLUTION FOR A SAFER PLATE: ADDRESSING CROSS-SPECIES PATHOGEN TRANSMISSION IN GLOBAL FOOD SYSTEMS

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REVIEW

Abstract

The spread of pathogens between species within global food systems presents a substantial challenge to food safety and public health, influenced by the interrelated aspects of human, animal, and environmental health. This review analyses the principal routes of pathogen transmission, including human-to-animal spillovers, animal-to-human infections, and environmental contamination. Additionally, the review emphasizes the significance of international collaboration, changes in legislation, and public education in ensuring a secure food supply. Implementing a One Health framework enables stakeholders to improve food safety, mitigate public health risks, and strengthen resilience against emerging threats in global food systems.

Keywords: foodborne pathogens, One Health, food safety, food security

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INTRODUCTION

The transmission of pathogens between species, commonly known as zoonotic transmission, poses a considerable challenge to global food safety and public health. This phenomenon takes place when pathogens transfer from animals to humans, occurring through multiple pathways such as direct contact, ingestion of contaminated food, or exposure to the environment. The consequences of this transmission are significant, potentially resulting in widespread outbreaks of foodborne illnesses that impact extensive populations. For example, pathogens like Salmonella and Campylobacter, commonly linked to animal products, account for millions of foodborne illnesses each year (Ejo et al., 2016; Abebe et al., 2020; Newell et al., 2010; Șonea, 2023a; Șonea, 2023b; Tudor, 2023; Gheorghe-Irimia, 2023). The intricate relationships among human, animal, and environmental health highlight the complexity of transmission dynamics, requiring a comprehensive approach to tackle the challenges presented by zoonotic diseases. The influence of pathogen transmission between species on food safety is complex and varied. It impacts not only the well-being of consumers

but also introduces economic challenges for the food sector and public health frameworks. Foodborne pathogens can infiltrate the food supply chain at multiple stages, from production to consumption, and can be intensified by elements such as substandard hygiene practices, insufficient food processing, and environmental contamination (Shin et al., 2016; Carstens et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2017). For instance, studies have found that contaminated raw meats, particularly poultry and beef, serve as major channels for Salmonella transmission, underscoring the necessity for rigorous food safety protocols across the food supply chain (Ejo et al., 2016; Bantawa et al., 2018; Heredia & García, 2018). Additionally, the rise of antibiotic-resistant strains of these pathogens introduces further complexity, complicating treatment options and heightening the severity of infections (Abebe et al., 2020; Nair et al., 2018). The interconnected nature of human, animal, and environmental health is presented in the One Health framework, which promotes a collaborative, multi-sectoral approach to address health challenges at the intersection of these domains. This framework acknowledges the interconnectedness of human, animal, and ecosystem health, highlighting that tackling health challenges in one domain can yield beneficial outcomes in others ("The European

Union One Health 2020 Zoonoses Report", 2021; Lahti et al., 2023). For example, zoonotic pathogens in livestock can have a direct effect on human health via foodborne diseases, and environmental factors like water quality and soil health can affect the prevalence of these pathogens in agricultural environments (Strawn et al., 2013; Gibb et al., 2020, Ayad et al., 2022; Nyachuba, 2010).

Additionally, improving food safety regulations and standards at the production level can reduce the risks linked to zoonotic pathogens, guaranteeing that food products are safe for consumption (Heredia & García, 2018; Newell et al., 2010; Ayad et al., 2022). The incorporation of modern technologies into food safety protocols represents a vital component of the One Health framework. Rapid detection methods for foodborne pathogens, including biosensors and molecular diagnostics, significantly improve the capacity to identify and respond to contamination events promptly (Yamada et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2014).

The aim of this review is to explore the critical issue of cross-species pathogen transmission within global food systems and to highlight the role of the One Health approach in mitigating these risks.

PATHOGEN TRANSMISSION ACROSS FOOD SYSTEMS

Human-to-Animal Pathogen Transmission

The transmission of pathogens from animals to humans, known as zoonotic spillovers, has been intensified by agricultural practices and food production systems. Intensive farming, marked by elevated animal density and restricted confinement, fosters conditions that promote the emergence and proliferation of zoonotic pathogens. The intensification of livestock farming has been associated with the emergence of diseases like Q fever, which is caused by *Coxiella burnetii* and is linked to regions with high livestock density (Smit et al., 2012; Freidl et al., 2017). The confined spaces in which animals are housed promote the spread of pathogens, affecting not only livestock but also humans, especially farm workers and those living nearby. Moreover, the ecological consequences of these methods, including the emission of pathogens into the atmosphere via ventilation systems, heighten the likelihood of zoonotic transmission to both wild and domestic animals (Jones et al., 2013). The misuse of antibiotics and intensive farming

practices significantly contribute to the amplification of pathogens due to human activities. The excessive use of antibiotics in livestock can result in the emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains of pathogens, presenting considerable threats to human health (Stevenson, 2023). The prevalence of Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) has been associated with intensive pig farming, where the close proximity of animals and the frequent use of antibiotics foster optimal conditions for the selection and dissemination of resistant strains (Kalupahana et al., 2019). Furthermore, the transportation of animals for commercial purposes or slaughter can promote the dissemination of these resistant pathogens across different areas, thereby complicating control measures (Murray et al., 2023).

Animal-to-Human Transmission

Pathogens are frequently transmitted to humans via the ingestion of contaminated food items, especially those sourced from livestock. For example, *Salmonella* ranks among the most common foodborne pathogens, causing millions of infections each year, with contaminated poultry and eggs identified as major sources (Zhai et al., 2018). In a similar vein, *Campylobacter*, frequently present in poultry, stands out as a primary contributor to bacterial gastroenteritis on a global scale (Zhai et al., 2018). The spread of these pathogens is frequently enabled by insufficient food processing and handling methods, which may result in cross-contamination during food preparation (Zhai et al., 2018). The transmission of zoonotic pathogens is significantly influenced by risk factors present in animal husbandry and food processing. Intensive farming practices, characterised by the confinement of animals in close proximity, heighten the risk of pathogen transmission among the animals and, consequently, to humans (Coker et al., 2011). Furthermore, inadequate biosecurity protocols on farms may result in the introduction and ongoing presence of pathogens among livestock populations (Coker et al., 2011; Espinosa et al., 2020, Heijne et al., 2018). Moreover, the transportation of livestock for commercial purposes or slaughter can promote the dissemination of pathogens between areas, hindering control measures and elevating the likelihood of outbreaks (Murray et al., 2023).

Environmental Transmission Pathways

The contamination of the environment through animal and human waste serves as a crucial route for the spread of zoonotic pathogens. The runoff from agricultural fields, especially those with intensive livestock operations, has the potential to introduce pathogens into water sources, soil, and crops (Jones et al., 2013; Sundberg et al., 2014). Contamination can arise through multiple mechanisms, including the use of manure as fertiliser, which may contain pathogens like *E. coli* and *Salmonella* (Jones et al., 2013; Sundberg et al., 2014). The existence of these pathogens in the environment presents a threat not just to agricultural output but also to public health, since contaminated water and crops can result in foodborne illnesses in humans (Jones et al., 2013; Sundberg et al., 2014). The significance of antimicrobial residues and resistant pathogens in environmental contamination is becoming increasingly acknowledged as a vital public health issue. Antibiotic use in livestock farming results in the excretion of antimicrobial residues into the environment, which contributes to the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria (Xiong et al., 2015). The persistence of these resistant pathogens in the environment presents significant risks to the health of both animals and humans (Xiong et al., 2015).

THE ROLE OF THE ONE HEALTH APPROACH

Integration Across Sectors

The One Health approach highlights the necessity of cooperation between human health, veterinary, and environmental sectors to address the intricate health issues that emerge at the convergence of these areas. This integration is essential for the effective management of zoonotic diseases, which frequently necessitate coordinated responses across various disciplines. The PREDICT project, initiated by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), serves as a prime example of a One Health initiative focused on monitoring potential spillovers of pathogenic viruses from animals to humans (Ajayi et al., 2021). This project has deepened our comprehension of viral evolution and showcased the effectiveness of interdisciplinary collaboration in mitigating future pandemics. Global initiatives have been established to address the challenges of food safety through a

comprehensive approach. For instance, the European Union has implemented a One Health framework that combines data from human health, animal health, and environmental monitoring to tackle foodborne pathogens (Zanet et al., 2022). This initiative has enabled the establishment of coordinated surveillance systems that allow for the identification and management of zoonotic diseases, thus enhancing food safety and public health results. Furthermore, the combination of veterinary and public health surveillance systems has demonstrated an ability to improve the identification of emerging pathogens.

Surveillance and Early Detection

The One Health approach encourages the development of comprehensive surveillance networks that include data from human, animal, and environmental health domains. The MediLabSecure project aims to improve pathogen detection and surveillance for arboviral infections by fostering a One Health collaboration, highlighting the necessity for integrated systems capable of addressing emerging infectious diseases (Mikaty et al., 2022). Coordinated efforts are essential for the early identification and swift action against potential health threats. The application of genomic tools and the exchange of data among various sectors play a vital role in the efficiency of surveillance systems. Genomic surveillance facilitates the identification of pathogen strains and their transmission pathways, offering important insights into disease dynamics (Gardy & Loman, 2017). The utilisation of high-throughput sequencing technologies has enhanced our capacity to monitor the dissemination of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, which is vital for public health initiatives (Bianconi, 2023). Moreover, combining genomic data with epidemiological insights can deepen our comprehension of pathogen evolution and enable prompt reactions to outbreaks (Vashisht, 2023). This genomic approach, guided by a comprehensive perspective, presents substantial potential for enhancing global health security.

Sustainable Agricultural Practices

Implementing strategies that emphasise environmental well-being allows farmers to reduce the threats posed by zoonotic diseases. For example, methods like crop rotation, organic farming, and integrated pest management can decrease dependence on

chemical inputs and lower the likelihood of pathogen contamination in food products (Ajayi et al., 2021). The implementation of these sustainable practices enhances public health while simultaneously strengthening agricultural systems against climate change and various environmental challenges. Alternatives to antibiotics in livestock production, including probiotics and vaccines, are gaining recognition as vital elements of sustainable farming practices. The excessive application of antibiotics in livestock management has been associated with the rise of antibiotic-resistant pathogens, presenting considerable threats to human health (Stevenson, 2023). Implementing probiotic treatments and vaccination programs allows farmers to improve animal health and minimise antibiotic use, which in turn reduces the chances of resistance development (Ajayi et al., 2021). The application of vaccines in poultry has demonstrated a significant reduction in the occurrence of *Salmonella* infections, leading to enhanced food safety outcomes (Zanet et al., 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the One Health approach offers a holistic framework for tackling the intertwined issues of human, animal, and environmental health. Through the promotion of cross-sector collaboration, the enhancement of surveillance systems and the advocacy for sustainable agricultural practices, various stakeholders can unite to address the risks linked to zoonotic diseases and advance public health outcomes. The incorporation of genomic tools and the sharing of data significantly improve our capacity to address emerging pathogens, leading to a more robust and secure global health environment.

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MANURE MANAGEMENT IN LIVESTOCK SYSTEMS: ASSESSING ONE HEALTH IMPACTS ON ENVIRONMENTAL CONTAMINATION AND HUMAN EXPOSURE

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REVIEW

Abstract

This review investigates the multifaceted environmental and human health implications of manure management, emphasizing the critical challenges presented by nutrient overload, greenhouse gas emissions, and the distribution of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and pathogens. Although the application of manure in agricultural systems is useful for soil fertility, it can result in substantial water contamination due to nutrient discharge, which contributes to eutrophication and the leaching of nitrates and phosphates into nearby groundwater. Furthermore, the review examines the role of inadequately managed manure in the production of greenhouse gas emissions, particularly methane and nitrous oxide, which contribute to the acceleration of climate change. Additionally, the review assesses the public health consequences of manure management, such as the occupational risks for farmers and labourers who are exposed to zoonotic pathogens and toxic gases, as well as the community's exposure to contaminated drinking water and food sources. The study also investigates the correlation between the application of manure and the development of foodborne illnesses, with a particular emphasis on the use of improperly treated manure as fertilizer and crops that are irrigated with an untreated effluent. In conclusion, this paper emphasizes the pressing necessity of sustainable manure management that is prioritized in integrated strategies that safeguard public health and environmental quality.

Keywords: Manure Management, One Health, Environmental Contamination

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INTRODUCTION

Livestock systems are critical in agriculture because they contribute significantly to food security and overall ecosystem health. Livestock are a significant source of protein and other necessary nutrients, and they support the livelihoods of millions of people worldwide, particularly in developing countries (Șonea, 2023a; Șonea 2023b; Gheorghe-Irimia, 2023; Tudor, 2023). Livestock integration into agricultural systems improves food production and resistance to climatic variability because livestock can use resources that are not suited for crop production, such as marginal lands and crop byproducts (Godfray et al., 2010). Furthermore, livestock systems improve soil fertility by applying manure, a natural fertilizer, and hence promote sustainable farming practices (Godfray et al., 2010; Liu, 2012). In addition to their direct benefits to

food security, livestock systems benefit a variety of socioeconomic elements. They generate revenue and employment opportunities, particularly for rural areas, which improves economic stability and reduces poverty (Kahn, 2011). The interconnection of livestock and crop production systems promotes a diverse agricultural landscape, which is critical for climate resilience and food security (Godfray et al., 2010; Hertel et al., 2021, Kahn, 2011). However, managing waste from livestock systems offers both benefits and challenges.

Manure is a rich resource that can be used as organic fertilizer, improving soil health while reducing the requirement for synthetic fertilizers (Godfray et al., 2010; Liu, 2012). Manure can improve soil structure, boost nutrient availability, and promote microbial diversity, all of which are necessary for sustainable agricultural operations (Godfray et al., 2010; Liu, 2012). On the other hand, inappropriate manure management can contaminate the environment, endangering

water quality and public health. For example, runoff from manure application can transfer pathogens and nutrients into water bodies, causing eutrophication and the development of waterborne diseases (Godfray et al., 2010; Liu, 2012). The concept of One Health is especially applicable in manure management since it emphasizes the interdependence of human, animal, and environmental health. One Health supports a collaborative approach to addressing health difficulties caused by interconnections between these domains (Pettan-Brewer et al., 2022). Effective manure management strategies must take into account the possible effects on public health, including antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and zoonotic diseases (Kalpana et al., 2023; Collignon and McEwen, 2019, Pettan-Brewer et al., 2022).

The importance of One Health goes beyond manure management to include the entire agricultural ecosystem. Recognizing the links between agriculture, health, and the environment allows stakeholders to collaborate to address complex concerns such as food security, climate change, and disease outbreaks (Pettan-Brewer et al., 2022). This comprehensive approach is critical for establishing sustainable agriculture methods that meet the nutritional needs of a growing global population while also maintaining environment and community health (Pettan-Brewer et al., 2022).

In this direction, the aim of this paper is to evaluate the One Health impacts of manure management practices in livestock systems, focusing on their role in environmental contamination and human exposure.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF MANURE MANAGEMENT

Nutrient overload and water contamination

The use of manure in agricultural activities can cause nutrient overload and subsequent water contamination. One of the main concerns is runoff from manure application, which contributes significantly to eutrophication in aquatic bodies. Eutrophication is defined as excessive nutrient enrichment, notably phosphorus and nitrogen, which causes algal blooms that decrease oxygen levels in aquatic environments and destroy aquatic life (Jahanzad et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019). Studies have shown that when manure is spread to fields, particularly

before rains, the nutrients can be washed away into neighbouring streams and lakes, worsening the problem of nutrient pollution (Wang et al., 2019; Johnson et al., 2011). For example, studies show that phosphorus loss from manured soils can be significant, especially if the manure is not properly mixed into the soil (Kumaragamage et al., 2012; Johnson et al., 2011). Another important concern with manure management is the leaching of nitrates and phosphate into groundwater. When manure is applied excessively or under inappropriate conditions, such as when the ground is frozen or saturated, nutrients can permeate through the soil and contaminate groundwater supplies (Haack et al., 2015; Varel et al., 2010). This leaching endangers not just water quality but also human health, as nitrates in drinking water can cause major health problems, including methemoglobinemia, also known as "blue baby syndrome" (Hilaire et al., 2022). Furthermore, the presence of phosphorus in groundwater might contribute to long-term impairment of surface water quality since it can be released into surface waters via groundwater discharge (Stocker et al., 2018). Case studies from diverse regions demonstrate the effects of manure mismanagement on water quality. For example, in California, concentrated animal feeding operations (CAFOs) have been connected to considerable water contamination caused by runoff from badly managed manure (Baek & Smith, 2019). Similarly, studies in the Midwest United States have demonstrated that improperly timed manure applications can cause high phosphorus levels in surface runoff, directly contributing to eutrophication in the Great Lakes (Johnson et al., 2011). These instances demonstrate the critical need for better manure management procedures to reduce water pollution hazards.

Greenhouse Gas Emissions & Climate Change

Manure management's environmental implications go beyond water contamination and include major contributions to greenhouse gas emissions. Methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) are two potent greenhouse gases generated from stored manure, especially in anaerobic conditions typical of manure storage facilities (Jokela et al., 2012; Song et al., 2010). Methane is created during the anaerobic

breakdown of organic matter in manure, whereas nitrous oxide emissions are predominantly caused by the application of nitrogen-rich manure to soils (Thiel et al., 2020). These gases have a substantially larger global warming potential than carbon dioxide, thus their management is crucial in terms of climate change mitigation (Guardian & Aga, 2019). Poorly managed manure systems increase the issue of global warming. For example, studies have found that methane and nitrous oxide emissions can be much greater when manure is not adequately stored or handled (Fahrenfeld et al., 2014). This emphasises the significance of using appropriate manure management strategies to limit these emissions. Anaerobic digestion can convert manure into biogas, collecting methane for energy consumption while limiting its escape into the atmosphere (Ghaly & Hattab, 2012). Furthermore, precise timing and methods of manure application can reduce nitrous oxide emissions by ensuring that crops use nitrogen efficiently (Vadas et al., 2017). Manure management plays an increasingly important role in reducing emissions, according to climate action plans. Farmers can cut greenhouse gas emissions greatly by using optimal management techniques, such as integrating manure into the soil rather than spreading it on the surface (Frentrup et al., 2021). Furthermore, incorporating manure management into crop production systems can improve nitrogen cycling, lowering the requirement for synthetic fertilisers and associated emissions (Hall et al., 2020). Overall, good manure management is critical for not just improving water quality but also mitigating climate change.

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) and Pathogen Spread

The presence of antimicrobial residues and resistant genes in manure poses a substantial risk to public health and the environment. Manure from livestock frequently contains antibiotic residues from animal husbandry, which can lead to the establishment and spread of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (Cavalcante et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2010). When manure is sprayed to fields, residues can enter soil and water systems, promoting the growth of resistant bacterial strains that can harm both human and animal health (Bojarski et al.,

2020). Research has shown that antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) can survive in the environment for long periods of time, creating persistent contamination threats (Hall et al., 2020; Hilaire et al., 2022). Pathogen contamination is another major worry with manure management. Manure can include a variety of diseases, including bacteria, viruses, and parasites, which can spread through soil, water, and air (Shrestha et al., 2019). For example, studies have shown that pathogens such as *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* can live in manure and be transmitted to water bodies via runoff, posing considerable public health hazards (Cardoso et al., 2012; Park et al., 2020). Such pathogens can spread not just through direct runoff, but also through the leaching of contaminated groundwater, affecting drinking water supplies (Song et al., 2010). The consequences of disease spread are severe, particularly in areas where agricultural activities are inextricably tied to water sources. For example, in the Kathmandu Valley, inappropriate sewage and agricultural runoff management has been related to enteropathogen pollution of water bodies, providing a public health risk (Shrestha et al., 2017). Effective manure management measures, such as vegetated filter strips and optimal application timing, can help lower the risk of disease transmission and pollution in nearby water bodies (Bai et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2011).

HUMAN HEALTH CONSEQUENCES

Occupational Hazards

The hazards associated with manure management are extensive and diverse, especially for farmers and personnel who have direct contact with manure. Handling manure exposes people to a variety of zoonotic pathogens, including *Salmonella*, *E. coli*, and *Campylobacter*, which can cause major health problems (Givens et al., 2016; McDaniel et al., 2014). These pathogens can be found in large quantities in animal waste, and direct exposure can occur during manure application, cleaning of animal housing, or even contact with infected equipment (Dungan, 2012). Furthermore, harmful gases such as ammonia and hydrogen sulphide, which are generated during manure decomposition, increase the risk of infection (Ko et al., 2010). According to

Śledź et al. (2017), ammonia can irritate the respiratory system and worsen pre-existing lung problems, whereas hydrogen sulphide, even at low quantities, can induce respiratory failure and death. Bioaerosols produced during manure management activities provide an additional occupational health risk. Land application of manure, composting, and even animal movement can aerosolise pathogens and particulate debris, which workers can then inhale (Dungan 2012). According to studies, workers who work close to livestock activities are more likely to get respiratory infections and other health problems as a result of inhaling these bioaerosols (Jahne et al., 2015). Endotoxins in the air, which are generated by manure, can also contribute to respiratory ailments and other health problems among agricultural workers (Ko et al. 2010). As a result of the occupational dangers linked with manure management, persons working in these areas must take protective measures and undergo health monitoring.

Community Exposure

Community exposure to manure-related health issues is a developing concern, particularly in terms of contaminating drinking water supplies and the food chain. Manure application on agricultural areas can cause pathogen and nutrient leaching into groundwater, contaminating drinking water sources (Zhang et al., 2020; Pandey et al., 2014). This contamination poses a serious public health risk since bacteria like *E. coli* and *Salmonella* can persist in groundwater for long periods of time, causing epidemics of gastrointestinal ailments in communities that rely on these water supplies (Samarajeewa et al., 2012). Furthermore, runoff from manure-treated fields can transport pathogens into surface water bodies, compounding water quality and safety concerns (Samarajeewa et al., 2012). In addition to water contamination, airborne particles and pathogens emitted during manure management can have a negative impact on respiratory health in surrounding areas. According to research, people who live near livestock operations have a higher rate of respiratory problems, such as asthma and chronic bronchitis, which are most likely caused by exposure to bioaerosols containing pathogens and particulate matter (Baghdadi, 2023; Jahne et al., 2015). Inhaling these airborne pathogens can have both acute

and chronic health effects, especially in vulnerable populations like children and the elderly (Baghdadi, 2023). As a result, the consequences of manure management go beyond occupational health issues to address broader community health concerns.

Link to Foodborne Illnesses

The contamination of crops by manure, particularly those irrigated with untreated wastewater or fertilised with poorly processed manure, is a serious public health concern. Manure can act as a reservoir for numerous diseases, which can then be transported to crops during irrigation or fertilisation processes (Givens et al., 2016; Jahne et al., 2016). For example, applying untreated or improperly treated manure to agricultural fields has been related to outbreaks of foodborne illnesses, as bacteria can remain in the soil and infect edible crops (Jahne et al., 2016; Seltenrich, 2017). This risk is especially high in areas where agricultural activities do not follow proper safety regulations for manure application (Seltenrich, 2017). Human pathogen exposure through the ingestion of contaminated produce can cause severe gastrointestinal ailments, putting a load on healthcare systems and affecting public health (Givens et al., 2016; Jahne et al., 2016). The Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has recorded multiple outbreaks associated with the consumption of fruits and vegetables contaminated with pathogens from manure (Jahne et al., 2016; Seltenrich, 2017). Furthermore, the increasing incidence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in manure raises additional concerns, as these resistance strains can be transmitted to people via the food chain, complicating illness treatment choices (Baghdadi, 2023; Garder et al., 2014). As a result, the links between manure management techniques and foodborne illnesses underline the importance of strict rules and best practices for ensuring food safety and protecting public health.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the health implications of manure management are substantial and intricate, covering occupational hazards for workers, community exposure to contaminated water and air, and associations with infectious diseases. This requires a comprehensive approach that includes public health education,

regulatory supervision, and enhanced manure management methods to mitigate the potential health risks associated with manure application and processing.

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BRIDGING THE GAP IN AMR: INTEGRATIVE CONTROL MEASURES FOR ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IN HUMAN, ANIMAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH

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REVIEW

Abstract

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents a significant global health threat, driven by the improper use of antibiotics in human healthcare, veterinary medicine, and environmental systems. This review consolidates current evidence on the diverse factors contributing to AMR, emphasizing the interconnected nature of human, animal, and environmental health within the framework of the One Health approach. Proposed solutions to address AMR include prudent antibiotic usage, robust waste management strategies, the advancement of vaccines and alternative therapies, and widespread educational initiatives targeting both healthcare professionals and the general public. Furthermore, the review highlights the critical role of international collaboration in data sharing and the development of regulatory frameworks to monitor and control AMR effectively. By targeting the underlying drivers of resistance and implementing integrated strategies, stakeholders can collectively reduce the impact of resistant pathogens and protect global health. Special attention is needed in low- and middle-income countries, where the AMR problem is disproportionately high, underscoring the importance of equitable and coordinated action.

Keywords: Antimicrobial Resistance, One Health, antibiotics

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INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents an escalating global health challenge, fuelled by the ability of microorganisms to withstand the antimicrobials that were once effective. The widespread and often inappropriate use of antimicrobial agents in clinical and agricultural settings has intensified this challenge, leading to infections that are becoming increasingly difficult to manage. Identified by the World Health Organisation (WHO) as one of the leading global public health threats, AMR could lead to an estimated 10 million deaths each year by 2050 if existing trends continue (Godinho, 2024). In addition to affecting personal health, AMR presents considerable challenges for healthcare systems, economies, and ecosystems (Vikesland et al., 2019; Ferri et al., 2015).

The intricacies of AMR arise from various elements, such as overprescription of antibiotics, inappropriate use in agriculture, and insufficient infection control measures. (Abbo &

Hooton, 2014, Brown et al., 2016; Saini et al., 2012). To tackle these challenges, it is essential to adopt a "One Health" approach that highlights the interrelation of human, animal, and environmental health (Matar et al., 2020).

The interconnected dynamics of AMR highlight the importance of understanding its transmission pathways and impacts. In agricultural contexts, antibiotic use not only fosters resistance in bacteria affecting livestock but also contaminates the environment, introducing resistant strains into ecosystems. These bacteria can enter the food supply and infect humans, complicating treatment efforts (Brown et al., 2016; Saini et al., 2012, Wang et al., 2023, Godinho, 2024; Wang et al., 2023, Vikesland et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023).

Socioeconomic factors significantly influence the prevalence and control of AMR. In numerous low- and middle-income nations, the accessibility of over-the-counter antibiotics alongside insufficient healthcare infrastructure leads to misuse (Ayukekbong et al., 2017). The lack of awareness among healthcare providers and the general public about AMR poses significant challenges to prevention and

stewardship initiatives (Waseem et al., 2019; Abera et al., 2014; Kraker et al., 2011; Kraker et al., 2011; Waseem et al., 2019; Ferri et al., 2015).

The aim of this review is to explore the multifaceted drivers and impacts of AMR across human, animal, and environmental sectors, emphasizing the interconnected nature of the problem.

AMR ACROSS SECTORS

The misuse of antibiotics in healthcare drives AMR. These vital medications are misused due to overprescription, patient demand, and poor diagnostic tools. Studies show that many antibiotics are useless, especially for viral illnesses when they have no therapeutic benefit (Smit, 2023). Misuse fails to treat infections and selectively pressures bacterial populations, promoting resistance.

Lack of timely diagnostic tools worsens the issue. Empirical prescribing without bacterial illness typically leads to needless broad-spectrum antibiotic use, which increases resistance (Sjöström et al., 2020). Lack of information among healthcare providers regarding AMR's long-term effects perpetuates overuse and poor management (Waseem et al., 2019; Abera et al., 2014).

The clinical effects of AMR are significant. Resistant infections like MRSA and ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* require sophisticated and expensive treatments with less effective or more hazardous alternatives (Kraker et al., 2011). AMR affects 33,000 Europeans annually, causing major economic and healthcare costs (Davies & Wales, 2019, Kasimanickam et al., 2021).

In many regions, antibiotics are administered not only to treat infections but also for growth promotion and disease prevention in healthy animals. These practices create selection pressure, encouraging the proliferation of resistant bacteria (Mshana et al., 2021; Tiseo et al., 2020).

Inadequate veterinary oversight and the indiscriminate use of antimicrobials exacerbate the problem. Resistant strains originating in animals can be transmitted to humans through direct contact, consumption of contaminated meat products, or environmental exposure (Smith et al., 2023; Rhouma et al., 2022). Moreover, antibiotic use in companion animals is a growing concern, as misuse by pet owners contributes to resistance in pathogens that can

cross the human-animal interface (Delalay et al., 2020).

The environmental impact of antibiotic use in agriculture is also significant. Resistant bacteria from livestock waste can contaminate soil and water systems, creating hotspots for resistance development (Nhung et al., 2015; Holvoet et al., 2013). Intensive farming practices with poor biosecurity measures further amplify the problem, necessitating stricter regulations and surveillance systems (Amin et al., 2020; Rhouma et al., 2022; Şonea, 2023a; Şonea, 2023b; Gheorghe-Irimia, 2023).

Agricultural runoff, hospital wastewater, and untreated sewage introduce resistant bacteria into natural ecosystems, where they persist and propagate (Holvoet et al., 2013; Guenther et al., 2011). Water systems, in particular, play a critical role in AMR dissemination. Contaminated water bodies not only affect aquatic ecosystems but also pose significant risks to human populations that rely on them for drinking and irrigation (Holvoet et al., 2013).

Soil contamination is another critical pathway. The application of manure from treated livestock can introduce resistant bacteria into agricultural soils, facilitating horizontal gene transfer and further resistance development within microbial communities (Nhung et al., 2015; Guenther et al., 2011). These bacteria can then affect crops, which may serve as another vector for AMR transmission to humans.

STRATEGIES FOR ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE (AMR) REDUCTION

A critical strategy in combating AMR is ensuring antibiotics are used responsibly and only when necessary. This involves selecting the appropriate drug tailored to the specific infection. Evidence demonstrates that antimicrobial stewardship interventions, such as educational campaigns and clinical guidelines, can significantly improve antibiotic prescribing practices (Durkin et al., 2018; Gerber et al., 2013). For example, simple measures like displaying informational posters in outpatient clinics have successfully reduced inappropriate prescriptions for conditions like acute respiratory tract infections (Durkin et al., 2018).

Additionally, adopting a "wait-and-see" approach, where antibiotics are delayed unless clinically warranted, has been shown to lower unnecessary antibiotic use while encouraging

patients to understand their appropriate application (Liu et al., 2019). Establishing stringent prescribing guidelines across healthcare and veterinary sectors is essential. In healthcare, implementing protocols that include regular audits and feedback mechanisms can help ensure adherence to evidence-based prescribing practices (Bello et al., 2021; Alkhuzaei et al., 2018). In veterinary medicine, regulations should restrict antibiotic use to prescription by licensed veterinarians and prohibit their application as growth promoters in livestock (Wilkinson et al., 2018).

Educational campaigns targeting both healthcare providers and the public are vital in fostering responsible antibiotic use. Research indicates that such interventions can significantly reduce antibiotic consumption (Velden et al., 2013; Zetts et al., 2020). For example, public awareness initiatives can inform individuals about the dangers of antibiotic misuse, while healthcare providers benefit from continuous training on stewardship principles, including appropriate prescribing and the use of diagnostic tools.

For healthcare professionals and farmers, tailored training programs are crucial. Healthcare providers should receive ongoing education on stewardship practices, while farmers should be trained in responsible antibiotic use under veterinary supervision. Collaborative initiatives that bring together these stakeholders can advance the One Health approach to addressing AMR (Watkins et al., 2019; Alkhuzaei et al., 2018).

Effective prevention of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) dissemination via environmental pathways necessitates the implementation of comprehensive waste management systems across healthcare, agricultural, and industrial sectors. Hospitals have effectively reduced environmental contamination by adopting engineering controls, including closed-system transfer devices (CSTDs) (Sessink, 2024). In agriculture, effective management of waste products, including composting and anaerobic digestion, can reduce the effects of antibiotic residues on soil and water systems (Watkins et al., 2019; Sessink, 2024).

Vaccination is essential for infection prevention and decreasing dependence on antibiotics. Vaccination against bacterial diseases can markedly reduce the occurrence of infections necessitating antibiotic intervention. Investment in vaccine research is essential,

especially for diseases lacking effective vaccines (Alanazi, 2023).

Vaccines in agriculture can effectively prevent diseases in livestock, thereby reducing the reliance on antibiotics. Alternative therapies, including probiotics, bacteriophage therapy, and herbal remedies, demonstrate potential in preventing or treating infections and mitigating the risk of resistance development (Alanazi, 2023; Tudor, 2023). Investigation into these alternatives should emphasise their effectiveness in both human and veterinary medicine.

Countries must share surveillance data, best practices, and strategies for antibiotic regulation and resistance management. International organizations, such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), provide critical frameworks for addressing AMR, offering resources to standardize interventions worldwide (Alanazi, 2023; Gerber et al., 2013).

Collaboration is particularly crucial for addressing socioeconomic disparities in low- and middle-income countries, where the AMR burden is often highest. Strengthening global research efforts to develop new antibiotics and alternatives, coupled with monitoring and regulating antibiotic use, is essential for mitigating the impact of AMR on public health systems (Alanazi, 2023; Gerber et al., 2013).

CONCLUSIONS

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents a complex global health challenge that demands urgent, collaborative, and thorough intervention. To tackle this challenge, it is essential to combine efforts across human, animal, and environmental health using a holistic approach. Essential strategies, including careful antibiotic administration, effective waste management, vaccination efforts, and the creation of alternative therapies, should be integrated with educational initiatives to enhance awareness and encourage behavioural transformation. Moreover, international cooperation is crucial for developing regulatory frameworks, exchanging surveillance data, and assisting low- and middle-income countries that are disproportionately impacted by AMR. Through the application of these strategies, stakeholders can reduce the effects of AMR, protect the effectiveness of antimicrobials, and secure sustainable public health results for future generations.

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ANNALS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ORADEA, FASCICLE: ECOTOXICOLOGY, ANIMAL SCIENCE AND FOOD SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY 2024

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REVIEW, RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Agricultural adaptation strategies and actions, included in the One Health concept, which are highlighted at the local and regional level are: the agrotechnical management of the genetic potential specific to varieties and hybrids, innovative breeding techniques of animal breeds, water and soil management, training of farmers and knowledge transfer, financial schemes, insurance, agrometeorological services, including the development of early warning systems. Adaptation strategies depend on the local context, region or country; limiting the discussion of options and measures to a single type of approach—"top-down" or "bottom-up"—may lead to unsatisfactory solutions for those areas affected by climate change but with few resources to adapt to it. Biodiversity-based or "ecologically intensive" agriculture and climate-smart agriculture are low-impact strategies with a strong ecological modernization of agriculture that aim to sustainably increase agricultural productivity and income while addressing the challenges interdependence of climate change and food security.

Keywords: climate change, One Health management, agriculture systems

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INTRODUCTION

Human activities contribute to current environmental problems such as climate change, degradation of natural resources, including soil degradation and biodiversity loss, and environmental pollution. According to the World Economic Forum Global Risks 2021–2022 perception survey, "Climate Action Failure" and "Extreme Weather" were identified as the 1st and 2nd worst risks on a global scale for the next 15 years. The world's population is currently growing and is projected to reach 9.5 billion by 2050, which represents a major challenge for socio-economic progress and requires expanding the contributions of all resources to meet the needs of such a large population growth.

Food security is one of the main problems of the 21st century and due to population dynamics, agricultural production, both food and non-food, will have to increase by 47% by 2050 compared to 2020.

Understanding the major changes in soil and plants due to climate change

In the plant:

Prolonged pedological drought can prevent the emergence of plants or can lead to the death of plants during the vegetation;

External temperatures (late frosts at the beginning of vegetation, very high temperatures correlated with drought or early frosts before harvesting) can completely destroy crops. Stressed plants turn from carbon dioxide consumers (as is normal) into carbon dioxide producing plants (a less obvious aspect when talking about CO₂ emissions);

Plants subjected to increasingly strong solar radiation suffer burns, on the background of which diseases set in or continue the process of dehydration (alteration of tissues and organs), leading to important harvest losses or the death of the plants. Atmospheric drought has a major impact on crops, especially in areas with a temperate-continental climate (such as Romania), acting particularly on reproductive organs or causing rapid water loss through evapotranspiration;

Strong winds and storms, in addition to moving air masses very quickly (which can have disastrous effects) are also the main sources of infestations with harmful agents that can be transferred from thousands of kilometers.

In the soil:

The number and spectrum of macro and micro-organisms is majorly influenced by the climatic evolution, eg: in periods with large day and night amplitudes, parasitic fungi develop more;

In periods of pronounced pedological drought, most of the bacteria die that are responsible for making nutrients available to plants;

The mineralization process of organic residues requires sufficient reserves of water and air in the soil;

Very high temperatures on the soil surface can lead to the appearance of burns on plants in the area of contact with the soil;

Most crop damage agents (weeds, diseases, insects, mites, etc.) multiply faster and are more virulent under climate change conditions;

Long periods of pedological drought can lead to the total loss of production and if the drought periods last for several years, the phenomenon of "desertification" appears.

The climate is changing because of the way people live today, especially in richer and more economically developed countries.

In the long term, widespread climate change may lead to regional conflict, famine and refugee movements, as food, water and energy resources may become scarce. Globally, up to a billion "climate refugees" could be driven from their homes and may need help, especially from wealthier nations.

Climate and agriculture influence each other. This mutual impact is more significant today as climate change and variability manifests itself on a large scale. Climate change is a huge challenge for agriculture. On the one hand, agriculture is a source of greenhouse gas emissions, on the other hand, it is extremely vulnerable to the impact of climate change as the ability of rural areas to provide adequate food, support economic development and providing a safe living environment for rural communities directly depends on the existence of favorable climatic conditions.

Climate change affects agriculture globally. Negative effects on agricultural production will be influenced by extreme weather events. The efficient management of these extreme phenomena is of particular importance for the agricultural production process. Subsistence agriculture will be particularly affected because it has less capacity

to adapt. This will cause the risk of starvation to increase.

European agriculture is also affected. Climate change is also a real concern for EU agriculture. Agriculture will face many challenges in the coming decades, such as:

- increasing international competition,
- liberalization of commercial policy
- the continued decline of the rural population in many regions.

Climate change adds to the already existing pressures. It is true that some of the effects of climate change could be beneficial for agriculture in certain regions of Europe, especially in northern areas, but most of the consequences are likely to be adverse and occur in regions already under socio-economic pressure and other environmental factors such as water scarcity. This unequal effect of global warming amplifies the economic differences between the rural regions of the European Union, produces a greater risk of land abandonment and regional marginalization.

The biggest impact of climate change on agriculture will come through water. Climate change may lead to a decrease in annual water availability in many parts of Europe as a result of reduced summer rainfall, mainly in southern areas and some parts of Central Europe. In Western Europe and the Atlantic areas, summers are likely to be drier and warmer, with reduced water resources during this season. Many EU countries, especially in the southern states, have practiced irrigation for hundreds of years - this being part of the agricultural tradition, but this sector will need irrigation technique revisions in the context of climate change. For several regions it may be necessary to increase the irrigated area to ensure continuous production. But there is no doubt that agriculture must continue to strive to improve water use efficiency to reduce losses.

The consequences of the increasing frequency of extreme weather events such as hail, heavy winter precipitation, heat waves and drought will be felt across Europe. The succession of floods, droughts and storms in recent years has demonstrated Europe's vulnerability to extreme conditions. Their frequency could increase in the short and medium term (up to 2040). Also, the risk of drought in the southern EU and the risk of flooding in Central and Northern Europe will increase.

The probability of reduced production, in some regions of the EU, the variability of

production, changes in the seasonal structure of production, possible increased costs for farmers are consequences of climate change that have negative effects on consumers.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The specialist literature consultation was carried out during 2023-2024, accessing electronic databases such as Google Scholar and Scientific Electronic Library, which contain summaries and full texts of studies related to the issue addressed. We also studied representative works, recognized worldwide. Relevant studies were selected to present the consequences of climate change in the period 2000-2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Good agricultural practices, integrated into the One Health concept, can reduce the vulnerability of crops to the effects of climate change. Climate variability and change must be addressed through the lens of daily agricultural activities, with the help of mitigation strategies and adaptation measures. Agricultural crops are vulnerable to exposure to limiting vegetation conditions generated by climatic extremes, are sensitive to their fluctuation and variability and depend on the ability to adapt to periods of thermal and water stress.

The benefits of choosing a sustainable management system, such as the One Health bioeconomic management, in the structure of crops and the choice of employment, include:

- adaptation of varieties/hybrids to the potential of ecological zones;
- direct effects on the physico-chemical and biological properties of the soil;
- reducing the risk of disease and pest transmission or weed development;
- efficient use of plant nutrients;
- agricultural land management through crop rotation, maintaining a ratio between the share of permanent and annual crops;
- prevention of water pollution through seepage and percolation outside the areas traversed by the plant root system, in the case of irrigated crops;
- protecting soils against erosion, surface runoff and crust formation on the surface;
- reducing the degree of erosion and maintaining agricultural production at constant values.

For the livestock sector, the code of good practices in agriculture recommends:

- large, sealed and properly equipped manure storage platforms;

- storing manure in cool and shady places;
- covering the basins with liquid residues to reduce ammonia emissions in the atmosphere by using impermeable tarpaulins;
- ensuring appropriate amounts of manure within farms specialized in its collection and processing;
- building some installations for capturing biogas, thus resulting in the reduction of methane emissions;
- outdoor grazing versus rearing in sheltered systems;
- educating and raising awareness among farmers about the consequences determined by the effects of climate change.

Climate change and the possible depletion of conventional energy sources have led to a new approach through the use of biofuels. They are obtained from renewable resources, i.e. from a raw material that can be permanently renewed

As a result of the increased heat and aggressiveness of the sun's rays, protected spaces must be equipped with shading nets to prevent this phenomenon. At the same time, favorable conditions were created for the aggressive development of diseases and pests, with growers having to apply repeated treatments with high cost prices and often with a negative impact on production, the environment and people. Because of the strong and frequent winds in recent years, growers have great problems with soil preparation, due to its strong settlement, leading to the evaporation of water and the main nutrients.

The main problem faced by Romanian farmers in the context of climate change is the fact that most of the time they cannot establish their crops in the optimal time. For example, in Braila county, in the cold protected spaces, the establishment of crops took place around April 1st, and in the field, around May 1st. Due to temperature drops and large oscillations between day and night, the establishment period of crops started to lag by 15-20 days, both for the protected spaces and for the field.

The use of Romanian varieties and their promotion in production can be a viable alternative for mitigating the negative effects of climate change.

Concerns and directions of action at the level of the European Union

There is a wide range of adaptation measures, from technological options to improved farm management practices, but also policy instruments (eg adaptation action plans). To cope with anticipated changes in climate conditions, agricultural producers can change their crop rotation for the best use of available water, adjust

sowing dates according to temperature and rainfall patterns, use crop varieties better suited to new weather conditions (eg more resistant to heat and drought) or they can plant small areas of shrubs or forests on arable land to reduce water runoff and act as windbreaks. It is also important to better inform agricultural producers about climate risks and feasible adaptation solutions. The member states of the European Union have already taken action to adapt. Much of the effort to date has focused on preventing the effects of extreme weather events, perceived as an imminent risk (such as flooding).

Agricultural producers cannot face the burden of climate change alone. Public policy must provide the right support so that agricultural producers adapt their agricultural structures and production methods and continue to provide services for the countryside. The Communal Agricultural Policy already contains constituent elements that should facilitate adaptation to climate change. Facilitating agricultural producers' access to risk management tools, such as insurance programs, that can help them cope with losses from weather-related disasters as a result of climate change. Rural development policies offer opportunities to offset the adverse effects that climate change can cause on agricultural producers and rural economies, for example by providing aid for investment in more efficient irrigation equipment. Agricultural and environmental programs to encourage better management of soil and water resources by agricultural producers are also important for adaptation.

One Health management and climate smart agriculture

Agricultural ecosystems, like other ecosystems, depend on biodiversity, and animal and plant species depend on sustainable agricultural landscapes. But in recent decades, due to intensive monoculture, agrobiodiversity has been reduced, along with the sowing of large areas of land with corn, wheat, rice, soybeans and others. It is estimated that in the 20th century, 75% of the

world's food crop diversity was lost due to the replacement of local varieties by genetically uniform, high-yielding varieties. Biodiversity-based agriculture, or "ecologically intensive agriculture", is an agricultural system that is based on a large biological diversification of cultivated species and that potentiates the intensification of ecological interactions between the components of the agroecosystem, contributing to productivity, fertility and resilience to disturbances external. Biodiversity-based agriculture, as a way of adapting to the current changing climate, is characterized by stimulating natural food chains and by reducing the use of chemicals.

To better adapt to climate change, farmers need to develop or transform their farming systems by replacing old procedures and practices with a suite of climate-smart technologies. Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) is an integrated agricultural approach to One Health bioeconomic management aimed at sustainable growth of agricultural productivity and income, solving the interrelated problems of food security and climate change, reorienting agricultural development to achieve climate change adaptation goals. Climate-smart agriculture includes a range of adaptations and mitigation practices aimed at sustainably increasing productivity (food, fiber and fuel production), reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving resilience and advancing national food security goals and development.

Climate-smart agriculture activities are a combination of technologies and practices implemented at the macro-economic level. These include traditional methods of sustainable agricultural practices and innovative agricultural technologies, such as conservation agriculture, biodiversity-based agriculture, water management and sustainable land management technologies. At the farm level, the implementation of climate-smart agriculture practices depends on the socio-economic environment, which in turn is influenced by institutional patterns, resource accessibility and climatic conditions.

yields, the significant reduction of the genetic potential for a whole series of crop plant species, the reduction of the arable land surface, economic losses and last but not least, increased labor and equipment costs.

The recommended strategies and actions for adapting agriculture to climate change, which can be implemented at the local and regional level, are agrotechnical management specific to the conditions existing at the farm level, water and soil management, training of

CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this paper was to carry out a brief analysis of the influence of climate change on agricultural systems currently practiced worldwide, and to promote the concept of One Health management, integrating the specificity of agriculture with other areas of economic life.

The negative impact of climate change is characterized by the capping of productive

farmers and knowledge transfer, financial schemes to stimulate the practice of agricultural systems that implement One Health bioeconomic management, agricultural insurance adapted to the risks identified by farmers, high-performance agrometeorological services, including the development of early warning systems.

Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) is an integrated agricultural approach to One Health bioeconomic management aimed at sustainable growth of agricultural productivity and income, solving the interrelated problems of food security and climate change, reorienting agricultural development to achieve climate change adaptation goals.

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